

Chapter 1. Setting the scene¹

Coordinating Lead Authors: Vanesa Rodriguez Osuna (Plurinational State of Bolivia / Germany), Jane Carter Ingram (United States of America).

Lead Authors: Indah Budiani (Indonesia), Edgar de Jesus (Philippines), Luis Inostroza (Chile/Czechia), Elikana Kalumanga Ngallaba (United Republic of Tanzania), Anouska Perram (Australia), Lisen Schultz (Sweden), Jay Shimshack (United States of America), Gabriella Teren (South Africa).

Fellows: Raphael Ayambire (Ghana), Priya Priyadarshini (India).

Review Editor: Rachel Fossbakk (Norway).

Contributing Authors: Emily McKenzie (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Sandra Díaz (Argentina).

Co-chairs of the assessment: Matt Jones (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Steve Polasky (United States of America), Ximena Rueda (Colombia).

Technical support unit: Alina Vera Paz, Érika Peñuela Vega, Olena Tarasova-Krasiieva, Orlando Vargas Rayo.

This chapter should be cited as: Rodriguez Osuna, V., Ingram J.C., Budiani I., de Jesus E., Inostroza L., Kalumanga Ngallaba E., Perram A., Schultz L., Shimshack J., Teren G., Ayambire R., Priyadarshini P. (2026). **Chapter 1: Setting the scene.** In: Methodological Assessment Report of the Impact and Dependence of Business on Biodiversity and Nature's Contributions to People of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Rueda X., Jones M., Polasky S., (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17074175>

The designations employed and the presentation of material on the maps used in the assessment do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries. These maps have been prepared or used for the sole purpose of facilitating the assessment of the broad biogeographical areas represented therein.

¹ Authors are listed with, in parentheses, their country or countries of citizenship, separated by a comma when they have more than one; and, following a slash, their country of affiliation, if different from that or those of their citizenship, or their organization if they belong to an international organization. The countries and organizations having nominated the experts are listed on the IPBES website (except for contributing authors who were not nominated).

Contents

Executive summary	1
1.1. Setting the scene	4
1.1.1. Purpose and intended audience	4
1.1.2. Significance of undertaking the business and biodiversity assessment	5
1.1.3. Linkages with the IPBES conceptual framework	9
1.1.4. Linkages with upcoming and existing IPBES assessments	9
1.2. Key concepts	12
1.2.1. Biodiversity and nature	12
1.2.2. Ecosystem services and nature’s contributions to people	12
1.2.3. Business.....	13
1.2.4. Financial institutions	14
1.2.5. Typology of business activity.....	14
1.2.6. Value chains	16
1.2.7. Business dependencies on nature	17
1.2.8. Business impacts on nature	18
1.2.9. Nature-related risks: physical, transition and systemic	20
1.2.10. Nature-related opportunities.....	23
1.3. Evolving business engagement with nature	25
1.3.1. Integration of climate and nature actions, including human rights interlinkages	26
1.4. Recent framings of the interactions between business, financial institutions and nature.	27
1.4.1. Initiatives and frameworks guiding business and financial institutions actions on nature	27
1.4.2. Implementing businesses and financial institutions action on nature: climate and biodiversity metrics, targets and policies	34
1.5. Elements of an enabling environment that supports positive outcomes for biodiversity..	36
1.5.1. Policy, legislation and regulatory frameworks.....	37
1.5.2. Economic and financial frameworks.....	38
1.5.3. Social norms, values and culture.....	39
1.5.4. Technology and data that enable business decisions.....	41
1.5.5. Capacity & knowledge	42
1.5.6. Partnerships and collaborations for transformative change	42
1.6. Summary	44
1.7. References	45

List of boxes

Box 1.1. Indigenous Peoples and local communities, Indigenous and local knowledge, and the business and biodiversity assessment	8
Box 1.2. IPLC businesses, traditional economies and livelihoods.....	13
Box 1.3. Business impacts on Indigenous Peoples and local communities	20
Box 1.4. Examples of emerging implications of artificial intelligence and machine learning for businesses’ interactions with biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people.	41

List of figures

Figure 1.1. Creating an enabling environment that supports businesses’ outcomes for nature and society.	8
---	----------

List of tables

Table 1.1. Typology of business activity by size, region and sector using the ISIC classification system.....	15
Table 1.2. Examples of Central Banks and Supervisors Assessing Nature-Related Portfolio Exposures in High-Dependency Sectors	22
Table 1.3. Selected voluntary market-led measurement and reporting initiatives	29

Executive summary

1. The global economy depends heavily on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people and the interconnected challenges of biodiversity loss and climate change pose growing risks to financial systems and the global economy worldwide {1.1.2, 1.2.9, 1.3.1}. Nature generates essential economic and social value through benefits such as food and fuel production, climate regulation, water purification, flood regulation, air filtration, and aesthetic beauty. An estimated \$ 44 to 58 trillion, or over half of global GDP, moderately or highly depends on ecosystem services. However, recent estimates likely understate the full economic value of the global dependency on biodiversity and the significant macroeconomic implications of biodiversity loss. Failing to account for, mitigate, and/or adapt to these risks poses significant threats to financial stability and the global economy. Biodiversity loss and climate change are closely intertwined, sharing common drivers and mutually amplifying their impacts on water, food, and health systems (IPBES, 2024d; Pörtner et al., 2021, 2023). Healthy and resilient ecosystems are vital for climate mitigation and adaptation, as they store and sequester carbon and reduce the impact of extreme weather events. In contrast, biodiversity loss weakens these natural capacities—reducing forests' and oceans' ability to store carbon and further accelerating climate change.

2. A failure to account for nature and integrate its value into economic and financial systems has led to its degradation and the unprecedented rates of biodiversity decline globally {1.1.2, 1.3}. Historically, the many values that nature provides to society have been invisible in the economy, financial system, and corporate balance sheets. The contributions of nature to market values are not comprehensively and/or explicitly recognized within national accounts and/or economic indicators such as gross domestic product. Similarly, the valuable contributions that nature provides to business value chains and operations are often missing from corporate financial statements and disclosures. This omission has contributed to policies, incentives, and pricing signals that disregard nature's values and, in many cases, lead to its degradation and loss.

3. Businesses have impacts and dependencies on biodiversity that vary by sector, size, structure and geography. Business impacts on biodiversity can be positive or negative {1.2.5, 1.2.6, 1.2.7, 1.2.8}. All businesses depend on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. The type and magnitude of dependencies vary across sectors, sub-sectors, ecosystems, and geographies. A dependency arises when businesses rely upon, or are affected or constrained by, nature's contributions to people, including ecosystem services. Financial institutions may depend on nature through the reliance of the businesses they invest in, lend to or insure. Business activities also impact biodiversity (reviewed in detail in Chapter 3). In this assessment, business impacts on biodiversity are defined as positive or negative changes in the quality or quantity of biodiversity resulting from land and sea use, direct exploitation of organisms, climate change, pollution, or the introduction of invasive alien species. Such impacts may result in changes to the capacity of biodiversity to support social, economic and cultural functions. Businesses' impacts on biodiversity include direct, value chain, indirect and cumulative impacts and can be negative or positive, although evidence shows most impacts have been negative

4. Business impacts and dependencies on biodiversity can result in a range of physical and transition risks that have financial implications for organizations {1.2.9}. Business's nature-related risks refer to the "potential threats posed to an organization that arise from its and wider society's dependencies and impacts on nature". These risks may manifest as physical, transition, and systemic risks for a business. Nature-related physical risks to an organization result from the degradation or loss of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people that businesses depend on.

These can be acute in the case of a short-term event or chronic if they involve longer-term shifts in the state of biodiversity. Nature-related transition risks to an organization may result from a misalignment of business behaviours or actions with efforts to conserve, restore or sustainably use biodiversity. These types of risks can be prompted by changes in regulation and policy, legal precedent, technology, or investor sentiment and consumer choices that may cause adverse business consequences. Systemic risks emerge from disruptions that collectively lead to the collapse of the whole system. Despite growing awareness of the systemic risks that biodiversity loss poses to the global economic and financial system, there is still limited clarity on how these risks translate into businesses' balance sheets. However, a growing body of literature is developing on how systemic risks can be assessed and translated for businesses and financial institutions.

5. Business impacts and dependencies on biodiversity can also result in a range of opportunities that have financial implications for organizations {1.2.10}. Nature-related opportunities for businesses and financial institutions can arise from both their dependencies and impacts on biodiversity and refer to activities that create positive outcomes for organisations and biodiversity. Opportunities may include the strategic transformation of business models, products, services, markets, and financing mechanisms that deliver biodiversity benefits or activities that avoid, reduce, mitigate or manage nature-related risks. Potential opportunities for businesses stemming from their impacts and dependencies will vary across sectors, geography, local social and cultural contexts, and market and economic factors. A growing number of examples demonstrate opportunities that can deliver positive outcomes for businesses, biodiversity, and other stakeholders.

6. Businesses also impact IPLCs through the impacts and dependencies that they have on nature. These impacts can be positive or negative, with most impacts throughout history being negative {1.2.8.2}. Business impacts on biodiversity – both negative and positive – can create costs, benefits, risks and opportunities for the business as well as a range of affected stakeholders. The distribution of the benefits and costs of business impacts on biodiversity is unequal over time and space, and perceptions of what constitutes a good quality of life, as well as the value of nature, vary among different groups. Business activities may bring benefits to some groups while negatively affecting the quality of life of others. For example, IPLCs and the urban populations (often composed of ethnic minorities) have often been negatively impacted by industrial activities. Unsustainable business practices can also compromise the quality of life of future generations. These impacts can lead different groups to change their behaviour in ways that either amplify or counteract the initial impact on biodiversity. To navigate these interactions, businesses need to consider the interconnected relationships between social and environmental impacts.

7. Few businesses currently understand and actively manage their impacts and dependencies on nature leaving many businesses exposed to unmitigated risks and unrealized opportunities {1.1.2, 1.2.7, 1.2.9, 1.2.10}. Few businesses have assessed their impacts on biodiversity and even fewer have assessed their dependencies on biodiversity. Because many dependencies on biodiversity can be intangible and/or difficult to measure, they are often underrepresented in decision-making. Methods for assessing dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people are generally less advanced than those for assessing impacts on biodiversity. Most available methods for quantifying business dependencies on nature focus on direct dependencies, with fewer approaches available for assessing dependencies within value chains, as discussed in Chapters 3 and 4. Because impacts and dependencies on nature can lead to a range of risks and opportunities, understanding these interactions can be important for informing business decisions, policies, and actions that may have financial implications for an organization.

8. Most business actions related to managing negative impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people have been historically driven by regulation. More recently, businesses have focused on identifying and assessing nature-related risks and piloting these through voluntary disclosure and reporting initiatives {1.3, 1.3.2, 1.3.3, 1.4}. Throughout much of recent history, policy and regulations have mostly focused on the negative impacts that businesses may have on biodiversity and, thus, business actions have focused on reducing or managing their negative impacts. As businesses and financial institutions increasingly recognise their impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and the business value that nature-related opportunities and risks present –some are taking voluntary measures that go beyond regulatory requirements. For example, voluntary market-led initiatives for measuring and reporting on biodiversity are catalysing business and financial institutions' efforts to understand, identify, assess, disclose, and manage nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks and opportunities. While voluntary disclosures can drive greater understanding, accountability and transparency, they are not always effective at driving action in the absence of a strong enabling environment. Business actions and policies on biodiversity continue to lag behind reporting trends.

9. Transformative change is needed to conserve and restore nature in alignment with the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. All actors in society will have to work together to advance an enabling environment in which businesses can contribute to the transformative changes needed to achieve a just and sustainable future {1.5}. Governments, the financial system, and other actors, (including civil society and IPLCs) have to work together, with businesses and financial institutions to promote and ultimately deliver the global systemic and transformative changes needed to support businesses' efforts to contribute to the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity and the objectives of the Convention on Biological Diversity.

1.1. Setting the scene

1.1.1. Purpose and intended audience

The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) approved the undertaking of the business and biodiversity assessment at its ninth Plenary session in 2023. This decision was outlined in the ‘Scoping report for a methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people’ (IPBES, 2023b).

The purpose of this methodological assessment (hereafter referred to as the business and biodiversity assessment) is to strengthen knowledge on the relationships between businesses and biodiversity. It includes a critical review and evaluation of the diverse ways in which businesses depend on and impact biodiversity and methods to measure this interaction—including those occurring throughout value chains. The assessment also explores how this information can support businesses and financial institutions in making decisions that lead to better outcomes for biodiversity. Finally, it examines the roles of governments, the financial system, businesses and other stakeholders in creating an enabling environment for such improvements. Considerations of these issues as they relate to people, including Indigenous Peoples and local communities (‘IPLCs’), are integrated into the assessment.

The primary audience of this assessment includes governments, businesses, and financial institutions. In addition, the assessment is intended to be of value to civil society and IPLCs in their interactions with businesses.

The assessment aims to support efforts to achieve the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity—living in harmony with nature—, and the objectives of the Convention on Biological Diversity: the conservation of biological diversity, the sustainable use of its components, and the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of the utilization of genetic resources. It also seeks to enhance businesses’ contributions toward just and sustainable futures, in line with global policy goals and frameworks such as the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and its Sustainable Development Goals², the Convention on Biological Diversity and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework³, and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change⁴ and the Paris Agreement⁵. Hereafter, we refer more concisely to these global policy goals and frameworks as the Sustainable Development Goals, the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, and the Paris Agreement. Underscoring urgency, it highlights the need for enhanced business engagement in order to address the unprecedented decline in biodiversity globally.

A key consideration of this assessment is the clear link between biodiversity loss and climate change, which exacerbate each other, with common causes and effects on one another (Pörtner et al., 2021, 2023; Weiskopf et al., 2024a) and with implications for water, food and health (IPBES, 2024d; UNEP, 2023b). Functioning and resilient ecosystems play an important role in both mitigating and adapting to climate change by storing and sequestering carbon and reducing the impact of extreme weather events (IPBES, 2024d; Pörtner et al., 2021). For example, when biodiversity declines, forests and oceans lose their capacity to store carbon, leading to higher greenhouse gas levels and further accelerating climate change (IPBES, 2024d).

² Resolution adopted by the United Nations General Assembly, A/RES/70/1

³ Adopted by the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity, in decision CBD/COP/DEC/15/4

⁴ United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 1771, No. 30822

⁵ Adopted by the Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, Decision 1/CP.21, FCCC/CP/2015/10/Add.1

Chapter 1 provides a common framework for this assessment and lays out the context for understanding how businesses interact with biodiversity. It gives an overview of how business engagement on biodiversity has evolved, including through initiatives and frameworks. Additionally, it presents a definition of business—including financial institutions—and introduces a typology of business activities based on size, geography and sector for use within this assessment. Finally, the chapter defines key terms and gives examples of risks and opportunities that arise from interactions between businesses and biodiversity⁶.

1.1.2. Significance of undertaking the business and biodiversity assessment

The significant value of nature and its importance for national economies and businesses globally is increasingly recognized (Dasgupta, 2021, 2025; WEF & PWC, 2020; World Bank Group, 2021) alongside the substantial risks that nature loss poses to the global economy (Alvarez et al., 2025; Ranger et al., 2023; TNFD, 2025d; United Nations Global Risk Report, 2024; WEF, 2024). Nature generates immense economic and social value by providing key benefits such as food production, carbon sequestration, and water and air purification. According to recent research, these services alone are valued at over \$150 trillion per year – roughly twice the global Gross Domestic Product (BCG, 2021). Other reports estimate \$58 trillion of global annual economic activity (value in 2023), equivalent to over half of global gross domestic product, is tied to sectors depending moderately or highly on nature and its services (IPBES, 2024d; PwC, 2023). These estimates likely understate the full economic value of the global dependency on nature and the significant macroeconomic implications of nature loss. Failing to account for, mitigate, and/or adapt to these risks poses a threat to financial stability (NGFS, 2023a, 2024a, 2024b). More generally, no economy or community could function without nature's contributions to people, such as food, fuel, water, clean air, and fertile soils (IPBES, 2018b, 2018c, 2018d, 2018e; Ranger et al., 2023; Dasgupta, 2021).

This should be seen in the context of growth in global economic activity which has outstripped human population growth. Since 1992, human-produced capital (e.g., buildings and machinery) that improves economic productivity has increased by approximately 100 per cent per capita on average though with wide disparity among countries – while stocks of natural capital (ecosystems and natural resources) have been reduced by nearly 40 per cent (Dasgupta, 2021; IPBES, 2019a; Managi & Kumar, 2018).

However, current economic and financial systems indirectly incentivize investments that harm biodiversity that supports water, food, human health, and climate regulation (Dasgupta, 2020). These harmful financial flows are estimated at up to \$7.3 trillion per year (in 2023), whereas only about \$220 billion is directed towards activities that have positive impacts (IPBES, 2024d; UNEP, 2023b, 2026). The private sector was responsible for the majority of the nature-negative finance flows in 2023, equivalent to approximately \$4.9 trillion and around \$2.4 trillion in public sector finance flows through subsidies were directed towards environmentally harmful activities (IPBES, 2024d; UNEP, 2023b, 2026). The degree to which sectors are sustainably managed, however, differs widely and some subsidies to these sectors may improve biodiversity outcomes (World Bank Group, 2023).

One reason why significant financing continues to flow towards activities that degrade biodiversity and not enough flows towards its protection is the invisibility of biodiversity in the economy, financial system and corporate balance sheets. This omission has led to policies, incentives and pricing signals that disregard nature's values and, in many cases, lead to its degradation and loss (Dasgupta, 2021; UNEP, 2010). For example, the contributions of nature to market values are not comprehensively and/or explicitly recognized within national accounts and/or economic indicators such as gross

⁶ A detailed explanation and comprehensive review of the process for selecting the literature for this chapter can be found in the data management report <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12785911>

domestic product (Dasgupta, 2021). Similarly, the valuable contributions that nature provides to business value chains and operations are often missing from corporate financial statements and disclosures. For example, a study analysing more than 800 businesses between 2022 and 2024 showed that only 5 percent had measured and understood their impacts on biodiversity and just 1 per cent assessed their dependencies on biodiversity (WBA, 2024). Understanding a company's impacts and dependencies on nature is important because they can result in a range of risks and/or opportunities for the business (TNFD, 2023c).

Negative externalities—costs not included in market prices or decision-making—across the fossil fuel, agriculture, and fisheries sectors are estimated at \$10–25 trillion per year (IPBES, 2024d). These reflect significant harmful impacts on biodiversity, climate, water, and human health (IPBES, 2024e). One study estimated that the unpriced business impacts on biodiversity, including unsustainable land and water use, greenhouse gas emissions, air pollution and waste that can degrade natural capital amounted at approximately \$7.3 trillion per year (using 2009 values) (Trucost, 2013). Mismanagement of nature-related issues by 10 large businesses alone has resulted in financial losses of \$83.2 billion, stemming from the physical risks associated with business dependencies on biodiversity and the transition risks resulting from business impacts on biodiversity (BloombergNEF, 2023). A growing body of evidence now exists on the financial effects of nature-related risks for businesses across sectors, geographies, and time horizons, which include impacts on revenues, costs, asset values and access to capital (Alvarez et al., 2025). Thus, several studies have documented the financial reasons for businesses and financial institutions to address nature-related risks and opportunities.

As attention to the financial and economic importance of biodiversity grows, businesses will need clear, science-backed approaches, indicators, tools and metrics for effective decision-making (EREA, 2024; TEEB, 2012a). Numerous frameworks, methods and tools now exist to support businesses to better understand, manage and disclose their interactions with biodiversity (Beck-O'Brien & Bringezu, 2021; IUCN, 2023; Katic et al., 2023; Science Based Targets Network, 2024; TNFD, 2023d). Legal reporting requirements on biodiversity risks and impacts are progressing but with mixed signals across regions. For example, all French financial institutions must disclose both biodiversity- and climate-related risks and impacts (LOI n° 2019-1147 du 8 novembre 2019 relative à l'énergie et au climat (1), 2019). The European Union's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive initially marked a major step toward greater corporate transparency and accountability on environmental and social risks (European Union, 2022). However, recent changes have weakened its ambition as under the European Commission's Omnibus package about 80 per cent of businesses are excluded from the Directive's scope and delays mandatory biodiversity disclosures by two years, limiting reporting to only the largest companies (European Commission, 2025a, 2025c). While presented as simplification, this shift reduces visibility of climate- and nature-related risks across value chains and constrains the ability of businesses and financial institutions to assess physical and transition risks using consistent, comprehensive data (IIGCC et al., 2025).

Increasing understanding and consistency across different approaches, frameworks and tools available for businesses is important for effective, transparent, coherent and robust environmental governance (IPBES, 2024a). These efforts need to account for regional, ecosystem and sector-specific challenges. They also need to consider the capacity, technical and technological differences among businesses, including micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises, as well as those of IPLCs and marginalized populations (IPBES, 2024a; IPBES et al., 2023). Businesses also can benefit from and have the opportunity to enhance their understanding of diverse values, worldviews and different approaches to valuing nature, while recognizing the contributions of IPLCs (Chettri & Sharma, 2022; Forest Peoples Programme et al., 2020; Khalvati et al., 2011; Pascual et al., 2023). This assessment evaluates approaches to measure the interlinkages between businesses and biodiversity to enhance

understanding, consistency, reporting and management of the ways in which businesses depend on, impact and interact with biodiversity. This evaluation also incorporates diverse knowledge systems, including Indigenous and local knowledge (**Annex 1.1**).

The adoption of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework in 2022 highlighted the importance of these issues and the need for enhanced business involvement to address unprecedented global declines in biodiversity (CBD, 2022; IPBES, 2019a). The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework adopts a 'whole of society approach' and each of the goals and targets are relevant not only to businesses individually but also to all sectors of the economy and society. Target 15 of this Framework emphasizes the need for businesses to identify, assess, and reduce their biodiversity-related risks and negative impacts while enhancing positive outcomes for biodiversity. This involves implementing legal, administrative or policy measures that mandate regular monitoring, transparent disclosure, and reporting on biodiversity dependencies and impacts, especially for large and transnational businesses and financial institutions, to drive sustainable production and consumption (CBD, 2022).

The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework also identifies an overall finance gap for biodiversity of \$700 billion each year – the difference between current biodiversity-related financial flows and future investment needs by 2030 (IPBES, 2019a). The IPBES Nexus Assessment estimates this biodiversity finance gap to range from \$300 billion to 1 trillion annually (IPBES, 2024e). These figures highlight a major need and an opportunity to repurpose capital and unlock new financial flows to support biodiversity. As specified in Target 18, this requires eliminating, phasing out or reforming phasing out or reforming subsidies that are harmful to biodiversity by at least \$500 billion annually, while increasing positive incentives for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity. Positive incentives include economic, legal or institutional measures such as land purchases supported by public funds or grants, and legal agreements to preserve natural areas (CBD, 2022). Target 19 calls for mobilising at least \$200 billion each year in domestic, international, public and private biodiversity-related funding (CBD, 2022).

Achieving the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework's goals and targets requires transformative change across all levels of society, including national governments, subnational and local authorities, civil society, individuals, businesses and financial institutions. Transformative change is defined as "fundamental, system-wide shifts in views, structures, and practices" (IPBES, 2024c). When deliberately pursued for a just and sustainable world, such change can address the root causes of loss and decline of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. At the same time, it is essential to recognize and strengthen existing views, structures, and practices that already align with sustainability – such as those of many IPLCs.

For businesses to participate in the transformative changes needed to halt and reverse biodiversity loss, the conditions under which they operate must be fundamentally reshaped. Creating an enabling environment⁷ with strong incentives for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity can align business profitability with positive outcomes for biodiversity and society. These enabling conditions span legal and regulatory, economic and financial, norms and values, technology and data, as well as capacity and knowledge (**Figure 1.1**). Such an enabling environment depends on coordinated action by governments, the financial system, other actors including civil society and IPLCs, and businesses themselves.

⁷ This categorization builds on the IPBES Nexus Assessment, which defines enabling conditions across six areas: Financing Incentives, Equity, Data and Technology, Capacity, Norms and Values, and Policies and Regulations (IPBES, 2024d). However, for this assessment, we have refined these categories to specifically reflect enabling conditions important for business.

Figure 1.1. Creating an enabling environment that supports businesses' outcomes for nature and society.

Box 1.1. Indigenous Peoples and local communities, Indigenous and local knowledge, and the business and biodiversity assessment

At least 32 per cent of land globally is owned or governed, either legally or under customary arrangements, by IPLCs. Some 91 per cent of IPLCs' lands are in good or moderate ecological condition, with 65 per cent being ecologically intact. Nature managed by IPLCs is therefore globally significant (WWF et al., 2021). The state of nature on IPLCs' lands reflects the fact that many IPLCs hold values and worldviews that differ from those that often dominate global political and economic decision-making - and which are often ignored (IPBES, 2022a). These diverse values such as prioritising a reciprocal and harmonious relationship with nature and social equity, inform their social, cultural and economic activities, including their business activities (IPBES, 2023a; IPBES et al., 2024). IPLCs' close relationships with land and nature also mean that they have developed dynamic bodies of integrated, holistic, social and ecological knowledge, practices and beliefs pertaining to the relationship of living beings, including people, with one another and with their environments, known as Indigenous and local knowledge. Improved acknowledgment and integration of their values and perspectives can support transformative change (IPBES, 2022a).

However, the nature managed by IPLCs is under increasing pressure, including from a range of business activities (IPBES, 2019b; WWF et al., 2021). In practice, this often manifests in the encroachment of

business activities on their lands and resources, with significant social, cultural, economic and environmental consequences (IPBES et al., 2023, 2024). As a result, nature on many IPLC lands is declining - although still more slowly than in other areas (IPBES, 2019b).

Protecting and restoring IPLCs' collective custodianship of land, resources and nature and creating space for their values, cultures and own economic activities and businesses to flourish, and increasing their influence decision-making in relation to business activities, is therefore critical to stemming the loss of nature.

The involvement of IPLCs in the production of this assessment is described in *Annex 1*

1.1.3. Linkages with the IPBES conceptual framework

The business and biodiversity assessment builds on the IPBES conceptual framework (Díaz et al., 2015), which addresses how nature and its contributions to people underpin a good quality of life for humanity (IPBES, 2018b, 2018c, 2018d, 2018e, 2019a).

This assessment covers five direct drivers of the loss and change of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people by business operations, including those related to: 1) changing land/sea use, 2) unsustainable exploitation of biodiversity, 3) climate change, 4) pollution, and 5) introduction of invasive alien species. Since 1970, land-use change (mostly driven by agricultural conversion) has had the most significant negative impact on terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems (IPBES, 2019a). In marine ecosystems, fishing has had the greatest negative impact on nature in the past 50 years (target species, non-target species and habitats) (IPBES, 2019a).

These five direct drivers result from various causes, known as indirect drivers, which are shaped by worldviews, societal values and behaviours. These indirect drivers include demographic and sociocultural, economic and technological, institutions and governance, and conflicts and epidemics (Bjelle et al., 2021; IPBES, 2019a; Marques et al., 2019; Wiedmann et al., 2013). Both indirect and direct drivers are influenced by underlying causes of biodiversity loss stemming from a disconnection from and domination over nature, the concentration of power and wealth, and the prioritization of short-term, individual and material gains over long-term sustainability (IPBES, 2024b). Collectively, these factors are leading to an unprecedented decline of biodiversity (1 million animal and plant species at risk of extinction, many within decades, and decline in most of nature's contributions to people, on which businesses and society depend) (IPBES, 2019a). Transformative change must address these underlying causes and the indirect and direct drivers they influence to achieve a just and sustainable world (IPBES, 2024c).

1.1.4. Linkages with upcoming and existing IPBES assessments

This assessment builds on previous work and summarizes the current state of knowledge on how businesses depend on and impact biodiversity, which can create business risks and opportunities. Upcoming IPBES assessments focus on contributing and supporting national and global efforts to monitor biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, as well as supporting countries and other actors in tracking progress and contributions towards the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and the Sustainable Development Goals. Existing IPBES assessments have highlighted connections between businesses and biodiversity from various perspectives. This includes highlighting the direct drivers of biodiversity loss to which businesses contribute, which are changes in land and sea use, unsustainable direct exploitation of organisms, climate change, pollution, and invasion of alien species as identified in the IPBES Global Assessment (IPBES, 2019a).

The IPBES Transformative Change Assessment identified three underlying causes of biodiversity loss: disconnection from nature, concentration of power and wealth, and prioritization of short-term

individual and material gains. It also underscores the urgent need to address interconnected crises – the loss and decline of biodiversity, and the projected collapse of key ecosystem functions – through transformative action. Overcoming these challenges requires not only changes in actions and strategies but also shifts in underlying values, worldviews, and systems. The Transformative Change assessment offers insights for governments, businesses, civil society, IPLCs on how to engage with transformative change for a just and sustainable world (IPBES, 2024b).

The Nexus Assessment evaluates the complex interlinkages between biodiversity loss, water availability and quality, food insecurity, risks to health, and climate change (IPBES, 2024e). It underscores the importance of nexus approaches in addressing these linked challenges, preventing isolated decisions that could lead to misalignment, trade-offs, or unintended consequences (IPBES, 2024e).

The Assessment on Invasive Alien Species and their control further identifies businesses as drivers responsible for the introduction and spread of invasive species between and within countries, specifically through global trade (IPBES, 2024a). The Methodological Assessment on Diverse Values and Valuation on Nature emphasizes the need to shift the values associated with political and economic decision-making, including those by businesses, to be more aligned with sustainability goals, and highlights different pathways for achieving this, including green economies, degrowth, earth stewardship and biodiversity protection (IPBES, 2022a).

The IPBES Assessment on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species provides a detailed description of the various extractive activities such as fishing, gathering, logging and terrestrial animal harvesting that often result in exploitative use of wild species (IPBES, 2022d). Sustainable use of wild species, therefore, calls for diversification of global value chains, policy instruments that effectively regulate resource extractive activities and the recognition of biocultural practices of IPLCs as necessary for promoting sustainable use (IPBES, 2022d).

Several IPBES assessments focus on documenting the importance of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people for economies at regional scales across each continent (IPBES, 2018b, 2018c, 2018d, 2018e) and at the global scale (IPBES, 2019a). The Global Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services provide a useful summary of status and trends of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, making clear that measures of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people have shown declines for decades. This IPBES Global Assessment made also clear that more than 90 per cent of deforestation worldwide is primarily driven by the expansion of agricultural commodities (IPBES, 2019a). Between 1980 and 2000, one hundred million hectares of tropical forest were lost, mainly as a result of cattle ranching in Latin America and plantations in Southeast Asia (80 per cent of which are for palm oil) (IPBES, 2019a). These assessments serve as important resources in biodiversity-related decision-making (CBD, 2022). They also elaborate on management and policy options, including the role of business activities in halting or reversing biodiversity loss.

The Assessment of Land Degradation and Restoration acknowledges that land degradation drivers and processes vary in severity both within and between countries and impacts the full range of human-altered systems, including drylands, agricultural and agroforestry systems, savannahs, forests and aquatic systems associated with these areas (IPBES, 2018a). Business-related drivers and processes (which the present assessment can help better establish) are also relevant to inform progress towards land degradation neutrality by 2030.

The Assessment of Pollinators, Pollination and Food Production highlights that more than three quarters of leading global food crops rely to some extent on pollinators for yield and/or quality. Furthermore, animal pollination directly contributes to 5-8 per cent of current global crop production, with a market value at \$ 235 – 577 billion (in 2015). It also highlights that current intensive

agricultural practices threaten pollination. Adopting sustainable agricultural practices and reversing the simplification of agricultural landscapes are key strategies to address the risks associated with pollination decline. These insights are particularly relevant for businesses involved in the food and agriculture sector (IPBES, 2016a).

The Methodological Assessment of Scenarios and Models highlighted “fit-for-purpose” qualitative and quantitative scenarios and models to produce knowledge and evidence for informed policymaking, including business strategy development. It also recommended that all stakeholders, including the private sector, build capacity in the use of fit-for-purpose scenarios and models and improve accessibility of data sources (IPBES, 2016b).

1.2. Key concepts

A clear and common understanding of key terms such as nature, biodiversity, ecosystem services, natural capital, nature's contributions to people, and businesses are needed as a starting point to understand the interaction of businesses and financial institutions with nature.

1.2.1. Biodiversity and nature

The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, 2011) defines “biodiversity” as the variability among living organisms from all sources including, *inter alia*, terrestrial, marine and freshwater ecosystems, and the ecological complexes of which they are part. This includes diversity within species (genetic diversity), between species, and of ecosystems.

Nature underpins and sustains human quality of life. Nature, in the context of IPBES, refers to the natural world with an emphasis on the diversity of living organisms and their interactions among themselves and with their environment (Díaz et al., 2015). Non-living components of the natural world that do not interact closely with living organisms, such as deep aquifers, mineral and fossil reserves, and wind, solar, geothermal and wave power, are also part of nature, but not the focus of IPBES (Brondizio et al., 2019; Díaz et al., 2015; IPBES, 2019a).

The degree to which humans are considered part of nature varies considerably across disciplines and knowledge systems (Brondizio et al., 2019; Díaz et al., 2015). Within the context of natural sciences, nature includes categories such as biodiversity, species, genotypes, populations, ecosystems, the biosphere, ecosystem functioning, communities, biomes, Earth life support's systems, and their associated ecological, evolutionary, biogeochemical processes and biocultural diversity. Within the framework of economics, it includes categories such as biotic natural resources, natural capital and natural assets (Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2023). Within a wider context of social sciences and humanities and interdisciplinary environmental sciences, it is referred to within categories such as natural heritage, living environment, or the nonhuman. Within the context of other knowledge systems, it includes categories such as Mother Earth (shared by many IPLCs around the world), and Pachamama (South American Andes), among many others. Nature's intrinsic values are independent of any human considerations of its worth or importance, whereas instrumental and relational values are human-centered (Pascual et al., 2017).

This assessment predominantly uses the term “nature”, particularly when referring to the natural world in general. The term “biodiversity” is used in specific contexts where it is more appropriate, such as when describing approaches for measuring distinct components of biodiversity.

1.2.2. Ecosystem services and nature's contributions to people

Nature's contributions to people refer to all of the contributions, positive and negative, of nature to people's quality of life (Díaz et al., 2015, 2018). Ecosystem services, a term widely used in the economic and ecological literature, and in the business community, are defined as the benefits that people obtain from ecosystems (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2003). The two concepts overlap in describing people's dependence on nature. The inclusive concept of nature's contributions to people adopted by IPBES fully includes ecosystem services as one culturally relevant concept of people-nature interactions (Brondizio et al., 2019; Díaz et al., 2018; Hill et al., 2021).

This assessment uses the broader term “nature's contributions to people”, unless there is a reason to specify ecosystem services. For example, where a particular study has segmented and referred to

individual ecosystem services, or where the term is part of the name or methodology of an approach, the term “ecosystem services” is used.

1.2.3. Business

There is no universally accepted definition of business or a typology of business, generally or for the specific purpose of assessing impacts and dependencies between businesses and biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.

For the purposes of this assessment, business is defined as an entity that is voluntarily involved in the production, exchange and distribution of goods or services that are sold for currency (Donaldson & Walsh, 2015). This definition naturally includes for-profit businesses taking part in regular monetary transactions for purposes that include creating profit. The definition also encompasses state-owned enterprises that engage in the production, exchange and distribution of goods and services for sale to satisfy objectives that may include broader national welfare goals (Boardman & Vining, 1989; Christiansen, 2011; Lawson, 1994; Putniņš, 2015).

Organizations engaging in the production, exchange and distribution of goods and services for sale and for purposes that include creating social, environmental, or community value – including but not limited to those labelled social enterprises, purpose-driven businesses, and hybrid organizations – are considered businesses in this report (Bocken et al., 2014; Busch et al., 2018; Feger & Mermut, 2022; Gartenberg et al., 2016; Slawinski et al., 2021; Vlasov, 2021). In this assessment, family-owned organizations and individuals (or other “smallholder” units) producing, exchanging or distributing goods or services for sale are also considered (Dou et al., 2019; Golez, 2015; Kariyapperuma & Collins, 2021). Individuals or entities operating in the informal sector – defined here as encompassing activities outside of formal markets subject to regulatory, legal and tax oversight and not contributing to formal economic accounting metrics like gross domestic product (Gërkhani, 2004; ILO, 1972) – are also defined as businesses as long as they engage in the production, exchange and distribution of goods and services for sale.

Box 1.2. IPLC businesses, traditional economies and livelihoods

IPLCs carry out a diverse range of economic activities as part of their traditional economies and livelihoods, including in the exercise of their collective autonomy and self-governance or as activities for their basic sustenance. Not all of these activities are categorized as businesses. Similarly, IPLCs may sometimes engage in business activities – usually as individuals – that have no relation to their identity as IPLCs, and do not need to be analysed separately from other types of businesses.

In this assessment, IPLC businesses are understood by reference to several key characteristics. They will generally be owned by IPLCs and governed collectively or contribute to collective objectives. IPLCs businesses can be diverse and may vary significantly on their organizational objective, structure, size, business type, degree of formality and recognition. Although many IPLCs businesses seek to generate profit, they will often be guided by other values such as benefit sharing, equity, fairness, a relationship of reciprocity with nature and respect for customary laws, governance and principles (IPBES et al., 2023, 2024).

Some examples include: in Bolivia, Indigenous and local communities selling vicuña fiber sourced sustainably from live-shorn animals (CITES, 2019); in Brazil, the Wai Wai Indigenous People operating a Brazil nut business (Instituto Socioambiental, 2024), Indigenous communities in Bolivia involved in the chocolate industry (FAO, 2019); and in Fiji, the Tifajek Mudpools and Hot Springs, a tourism venue established on customary land by Indigenous business (Scheyvens et al., 2020).

IPLCs businesses may be developed from traditions, customs and Indigenous and local knowledge and may make use of in-depth local ecological information developed and transmitted over generations. IPLCs businesses may be governed by customary law and regularly incorporate principles of sustainability (for example, looking seven generations forward in decision-making) (IPBES, 2023a). The values that inform

IPLCs business will often stem from, and support, close spiritual and cultural connections to ancestral lands and territories. This assessment acknowledges this important history and recognizes that many IPLCs have strong cultural and spiritual relationships with nature.

Governments, public authorities, civil society, policymakers, consumers, and non-governmental organizations are not defined as businesses. Likewise, individuals producing goods and services for the primary purpose of subsistence or barter are also excluded from the definition of business. While these entities all generate value and regularly have important dependencies and impacts on nature—and may occasionally produce, exchange, or distribute goods and services for sale—their primary activities do not align with the commercial focus that defines businesses in this context. However, although some elements of this assessment may still be relevant to them, they are not the primary focus.

This assessment recognizes the considerable diversity of entities that fall within the broad category of “business”. While all businesses have a role to play in addressing their relationship with nature, the extent and nature of that role varies depending on factors such as size, location, sector and geographic location and the scale of their impact and dependencies on nature. This assessment is primarily focused on those businesses with the greatest impacts and dependencies on biodiversity, which include large, small and medium-sized enterprises and transnational businesses.

1.2.4. Financial institutions

This assessment distinguishes between financial institutions and the broader financial system. Financial institutions —such as banks, insurance businesses, asset owners and managers, public development banks, and investment funds (as discussed in **Chapter 5**)—may provide financial goods and services to businesses and individuals in the form of loans, insurance and investments. When financial institutions engage in the production, exchange, or distribution of goods and services for sale, they are considered businesses for the purposes of this assessment. However, we specifically highlight financial institutions when their nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks, or opportunities differ significantly from those of other types of businesses.

In addition, this assessment considers financial institutions in the context of the broader financial system in which they operate. This includes central banks, financial regulators and supervisors, and international financial institutions and standard-setting bodies. Such financial institutions operating in the broader financial system are not considered businesses within this assessment but are recognised for their important role in shaping the financial system. The financial system also encompasses the legal rules, regulatory frameworks, and business practices that govern financial transactions. The financial system influences the conditions within which businesses operate and is explored further in **Chapter 6**.

1.2.5. Typology of business activity

A typology of business activity serves as a foundation for exploring business impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. Although there is no universally accepted typology of business activity, this assessment characterises businesses based on traits frequently emphasized in the related scholarly and grey literatures. The key differentiating properties of business used in this assessment are sector, size and geography (**Table 1.1**).

Table 1.1. Typology of business activity by size, region and sector using the ISIC classification system.

Baseline typology of business				
By size:	Micro < 5 participants	Micro 6 - 50 participants	Medium 51- 500 participants	Big> 500 participants
By region:	Africa	The Americas	Asia and the Pacific	Europe and Central Asia
By sector:	Description			
	Agriculture, forestry, and fishing			
	Mining and quarrying			
	Manufacturing			
	Electricity, gas, steam, and air conditioning supply			
	Water supply; sewage, waste management, and remediation activities			
	Construction			
	Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles			
	Transportation and storage			
	Accommodation and food service activities			
	Information and communication			
	Financial and insurance activities			
	Real estate activities			
	Professional, scientific, and technical activities			
	Administrative and support service activities			
	Public administration & defence; compulsory social security			
	Education			
	Human health and social work activities			
	Arts, entertainment, and recreation			
	Other service activities			
Activities of households as employers				
Activities of extraterritorial organizations and bodies				

The typology of business sectors used in this assessment follows the International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) System (UN, 2008). This system classifies entities on the basis of activities that use inputs (e.g., capital, labour, energy, materials) to produce goods and services (UN, 2008). Alternative typologies that classify business sectors based on revenues, sales and other formal metrics may not fully capture activities in the informal sectors or those conducted by IPLCs actors. Although the ISIC system does not distinguish between formal and informal activities or necessarily between market and non-market activities, its classifications are intended to capture businesses in both the formal and informal economic sectors (UN, 2008) (for further details see Appendix 2).

The ISIC system offers other advantages in the context of this assessment. First, it is global rather than regional. Common alternative classification systems – including but not limited to the Brazilian Classificação Nacional de Atividades Econômicas (CNAE), the Chinese Industrial Classification for National Economic Activities, the European Nomenclature des Activités Économiques dans la Communauté Européenne (NACE), the Indian National Industrial Classification (NIC), or the North American Industry Classification System (NAICS)– may lack global generality. Second, the ISIC system is administered by the United Nations Statistics Division and based on internationally agreed-upon definitions. The system provides classifications generally consistent with the existing grey literature (CBD, 2022; IPBES, 2019a; UNEP, 2022; WBCSD, 2022). It is compatible with the United Nations System of Environmental and Economic Accounting, the system of national accounts, and other common global classifications like the Global Industry Classification Standard (GICS). Third, although the system is based on incumbent sectors in any given time, the system is adaptable, periodically updated and flexible⁸.

This assessment defines a typology of business geography, largely following IPBES regional assessments: the Americas; Africa; Asia and the Pacific; and Europe and Central Asia. Although some businesses may have multiple locations to satisfy legal, tax, organizational, and other objectives, for the purposes of this assessment entities are assigned to a geography on the basis of primary location of the activities that use inputs to produce goods and services. This assessment may also identify broader geographies as transnational, encompassing entities with operations in at least one region outside of the “home” geography.

1.2.6. Value chains

Understanding impacts and dependencies of business on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people requires an understanding of value chains. A value chain is defined as “the full range of activities, interactions, resources and relationships required to bring a product or service from conception through production, delivery, consumption and end-of-life” (Kaplinsky & Morris, 2000). The related concept of supply chain refers to “the linear sequence of processes, actors and locations involved in the production, distribution and sale of a commodity from start to finish” (TNFD, 2023d).

Supply chains often focus on the sequence of suppliers contributing to a final product, while a value chain emphasizes the value created throughout its full process (SustainAbility, UNEP & UNGC, 2008). This assessment's value chain definition is intended to encompass common aspects of supply chain definitions.

⁸ The “Exploring Natural Capital Opportunities, Risks and Exposure- ENCORE” tool, which helps assess sector impacts and dependencies on nature, has shifted from using the GICS classification to the International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) system (ENCORE, 2025). Some related initiatives (e.g., TNFD, 2022, 2025a); UNDP SDG Investor Platform; Business for Nature; the International Sustainability Standards Board) use the Sustainable Industry Classification System (SICS) developed by the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB) now part of the IFRS Foundation and the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB). SICS shares many features with the ISIC system and key differences are organizational rather than substantive.

Value chains include various elements. They involve stakeholders such as suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, retailers and customers. External actors also play a role, including strategic partners, business associations, standard setting organizations, governments, communities, all influencing the financing, geographical, geopolitical and regulatory landscape (TNFD, 2023d). Value chains cover activities such as the physical transformation and transportation of goods and services; knowledge; human resources, marketing and other operational inputs and processes (Kaplinsky & Morris, 2000). They include logistical pathways from material sourcing to consumption, complex interactions in space, time, and feedback processes that reflect both human and natural system dynamics (Moretti et al., 2023). Additionally, they show how control, coordination and power may be exercised among stakeholders (Gereffi, 2019; Gereffi et al., 2005).

Other assessments and much of the scholarly literature use the terms value chain and supply chain interchangeably. Many scholars and organizations use both terms without clear definition. Given no universally accepted usage of value chain and supply chain concepts, this assessment defaults to “value chain” as defined to be maximally inclusive of concepts commonly associated with both value and supply chains in the scholarly and grey literatures. ‘Supply chain’ is used only when a specific narrower concept is intended and articulated. In the context of this assessment, and when considered from the perspective of any business, the concept of value chain should be understood as referring both to upstream and downstream activities.

1.2.7. Business dependencies on nature

All businesses depend on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. The type and magnitude of dependencies vary across sectors, sub-sectors, ecosystems, and geographies as detailed in **Chapter 2**. A dependency arises when businesses rely upon, or are affected or constrained by, nature's contributions to people, including ecosystem services, while financial institutions may depend on nature through the reliance of the businesses they invest in, lend to or insure (reviewed in detail in **Chapter 2**). Businesses depend directly on biodiversity for inputs such as water, fiber, animal-based energy and genetic materials for their operations and value chains (Natural Capital Coalition, 2016; NCFA & WCMC, 2018). Businesses also depend on a range of regulating and non-material nature's contributions to people such wild pollination, pest control, water quality and climate regulation for the agriculture sector while those operating in the real estate sector may depend on nature's scenic beauty (BCG, 2021; TEEB, 2012b).

Business dependencies on biodiversity can result in negative impacts if they exceed sustainable levels, which can ultimately pose risks to the business itself. The extent of these risks depends on factors such as the magnitude of the dependency, the availability of substitutes, competition over natural resources, and the long-term availability, accessibility and reliability of a sustainable supply of the nature's contribution to people, all of which vary by location (A4S, 2024; TNFD, 2023c).

Despite how important nature-related dependencies can be for an organization, few businesses have assessed them (WBA, 2024). Because many dependencies on biodiversity can be intangible and or difficult to measure, they are often underrepresented in decision-making (Mengist et al., 2020; Dasgupta, 2021). Most scientific studies on the dependencies of businesses on biodiversity and ecosystem services have focused on a few sectors including agriculture, forestry and fishing, arts, entertainment and recreation, and water supply and waste management sectors. As reviewed in **Chapters 3 and 4**, methods for assessing dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people are generally less advanced than those for assessing impacts on biodiversity, with most available methods for quantifying business dependencies on nature focus on direct dependencies, with fewer approaches available for assessing dependencies within value chains.

1.2.8. Business impacts on nature

Business activities also impact biodiversity (reviewed in detail in **Chapter 3**). In this assessment, business impacts on biodiversity are defined as positive or negative changes in the quality or quantity of biodiversity resulting from land and sea use, direct exploitation of organisms, climate change, pollution, or the introduction of invasive alien species (IPBES, 2019a). Such impacts may result in changes to the capacity of biodiversity to support social, economic and cultural functions. Businesses' impacts on biodiversity include direct, value chain, indirect and cumulative impacts and can be negative or positive (TNFD, 2023d), although the evidence shows most impacts have been negative (see **Chapter 3**).

1.2.8.1. Types of business impacts on nature: Direct, value chain, indirect and cumulative

Businesses have direct, value chain and indirect impacts on biodiversity and its contributions to people. A business's direct impacts refer to those within its direct control and may arise from activities such as resource extraction (e.g., mining and drilling), deforestation or other vegetation clearing for agriculture, manufacturing, transportation and the sale of goods. A business's value chain impacts result from the impacts incurred through its upstream or downstream value chain. Indirect impacts result from activities that were catalyzed by a business's actions but extend beyond its direct operations or value chain. For example, mining operations are expanding in biodiversity-rich biomes (Maus et al., 2022) resulting in direct damage to biodiversity from ecosystems alteration, such as clearing old-growth forests, to access and extract mineral deposits (Sonter et al., 2018). Indirect impacts include population growth in surrounding areas driven by jobs, improved transportation and energy infrastructure, which in turn increase pressure on biodiversity and its contributions to people beyond sites directly controlled by mining businesses (Sonter et al., 2017). Mining operations can also foster migration with long-lasting impacts and transformation of economic, political, and physical landscapes (Botchwey et al., 2019; Crawford et al., 2015).

Indirect impacts can also stem from businesses' financing and investing activities. It can be more difficult to measure and attribute indirect impacts to a single business, although these impacts can have significant implications for nature and its contributions to people (Kramer et al., 2023). A recent study found that ten European banks with the highest financing shares were responsible for about 40 per cent of the global biodiversity impacts linked to European area businesses (ECB, 2023).

When assessing businesses' impacts on biodiversity, it is also important to consider cumulative changes in the state of biodiversity over time (Houdet & Teren, 2022). Cumulative impacts occur when the impacts from multiple businesses combined with impacts from other actors in an area have additive or interactive effects that are greater than would be expected from their individual activities occurring in isolation. Considering cumulative impacts is essential for a comprehensive assessment of businesses' impacts on biodiversity and its contributions to people (more details in **Chapter 3**). For example, marine and coastal ecosystems are threatened by the cumulative impacts from overfishing, land- and sea-based pollution, rising sea temperatures and ocean acidification (IPBES, 2019a; Simeoni et al., 2023). These combined pressures can interact, potentially pushing ecosystems past critical tipping points, leading to irreversible losses (Armstrong et al., 2022; Bai et al., 2022; Flores et al., 2024; Heinze et al., 2021; Simeoni et al., 2023). Similarly, intensive land management practices combined with the impacts of climate change lead to stronger decline in ecosystem multifunctionality – the ability of ecosystems to provide ecosystem services – in both grasslands and croplands, posing significant risks to the agriculture sector (Scherzinger et al., 2024). When multiple factors contribute to environmental challenges, determining attribution can be challenging but remains essential for effective risk management and informed decision-making.

1.2.8.2. Positive and negative impacts of business on nature

Businesses, including financial institutions, are pivotal in driving economic activity in sectors that contribute to jobs, health, food production, economic development, and many other factors associated with quality of life. For example, sectors such as agriculture and livestock, fisheries, forestry, infrastructure, and mining deliver many benefits to society but activities in these sectors also heavily contribute to biodiversity loss (IPBES, 2024c). Businesses may have both positive and negative impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, which will vary based on factors such as sector, size, and geography.

Businesses negatively impact nature and its contributions to people by influencing the major drivers of biodiversity loss (IPBES, 2019a). Examples of negative impacts from businesses include the conversion and degradation of ecosystems, the overharvesting of wild species for trade, food or medicine (e.g., fisheries, timber), pollution from chemicals, plastic and other forms of packaging (Cowger et al., 2024), the spread of invasive species through global trade, and greenhouse gas emissions from business activities (Hulme, 2009; IPBES, 2019; Thomson & Fairbairn, 2023).

Businesses can also have positive impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, however, as noted in **Chapter 3**, these are not often tracked in a standardized way, and are smaller than the negative impacts that businesses have on biodiversity. For example, businesses have had positive impacts on biodiversity by restoring forests, pollinator habitat important for food production, and watersheds or wetlands that support habitats for birds and mitigate flooding (Ingram et al., 2022; WBCSD, 2017). While positive impacts on biodiversity combined with a reduction in negative impacts are both important actions for businesses to take, all impacts on biodiversity need to be compared to a baseline. Furthermore, it is critical that business contributions to biodiversity outcomes incorporate alignment with the mitigation hierarchy to ensure that activities are indeed positive for biodiversity (Maron et al., 2023). In addition, for businesses to align with global goals for nature such as those set out within the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, they will need to do more than merely compensate for negative impacts, they will need to deliver biodiversity improvements relative to a static baseline line.

Within this context, the concept of businesses, financial institutions and others being “nature positive” or contributing to “nature positive” outcomes has emerged since 2021 across multiple fora and initiatives, particularly in Europe and North America. The central principle of the concept is that business-as-usual is “nature negative” and this needs to become “nature positive” (Locke et al., 2021; Milner-Gulland, 2022). However, definitions and interpretations vary and the concept is used in different ways in different contexts (Pollination, 2024; zu Ermgassen et al., 2022). As increasing numbers of businesses and initiatives adopt the language of nature positive, including in their names, it is unlikely that a single, universally accepted definition is needed or could cover all uses of the term, or apply across all regions (SBTN, 2024b). Prior to the adoption of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, there were efforts promoted by a group of NGOs to make the concept a central tenet of the framework (Locke et al., 2021). The mission agreed at COP15 is to “take urgent action” by 2030, where actions are the focus of effort. The outcome of those actions is expected to “halt and reverse biodiversity loss and put nature on the path to recovery”, recognising these outcomes will only be achieved over a longer timeframe in the period beyond 2030. However, the concept of nature positive – as variously defined – typically claims outcomes over a much shorter period and cannot therefore be said to align with or represent the Goals and Targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), 2022).

Business impacts on nature – both negative and positive – create costs, benefits, risks and opportunities for the business and affected stakeholders (TNFD, 2023c). The distribution of the benefits and costs of the impacts from business activities is unequal over time and space, and

perceptions of what constitutes a good quality of life, as well as the value of nature, vary among different groups (IPBES, 2022b). Business activities may bring benefits to some groups while negatively affecting the quality of life of others. For example, IPLCs have been impacted by industrial activities (Scheidel et al., 2023a) and the urban poor (often ethnic minorities) have been affected by air pollution caused by industrial activity (Leonova & Rentschler, 2022). Unsustainable business practices can also compromise the quality of life of future generations. These impacts can lead different groups to change their behaviour in ways that either amplify or counteract the initial impact on nature (**Box 1.3** illustrates examples of impacts on IPLCs). To navigate these interactions, businesses need to consider the interconnected relationships between social and environmental impacts.

Box 1.3. Business impacts on Indigenous Peoples and local communities

IPLCs' interaction with business is complex. On the one hand, many IPLCs are business actors, often operating in more sustainable ways than other businesses and guided by diverse values. Sometimes, IPLCs have been chosen to engage in business; sometimes they have been pushed into it as a result of displacement, loss of access to traditional livelihoods and/or forced urbanisation. In other cases, IPLCs would like to operate businesses but are faced with barriers to doing so (IPBES et al., 2024).

On the other hand, IPLCs are also very often affected by the operations of other businesses. Some business interactions with IPLCs can be positive, for example the rooibos benefit sharing agreement in South Africa (Rooibos Council, 2022). However, IPLCs overwhelmingly report negative interactions with business, for example experiences of dispossession of their lands and resources for mining or agribusiness, extractives, oil and gas, infrastructure development, commercial logging and timber concessions (Scheidel et al., 2023; Dobinson et al., 2023; Pictou et al., 2021;), toxic pollution of their environment (Fernández-Llamazares et al., 2020), loss of access to or desecration of sacred sites (Barclay & Steele, 2021), unacknowledged and unauthorised use of Indigenous and local knowledge (Shiva, 2016; Wynberg, 2023), violations of their biocultural rights (Girard et al., 2022) or threats or killings of human rights defenders (Butt et al., 2019).

Often these negative business impacts have had deleterious impacts on IPLCs because of their strong cultural and spiritual relationships with, and dependencies on nature. For many IPLCs, impacts on nature and people are deeply intertwined and the separation between these impacts is artificial (IPBES, 2024a).

Because of IPLCs' high dependence on nature, negative impacts on biodiversity experienced by IPLCs will usually also have significant social and human rights impacts (Scheidel et al., 2023b). In some cases, such impacts can lead to these groups adopting more unsustainable behaviour as a coping mechanism, amplifying environmental harm. In addition, efforts by businesses to manage environmental impacts, for example by using conservation or biodiversity offset areas, may also have negative impacts on IPLCs by dispossessing or limiting their access and use (Bidaud et al., 2017, 2018; Jones et al., 2019). IPLCs also often struggle to receive equitable benefits when businesses exploit their resources. Even when projects they participate in achieve targets like reducing deforestation or lowering carbon emissions, they may still be excluded from equitable gains.

At the same time, IPLCs often hold deep local ecological knowledge that can be critical to understanding and monitoring impacts on biodiversity (Hill et al., 2020; Lyver et al., 2018; Balehegn, 2016). In their own interaction with nature, IPLCs often have either low impacts or positive impacts on biodiversity (Chettri & Sharma, 2022; Sangha et al., 2021). Guidance tailored to the private sector exists to support businesses in their engagement with IPLCs and affected stakeholders when identifying, assessing and disclosing impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people (SBTN, 2024a; TNFD, 2023b).

1.2.9. Nature-related risks: physical, transition and systemic

Risks are defined as the potential for negative or adverse consequences for societies and ecosystems (IPCC, 2023; UNDRR, 2019). In the context of businesses, nature-related risks refer to the “potential threats posed to an organization that arise from its and wider society's dependencies and impacts on nature” (TNFD, 2023c). From an economic perspective, biodiversity loss present significant risks to the global economy (UNEP, 2021) and have been identified as the highest-ranked global risks that

could negatively impact a significant proportion of global gross domestic product, business and populations or natural resources over the next 10 years, according to the World Economic Forum (WEF, 2025b).

In the business and finance context, climate and nature-related risks are categorised as physical, transition (TCFD, 2017) and systemic risks (TNFD, 2023c). Nature-related physical risks to an organization result from the degradation or loss of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people that businesses depend upon and/or impact (NGFS, 2023a; TNFD, 2023d). These can be acute in the case of a short-term event. For example, deforestation combined with heavy rainfall events in Rwanda has resulted in severe flooding and sedimentation of water resources that decreased production of hydroelectricity plants in the country, resulting in significant costs (IUCN, 2015). Physical risks can also result from chronic stressors if they involve longer-term shifts in the state of biodiversity (TNFD, 2023d). For example, declining water quality has been correlated with declining real estate values (Nicholls & Crompton, 2018). Nature-related transition risks to an organization may result from a misalignment of economic actors with actions to protect, restore and/or reduce negative impacts on biodiversity (TNFD, 2023d). These types of risks can be prompted by changes in regulation and policy, legal precedent, technology, and/or investor sentiment and consumer choices that may cause adverse business consequences (NGFS, 2023a). For example, consumer preferences and media scrutiny of businesses linked to deforestation in their supply chains have created significant reputational and market risks for some food and agriculture businesses (Bromley, 2023).

Systemic risks emerge from disruptions that collectively lead to the collapse of the whole system. These risks often start at seemingly minor thresholds that escalate into widespread breakdowns through a chain of interactions and contagions, where one incident sets off a sequence of others, leaving the system unable to stabilize after a shock (TNFD, 2023d). Systemic risks can result from ecosystems crossing tipping points – such as the irreversible melting of ice sheets in Greenland and Antarctica, the collapse of the Atlantic Ocean circulation system, and the transformation of the Amazon rainforest into a dry savanna (Möller et al., 2024), which could have far-reaching economic, social, and ecological consequences. According to recent projections, there is a roughly 45 per cent probability that these tipping points could be reached within the next 300 years (Möller et al., 2024; Willcock et al., 2023).

Despite growing awareness of the systemic risks that nature degradation and loss pose to the global economic and financial system, there is still limited clarity on how these risks translate into corporate/financial balance sheets (Carvalho et al., 2023). However, a growing body of literature is starting to shed light on how these risks can be assessed and translated for businesses and financial institutions (Alvarez et al., 2025; BloombergNEF, 2023; Green Finance Institute, 2024; Marsden et al., 2024; Ranger et al., 2023; TNFD, 2025d). While some sectors and regions recognise that their impacts and/or dependencies on biodiversity create risks for business (CERES, 2024; Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024; Ranger et al., 2023), many businesses remain unaware (WBA, 2024). A growing range of tools and datasets is becoming available to help businesses, investors, and other stakeholders better understand and manage their exposure to nature-related risks and impacts (TNFD, 2025c). For example, scenario analysis is a useful tool for supporting organizations in better understanding the risks they face and has been used for assessing climate-related risks on businesses (TCFD, 2020). Recent guidance has been developed to support central banks and supervisors (NGFS, 2023b) and financial institutions and large multinational businesses (TNFD, 2023a) with using scenario analyses to assess nature-related financial risks.

1.2.9.1. Financial effects from nature-related risks

Evidence of the financial effects of nature-related risks is extensive across sectors and scales, but company-specific data is limited due to reliance on publicly available sources. The strongest evidence

exists for financial effects linked to water scarcity, liability and policy and reputational risks, while full causal chains from nature loss to financial outcomes remain underexplored (Alvarez et al., 2025; TNFD, 2025d). Nature loss can have significant macroeconomic, macroprudential, and microprudential consequences, posing systemic risks to financial system stability (NGFS, 2023a).

Financial institutions within the broader financial system – including central banks and supervisors – are increasingly working to understand how nature-related risks affect both the broader economy and financial stability (Banque de France, 2021; DNB & PBL, 2020; Hadji-Lazaro et al., 2024; NGFS & INSPIRE, 2021; NGFS, 2023b, 2023a). These risks become material when biodiversity loss inhibits business operations or impacts supply chains. For example, ecosystem conditions such as reduced water availability can have a critical impact on business operations for beverage businesses (Weber & Saunders-Hogberg, 2018). Furthermore, environmental degradation can result in risks such as reduced creditworthiness of affected businesses, higher capital investment needs and costs, and/or lower productivity (NGFS, 2023a). A decline in creditworthiness can, in turn, create risks for banks, lenders and insurers.

To address these challenges, central banks and supervisors are advancing efforts to assess corporate dependencies on biodiversity as part of their credit and lending evaluations (ACPR, 2024; ECB, 2023; NGFS, 2023a, 2024a), recognising that poorly managed dependencies can translate into nature-related risks. For example, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), in collaboration with the Hungarian Central Bank, developed a supervisory framework that translates biodiversity risks into financial risks and conducted a technical assessment of these risks within Hungary's economy and financial system, (OECD, 2023). Similarly, the Financial Stability Board has also reviewed how financial authorities are addressing the implications of nature-related risks (FSB, 2024). **Table 1.2** presents a few examples of central banks and supervisors evaluating portfolio exposures to nature-related risks, especially focusing on sectors that are highly dependent on biodiversity. These efforts aim to identify and measure the nature-related risks facing financial institutions and their potential impacts on overall financial stability.

Table 1.2. Examples of central banks and supervisors assessing nature-related portfolio exposures in high-dependency sectors

Region/Entity	Key nature-related exposure	Source
Brazilian Banks	46 per cent of corporate loan portfolios are exposed to biodiversity loss, with significant lending to sectors highly dependent on ecosystem services.	Calice et al. (2021)
Dutch Financial Institutions	Dutch financial institutions alone have €510 billion in exposure to biodiversity-related risks.	DNB & PBL (2020)
French Financial Institutions	42 per cent of securities market value linked to businesses that are highly or very highly depending on at least one ecosystem service.	Banque de France (2021)
Euro Area Corporate Loans	Within Europe 72 per cent of businesses and 75 per cent of corporate loans highly depend on at least one ecosystem service.	Boldrini et al. (2023)
Georgian Commercial Banks	46 per cent of Georgian commercial banks' lending potentially exposed to biodiversity-related physical risks due to moderate to high or very high dependence on one or more ecosystem services. 54 per cent of these banks’ business lending portfolios may face high	Nikuradze & Tvalodze (2023)

	transition risk from lending to sectors with strong impacts on those ecosystem services.	
Malaysian Commercial Banks	54 per cent of commercial loan portfolio is exposed to sectors highly dependent on ecosystem services, with key vulnerabilities in surface water (29 per cent), carbon storage (26 per cent), and flood/storm protection (16 per cent). Additionally, 87 per cent of loans are to sectors that strongly impact ecosystem services, particularly through greenhouse gas emissions (61 per cent), water use (55 per cent), and terrestrial ecosystem disruption (43 per cent), indicating significant transition risk exposure.	World Bank & Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM) (2022)

Nature-related risks can also lead to legal liabilities, illustrated by litigation against businesses and financial institutions linked to ecosystem damage, especially through global supply chains (NGFS, 2024b).

Banks, insurers, and investors are exposed to nature-related risks through their lending, underwriting, and investment activities – particularly when financing sectors with significant dependencies or impacts on biodiversity, or businesses operating in sensitive locations such as key biodiversity areas (Calice et al., 2021; DNB & PBL, 2020; van Toor et al., 2020). For example, when banks and investors finance certain practices in high-risk sectors – such as seafood (wild-caught fisheries and aquaculture), ports, maritime transportation, marine renewable energy, and coastal or marine tourism – these activities may require thorough risk assessment and, in some cases, exclusion from financing (UNEP FI, 2021). Similarly, investors may be exposed to risks from portfolio holdings linked to deforestation and associated human rights abuses, particularly when financing certain commodities in high-risk regions (UNEP FI & PRI, 2025).

Nature-related risks are also important for insurers as degradation and biodiversity loss can affect their underwriting activities across their insurance value chain and through the activities of associated actors (ACPR, 2024; EIOPA, 2023; NGFS, 2023a; UNEP FI, 2023a, 2025b). This includes exposure via goods and services from upstream claims, as well as through insured assets, processes, liabilities, and human health and life covered in downstream underwriting portfolios (UNEP FI, 2025b). Efforts have focused on identifying pathways to capture the risk reduction benefits provided by reef habitats into insurance premiums (Reguero et al., 2020). However, existing examples of insurance products that integrate the risk reduction benefits of biodiversity are few (Asian Development Bank (ADB), 2022; Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), 2023; Schelske et al., 2021; Swiss Re Institute, 2020).

1.2.10. Nature-related opportunities

Nature-related opportunities for businesses and financial institutions can arise from both their dependencies and impacts on biodiversity and refer to activities that create positive outcomes for organisations and biodiversity through positive impacts or mitigation of negative impacts on biodiversity (TNFD, 2023d). These include the strategic transformation of business models, products, services, markets, and financing mechanisms that deliver biodiversity benefits and/or activities that avoid, reduce, mitigate or manage nature-related risks. Opportunities for businesses stemming from their impacts and dependencies will vary across sector, geography, local social and cultural contexts, and market and economic factors.

A growing number of examples demonstrate opportunities that can deliver positive outcomes for businesses, biodiversity, and other stakeholders. For example, recent studies show that sustainable land management, agroforestry, cover crops and improving grazing intensity may grow from the current \$ 200 billion to \$ 542 billion annually by 2030 and quadruple to \$ 737 billion by 2050 (UNEP, 2023b). Meta- analyses across multiple continents have shown that diversified farming systems are at least as profitable as simplified ones, and in some cases more profitable, while delivering positive outcomes for biodiversity and climate (Sánchez et al., 2022). Multiple examples show that projects and investments that are focused on delivering positive outcomes for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people – especially in agriculture – can be profitable, commercially viable, and scalable (The Climate Champions Team et al., 2024).

The business case for investing in nature-based solutions that deliver key benefits for business – such as regulation of water quality or water quantity – has been demonstrated globally (CPI, 2024; Green Finance Institute Hive et al., 2025; Green et al., 2024; UNEP Copenhagen Climate Centre (UNEP-CCC), 2025; WBCSD, 2017, 2024). Businesses have found such investments can be more cost-effective than built alternatives, require less capital investment, have lower long-term operational and maintenance costs, and/or can reduce labour requirements (WBCSD, 2017). Such solutions, ranging from conservation or restoration of tropical forests, mangroves, and/or seagrass meadows, can also offer significant co-benefits such as carbon storage or sequestration (Anderson et al., 2019; Buma et al., 2024; Griscom et al., 2017; Seddon, 2022; UNEP Copenhagen Climate Centre (UNEP-CCC), 2025; Weiskopf et al., 2024b). In some cases, carbon revenues from nature-based solutions have helped make investments in nature restoration and sustainable land management financially viable (UNEP, 2023b). However, although natural climate solutions are important for mitigating climate change, they do not lessen the urgent need for direct emission reductions in high greenhouse gas-emitting sectors (Anderson et al., 2019; Buma et al., 2024).

Efforts to halt and reverse biodiversity loss are also spurring new business products, services and models in sectors such as the chemicals, fashion, mining, forestry and agri-food (BloombergNEF, 2024; Business for Nature, n.d.-c; TNFD, 2025f; UNEP, 2023a; UNEP FI, 2024; WBCSD, 2023; WEF, n.d.). Specific examples include commercial opportunities such as advanced agricultural machinery manufacturers, startups focused on environmental DNA, businesses optimizing water use and wastewater treatment to improve resource efficiency, and businesses operating in the circular economy space (BloombergNEF, 2024). In addition, sectoral transitions can also create substantial lending, investment and underwriting opportunities for financial institutions (WEF, 2020; WEF & Oliver Wyman, 2024). For example, WEF (2020) identified fifteen systemic transitions with annual business opportunities valued at \$10 trillion and the potential to create 395 million jobs by 2030 – pathways that can support both people and nature while strengthening resilience to future shocks (WEF, 2020; WEF & Oliver Wyman, 2024).

1.3. Evolving business engagement with biodiversity and nature's contribution to people

In the absence of external pressures, regulatory incentives or clear business reasons, businesses and private markets often fail to integrate the values of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people into their investments, sourcing decisions and/or operations, reflecting classic market failures. Biodiversity loss represents a 'negative externality', where the costs of environmental damage are imposed on others without compensation. Biodiversity and ecosystem services can be viewed as 'public goods' (Costanza, 2008) that are underprovided by private markets due to "free riding", where individuals benefit from public goods without paying fully for them (Stiglitz, 1977). Additional barriers such as 'technology lock-in' and 'stranded asset' considerations further hinder integration of nature's values into business decision-making" (Caldecott, 2017; Unruh, 2000). As biodiversity is lost and degraded globally, the supply of these public goods declines and, consequently, the costs of delivering these benefits rises. Although many aspects of biodiversity and its contributions to people have historically been considered public goods, they can be managed as private goods when property rights or resource tenure are secure and clearly defined, as in cases of IPLCs management (Ostrom, 2010, 2015).

Because of these dynamics, throughout much of recent history, policy and regulations have mostly focused on addressing the negative impacts that businesses may have on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. For example, in the late 20th century, the public became more aware of environmental concerns from human activities, including those linked to businesses and their activities. International agreements such as the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES), signed by over 180 parties, were established to protect species from extinction attributable to trade, development and growth (CITES, 1973).

Environmental impact assessments, introduced in the 1970s and now embedded in national laws and multilateral agreements, are used mainly at project level as a tool to identify, predict, evaluate and mitigate the biophysical, social and other relevant effects of development proposals prior to major decisions and commitments (Arabadjieva, 2016; El-Fadl & El-Fadel, 2004; Morgan, 2012; UN, 1992). The mitigation hierarchy is a common approach in environmental impact assessments across sectors to prioritise avoiding negative impacts on biodiversity, minimising, restoring, and as a last resort, offsetting any residual impacts (Phalan et al., 2018). Environmental impact assessment processes face limitations, especially when economic priorities prevent businesses from applying the mitigation hierarchy (Bond et al., 2020). Nonetheless, they can help predict operations-specific impacts and support biodiversity measures (Hugé et al., 2020; Mandai & Souza, 2021), and have informed international standards, safeguards and guidelines for assessing project impacts (ADB, 2023; GEF, 2019; World Bank, 2017).

By the late 1980s and 1990s, growing recognition of biodiversity's economic value and the benefits of its conservation (Daily, 1997; Stiglitz, 1977, 1998; Wilson, 1999) and the rise of the concept of sustainable development – popularized by the Brundtland Report in 1987 and the Rio Earth Summit in 1992 – encouraged businesses to integrate environmental and social considerations (UN, 1992). The United Nations Global Compact in 2000 (UNGC, 2000) and the Johannesburg Summit in 2002 set guidelines on corporate responsibilities and multi-stakeholder collaboration (Latapí et al., 2019; Dasgupta 2021).

Most recently, attention has focused on the financial impacts and risks that businesses and financial institutions will face as a result of biodiversity loss (TNFD, 2023d). In addition, an emphasis has shifted to focus on businesses' dependencies on biodiversity, alongside their impacts on biodiversity

(Natural Capital Coalition, 2016). This represents a shift from a historical focus on the negative impacts that businesses have on biodiversity. As businesses increasingly address both their impacts and dependencies on biodiversity, and how these can create risks or opportunities for their organization, organizations are realizing that in many contexts there is a business case for reducing negative impacts and advancing opportunities that restore, protect or sustainably manage biodiversity (Alvarez et al., 2025).

1.3.1. Integration of climate and nature actions, including human rights interlinkages

Adopted by 195 parties in 2015, the Paris Agreement became a turning point for businesses and financial institutions on climate change. Building on experience gained under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, the business community began applying approaches for reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Pörtner et al., 2021). Links between climate and biodiversity are now increasingly understood and recognized (Pörtner et al., 2021). For example, at the United Nations climate change conference in 2021, the Glasgow Leaders' Declaration on Forests and Land Use – endorsed by 145 countries – pledged to mobilise public and private climate finance. This declaration highlights the crucial and interconnected roles of all types of forests, biodiversity and sustainable land use in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals, including balancing human-caused greenhouse gas emissions and removals by natural processes (carbon sinks), adapting to climate change and maintaining other benefits to people (UN, 2021). Because biodiversity loss and climate change are interdependent and produce compounding impacts on people and nature, addressing these issues in isolation of one another can lead to trade-offs and undermine opportunities of positive outcomes for people, nature and the climate (IPBES, 2024d).

1.4. Recent framings of the interactions between business, financial institutions and nature

1.4.1. Initiatives and frameworks guiding business and financial institutions actions on nature

As businesses and financial institutions increasingly recognise their impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and the business value, opportunities and risks, some are taking voluntary actions beyond regulatory requirements. For example, voluntary market-led initiatives for measuring and reporting on biodiversity are catalysing business and financial institutions' efforts to understand, identify, assess, disclose, and manage nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks and opportunities. **Table 1.3** provides an overview of several, current (as of 2025) voluntary initiatives and coalitions that are playing roles in supporting these efforts. These initiatives reflect a growing recognition of the financial risks posed by biodiversity loss and the opportunities for improving biodiversity outcomes and business performance (CISL, 2020b; Lammerant, 2021; PRI, 2024a; TNFD, 2025d; WEF, 2025a; WEF & PWC, 2020).

An initiative that has catalysed voluntary nature-related disclosures and related efforts by businesses and financial institutions is the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD). The TNFD followed a similar structure to the Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD). The TCFD was a market-led initiative created by the Financial Stability Board that released its climate-related financial disclosure recommendations in 2017 on the information that businesses should disclose to support investors, lenders and insurance underwriters in appropriately assessing and pricing risks related to climate change (TCFD, 2017). Both the TNFD and TCFD recommendations share four core pillars – governance, strategy, risk management, and metrics and targets.

A key development in the way businesses assess nature-related issues involves the concept of materiality. Various frameworks and guidance documents increasingly encourage businesses and financial institutions to evaluate the materiality of nature-related issues in their decision-making processes (CISL, 2020b; EFRAG, 2024a; IFRS, 2023; TNFD, 2023d). However, the concept is interpreted differently across sustainability reporting standards and initiatives (UNEP–WCMC & UNEP FI, 2025). Under the *single materiality* – or *financial materiality* – approach, materiality is defined solely in terms of how information may affect a company's financial performance. It focuses on identifying information that could influence the decisions of investors and other primary users of financial reports. Information is considered material if its omission, misstatement, or obscuring could reasonably be expected to affect these users' decisions based on the company's sustainability disclosures (EFRAG, 2024a). This is the approach adopted by the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB), which aims to meet the information needs of capital markets and focuses on the financial impacts of sustainability issues on enterprise value (IFRS, 2023).

There is growing evidence that nature-related risks can have material financial effects on businesses and financial institutions – by influencing cash flows, cost of capital, and access to finance over various time horizons (CISL, 2020a; TNFD, 2025d). These risks can, in turn, shape investor decisions and capital allocation. Yet, despite these clear linkages, nature-related issues are often not recognised as financially material in corporate reporting under the single materiality perspective (TNFD, 2025d). In contrast, the *double materiality* approach expands the scope of assessment to include not only how nature-related issues affect the company, but also how the company's activities impact biodiversity and people. This approach is supported by the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) standards, Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) questionnaires and embedded in the European Sustainability Reporting

Standards (ESRS), which require organisations to report both on the impacts of their activities on the environment and society, and on how sustainability matters affect the organisation (CDP, 2023a; EFRAG, 2024a; GRI, 2022). Double materiality enables a more holistic understanding of a company's dependencies and impacts on biodiversity, which can generate both risks and opportunities (EFRAG, 2024a).

While the TCFD applied a financial materiality lens to meet the needs of investors, lenders, and insurers on climate, the TNFD adopts a more flexible approach – allowing for financial, impact or double materiality, depending on the user's reporting objectives and context.

Table 1.3. Selected voluntary market-led measurement and reporting initiatives

Name	Actors	Description	Current Status of Users/ Outreach ⁹	Sources
Real economy actors (non-sector specific)				
The Science-based targets network (SBTN) for nature	Corporates and cities	Provides guidance for businesses and cities to set climate and nature targets that respect sustainability and social equity principles. The approach offers a method for setting targets using scientific principles, but it does not yet support businesses to set truly science-based targets for biodiversity.	Limited: As of October 2024, three businesses have publicly adopted science-based targets for nature, beginning with freshwater and land.	Science Based Targets Network (SBTN) (n.d.)
Business for Nature	Global, national and sector business associations, alongside leading conservation organizations	Global coalition of over 100 partner organizations aiming to accelerate the transition to a nature-positive economy by mobilising business leadership. Their 2030 strategy focuses on shaping global and regional policy direction and enabling national-level implementation.	High: Over 100 partner organisations and a network of 1500+ businesses through the Nature is Everyone’s Business Call to Action for governments to adopt policies now to reverse nature loss in this decade.	Business for Nature (n.d.-a)
The Nature Positive Initiative	Conservation organizations, business and finance coalitions	Since 2019, institutions coming together to support broader, longer-term efforts to deliver outcomes for biodiversity	Limited: 28 alliances and institutions comprise their core stewardship group	Nature Positive Initiative (n.d.)
CDP Biodiversity	Businesses, cities, states and regions	A global non-profit operating an independent environmental disclosure system for businesses, capital markets, cities, states, and regions to manage their environmental impacts. The platform covers disclosures on climate, water, forests, and biodiversity. As of 2023, 23,293 businesses reported on climate, 4,815 on water, 1,152 on forests, and 11,453 on biodiversity.	High: As of 2023, 11,453 businesses reported biodiversity-related disclosures, up from 7,974 in 2022.	CDP (2025)

⁹ Current user status is considered limited when fewer than 30 institutions are actively participating; medium when participation ranges from 30 to 100 institutions; and high when more than 100 institutions are actively engaged, with a growing membership or user base.

Frameworks and initiatives for corporates and financial institutions				
Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD)	Corporates, financial institutions, market service providers	A market-led initiative launched in 2021 with 40 members. Its mandate is to develop a framework for identifying, assessing, and disclosing impacts and dependencies on nature and associated financial risks and opportunities for organisations. In addition to its disclosure recommendations, the TNFD has developed additional guidance, including an approach called Locate Evaluate Assess Prepare “LEAP” to help businesses and financial institutions to assess nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks and opportunities.	High: In the latest status report in 2025, 620 businesses, including financial institutions, committed to start making nature-related disclosures between fiscal years (2024-2027) on their material nature-related issues following the recommendations of the TNFD.	TNFD (2023c, 2024c, 2025e)
The Partnership for Biodiversity Accounting Financials (PBAF)	Financial institutions	Framework for financial institutions to assess and disclose the impact and dependencies of their loans and investments on biodiversity.	Medium: As in July 2025, 71 financial institutions joined	PBAF Global (n.d.)
Finance for Biodiversity Pledge	Financial institutions	Launched by a group of 26 financial institutions in 2020. These institutions have committed to collaborate, engage, assess their own biodiversity impact, set targets, and report on biodiversity matters through their finance activities and investments	High: 200 signatories	Finance for Biodiversity Foundation (n.d.)

Methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people

Chapter 1. Setting the scene

Nature Action 100	Investor engagement	Global investor engagement initiative aiming to drive corporate ambition and action to reduce nature loss on key sectors including biotechnology and pharmaceuticals, chemicals, consumer goods retail, food, food and beverage retail, forestry and packaging, household and personal products, and metals and mining.	High: As of July 2025, more than 230 institutional investors – representing over \$30 trillion in assets under management or advice – from around the world participate in Nature Action 100.	Ceres & Nature Action 100 (2024)
Sector or Topic-Specific				
The Finance Sector Deforestation Action (FSDA) initiative	Financial institutions	Launched in 2021, involves 34 financial institutions with more than \$8 trillion in assets. The participating investors have committed to use best efforts through 2025 to eliminate deforestation connected to the operations of the businesses in their investment portfolios, by adopting deforestation policies, assessing and disclosing deforestation risk, and mitigating these risks.	Medium: All FSDA members (34 investors) now have a deforestation policy in place. In contrast, only 25 per cent of financial institutions globally with net zero or other climate commitments have any deforestation policy, according to the Deforestation Action Tracker.	FSDA (2024)
UN-Convened Finance Alliances (Asset Owner and Banking Alliances, Principles for Responsible Banking and Sustainable Insurance)	Mainstream finance: Institutional investors, commercial banks and insurers	In 2024, 553 financial institutions—collectively representing over \$125 trillion in assets—were members of UN-convened alliances or initiatives from institutional investors, banking and insurers. These industry-led alliances have dedicated working groups on nature-related issues, tailored to institutional investors, banks, and insurers. They have developed guidelines, documented emerging practices, launched pilots on assessing, disclosing and managing nature-related considerations into financial portfolios. For example, the Net-Zero Asset Owner Alliance has published expectations on eliminating deforestation from company supply chains, urged policymakers to mandate reporting and end harmful subsidies, and called on data providers to improve transparency and align metrics with reporting frameworks.	High: Tailored guidance and practice documents and commitments for different financial institutions, with high participation of mainstream financial institutions (over 500) and therefore, high usability.	UNEP FI (2023b, 2024, 2025b), UNEP FI & PRI (2025)
Forest 500	Businesses and financial institutions	A public data initiative by Global Canopy to identify high-risk businesses and financial institutions, enable peer comparison, and benchmark progress on deforestation. As of 2025, only 16 businesses (3 per cent) are considered leaders, with strong	High: Over a decade, Forest 500 has tracked the 500 most influential businesses in the global trade of nine key forest-risk commodities—beef, leather,	Thomson, E. (2025)

Methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people

Chapter 1. Setting the scene

		commitments across all forest-risk commodities and clear evidence of implementation. In contrast, 316 businesses (63 per cent) fall into the late majority, showing partial or poorly implemented commitments—often focusing on high-profile commodities like palm oil while neglecting major drivers like beef. Meanwhile, 168 businesses (34 per cent) are classified as laggards, with no public deforestation commitments; 24 of these have shown no progress over a decade.	soy, palm oil, timber, pulp and paper, cocoa, coffee, and rubber—assessing their deforestation commitments and performance.	
--	--	--	---	--

In parallel, businesses are also seeking to understand and manage the value that natural capital provides to businesses and financial institutions. Approaches such as ecosystem services valuation and natural capital accounting can support businesses and financial institutions with understanding and tracking how their impacts and dependencies on biodiversity as identified through a materiality assessment translate into monetary financial values, and business risks, or opportunities for the organization (Buckwell & Morgan, 2022; Mohr & Thissen, 2022). While this is a growing area of interest and practice as demonstrated by several businesses globally, the integration of natural capital values and accounting into business decision making is not widespread currently (J. C. Ingram et al., 2024).

An obstacle to business action on biodiversity is the challenge of applying metrics and setting goals related to biodiversity compared to climate. While there is a quantitative target for the global economy to decarbonize its greenhouse gas emissions by mid-century as per the Paris Agreement, there is no single, quantitative goal to guide actions on biodiversity. A number of initiatives have been established to support businesses and financial institutions in setting and measuring progress towards actions for biodiversity, building from the examples established for climate change (**Table 1.3**). Other initiatives are working at the interface between biodiversity or nature and business to advance sector guidance and roadmaps for business strategies and actions that align with the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and nature transition plans, which may be integrated with climate transition plans for a business (Business for Nature, n.d.-c; TNFD, 2024b; TPT, 2024; WBCSD, 2024; WEF, 2023). It is important that actions described as such improve the state of biodiversity in measurable ways (Maron et al., 2023).

Standards also exist to guide businesses in measuring, managing, and reporting on biodiversity and broader nature-related aspects. These include the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Biodiversity Topic Standard (GRI, 2024a) and the International Sustainability Standards Board's (ISSB) IFRS S1, issued in 2023, which outlines requirements for disclosing sustainability-related risks and opportunities, including those on nature-related aspects under a financial materiality perspective (IFRS, 2023). The International Finance Corporation's Performance Standard 6 on biodiversity conservation and sustainable management of living natural resources outlines the mitigation hierarchy to guide businesses in how to avoid, reduce and manage risks and impacts, and sets requirements for stakeholder engagement and project-level disclosure (IFC, 2012). More recent guidance, such as the biodiversity finance reference guide, provides insights on investment and finance activities that help protect, maintain, or enhance biodiversity and ecosystem services (IFC, 2023). An assessment of seven commonly used standards and frameworks for assessment and disclosure on nature-related issues—including CDP, European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS), Global reporting Initiative (GRI) Standards, ISSB standards, Natural Capital Protocol, Science Based Targets Network target setting guidance and TNFD framework—shows growing alignment in key concepts and methods across these frameworks (UNEP-WCMC & UNEP FI, 2024, 2025).

Many of these frameworks still lack ecosystem-specific guidance and offer limited support for monitoring and managing ecological systemic risks, due to limited research (UNEP-WCMC & UNEP FI, 2024, 2025). In addition, there is a need to ensure these approaches are grounded in science and informed by the best available research (Andersen et al., 2021; Karolyi & Tobin-de la Puente, 2023; UNEP-WCMC & UNEP FI, 2024; Vörösmarty et al., 2018). Greater consistency and interoperability across standards remain an important issue. This is reflected in ongoing alignment efforts, such as GRI–TNFD and EFRAG–TNFD mapping, and upcoming harmonization between ISSB, CDP, TNFD and GRI (EFRAG, 2024a, 2024b; GRI, 2024b; TNFD & EFRAG, 2024).

1.4.2. Implementing businesses and financial institutions action on nature: climate and biodiversity metrics, targets and policies

Although awareness of the need for sustainable business practices is growing, nature-related issues often receive lower priority than climate change (Capgemini Research Institute, 2023; McKinsey & Company, 2023). Biodiversity and climate change are often treated separately, despite being deeply interconnected. There is also growing recognition that businesses need to integrate human rights considerations into their approach to both issues (GBIHR, 2023; ILO and UNEP FI, 2023). Integrated climate and nature policies and actions can help identify and manage potential trade-offs and synergies between climate change and biodiversity interventions (Mariani et al., 2024; Wüstemann et al., 2017).

Businesses and financial institutions can help advance global commitments such as the Paris Agreement, the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development by linking action on climate, biodiversity and people. While some businesses are beginning to adopt this integrated approach, some businesses have called for greater action, especially by governments, to incentivise policy alignment across these agendas (Business for Biodiversity & We Mean Business, 2021).

Despite the growing momentum and important contribution of recent market-led initiatives for increasing transparency and guiding science-based actions, measurement, target setting, reporting and disclosure initiatives will not be sufficient on their own to drive meaningful action on nature loss (Irvine-Broque & Dempsey, 2023). A high-level review of Fortune Global 500 businesses shows that 83 per cent have climate-related targets or at least acknowledge climate change (+ 15 per cent). In contrast, while 51 per cent of businesses acknowledge biodiversity loss, only 5-6 per cent have set targets related to biodiversity and 13 per cent have set targets related to forests (McKinsey & Company, 2022, 2023). An analysis of the integration of biodiversity into corporate disclosures of Fortune 200 businesses for the years 2012, 2014 and 2016 in addition to their websites in the year 2019 showed that most disclosures and reporting on biodiversity were minimal, inconsistent and vague with respect to the information provided (Hassan et al., 2022). Similarly, a 2024 analysis of corporate disclosures produced by 369 businesses in Latin America, Canada and the United States found that 94 per cent of businesses assessed had disclosed against at least one of the TNFD disclosure pillars, but overall alignment with the full set of TNFD recommendations was limited (EY, 2024).

An analysis of 650 sustainability filings for fiscal year 2024 under the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive shows that around 30 per cent of preparers reported biodiversity metrics, with similar disclosure rates across financial and non-financial sectors – including some that did not deem biodiversity financially material but reported on it regardless. Disclosure levels vary widely: sectors with direct land or ecosystem impacts, such as construction (~60 per cent), electricity & gas (62 per cent), and real estate (64 per cent), lead adoption – for example, 100 per cent of Spanish and French construction businesses and 85 per cent of French real estate businesses report biodiversity metrics. Country variation is also significant, with higher disclosure in France (49 per cent), Sweden (44 per cent), Austria (44 per cent), and the Netherlands (39 per cent), and lower uptake in Italy (18 per cent) and Germany (23 per cent) (EFRAG, 2025).

Business actions and policies on biodiversity continue to lag behind reporting trends. There is currently a substantial gap between the proliferation of reporting initiatives and guidance frameworks for businesses and financial institutions to measure, manage, and report on their impacts and dependencies on nature and business actions in adopting and implementing the recommendations. For example, as of 2023, 201 businesses and financial institutions, constituting 40 per cent of those with substantial exposure to tropical deforestation, have not established a single policy to address

deforestation (Thomson & Fairbairn, 2023). Ninety-two financial institutions that are deemed most exposed to deforestation still lack deforestation policies covering their investments and lending to businesses in key forest-risk commodity supply chains. In 2022, these institutions provided \$3.6 trillion in finance to businesses with the highest deforestation risk exposure (Thomson & Fairbairn, 2023). In 2022, an unprecedented 1,043 businesses disclosed their progress in managing deforestation to CDP – an approximately 300 per cent increase compared to 2017. However, despite acknowledging risks, only a limited number of businesses claimed to be on track towards eliminating deforestation from their supply chains (CDP, 2023b).

Voluntary, industry-led initiatives currently far outnumber regulatory efforts, however, meaningful progress cannot rely solely on voluntary, market-led action; public intervention, including regulation and public funding, is essential (Kedward et al., 2023). A 2024 Financial Stability Board study highlights how TCFD and International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) standards played a crucial role in advancing climate risk disclosure, influencing individual jurisdictions to set or propose voluntary or mandatory climate-related disclosure requirements (FSB, 2024). A similar trajectory was emerging for nature-related risks, as seen with the European Sustainability Reporting Standards. However, under the EU's sustainability framework now appears to be weakening (European Commission, 2025b, 2025c). Businesses and investors have warned that maintaining the core elements of the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive is critical to redirecting capital toward future-oriented technologies and sectors. They emphasize that transparency, regulatory certainty and a stable policy environment are essential to achieving growth, supporting decarbonization, and enabling responsible businesses and investors to contribute to the EU's goals for a competitive and sustainable economy (IIGCC et al., 2025). While disclosures can drive business action, they are effective only when supported by a strong enabling environment (see **Section 1.5**).

1.5. Elements of an enabling environment that supports positive outcomes for biodiversity

Governments, the financial system, businesses, financial institutions and other actors (including civil society, IPLCs, individuals acting as consumers and investors) can work together to create an enabling environment where businesses contribute to a just and sustainable future aligned with the goals and targets set out in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. **Chapter 5** reviews key barriers and roles the business community can play in this context while **Chapter 6** summarizes “options for action” for each of the other key actors in detail. Indeed, multi-actor collaboration across all of these groups is needed to advance an enabling environment that supports the transformative changes needed to secure biodiversity and nature's contributions to people for the long-term.

The IPBES Transformative Change Assessment (IPBES, 2024b) notes five key strategies to advance deliberate transformative change (many of which are of relevance in this chapter and considered in **Section 6.1.4**):

1. Conserving and regenerating places of value to nature and people
2. Driving systemic change in sectors most responsible for nature's decline
3. Transforming economic systems for nature and equity
4. Transforming governance systems to be integrated, inclusive, accountable and adaptive
5. Shifting societal views and values to recognise interconnections between humans and nature.

Governments, the financial system, and other actors, (including civil society and IPLCs) have to work together, with businesses and financial institutions to promote and ultimately deliver the global systemic and transformative changes needed to support businesses' efforts to contribute to the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity and the objectives of the Convention on Biological Diversity. To catalyze such changes, all actors in society will need to work together to advance an enabling environment across the following factors:

1. Legal and regulatory: Policies, laws, and regulations that incentivize sustainable business practices, enforce accountability, and integrate biodiversity considerations into decision-making.
2. Economic and financial: Sufficient funding for biodiversity protection/restoration, the integration of nature's value into economic and financial systems, and alignment of financial incentives that promote biodiversity conservation flows with activities that support positive outcomes for biodiversity while eliminating harmful subsidies and activities that degrade biodiversity.
3. Norms and values: Societal awareness, cultural shifts, and collective action that drive demand for responsible business practices and reinforce accountability both from governments as well as from businesses.
4. Technology and data: Credible, accessible and decision-useful measurement tools, data, and technology that are based in the best available science to inform business decisions, improve impact assessments, and enhance transparency and accountability.
5. Capacity and knowledge: Developing skills and understanding of biodiversity related standards and reporting frameworks, as well as partnerships and knowledge-sharing to support sustainable business models and practices.

Such an enabling environment can foster and support business models and actions that meet commercial and/or enterprise objectives while also supporting positive outcomes for biodiversity. For businesses to fully contribute to this future, a combination of barriers will need to be removed and enabling factors advanced that encourage business actions and decisions to align with and/or support positive outcomes for biodiversity (e.g., IPBES, 2024b, 2024e; WBCSD, 2021). These barriers are reviewed in more detail in **Chapters 5 and 6**.

1.5.1. Policy, legislation and regulatory frameworks

Governments and financial systems shape the policy, legal, and regulatory frameworks that influence business operations. They can introduce measures such as policies, laws, and regulations that incentivize or require businesses to address their dependencies and impacts on biodiversity. Enhanced public disclosure of business impacts and dependencies on biodiversity can lead to increased accountability and support enforcement of laws and policies. Civil society and businesses can influence these frameworks through lobbying, advocacy, and participation in electoral processes.

Governments can adopt a range of policies to direct business practices toward beneficial outcomes for nature and people. These policies include incorporating biodiversity considerations into trade policies and requiring strategic environmental and impact assessments for new projects before they begin, alongside effective land use planning and zoning. Moreover, developing and enforcing National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs), and aligning them with National Climate Action Plans (NDCs) and economic development plans through integrated policies (World Bank, 2022), can help regulate and monitor the impact of businesses on nature and climate, contributing to sustainable development and safeguarding human rights (CBD, 2023c). Government and regulatory agencies can encourage or require disclosure on nature-related dependencies, impacts, risks, and opportunities from businesses, investors and other financiers. In addition, government agencies also play a key role in collecting and providing robust, consistent and credible biodiversity data for business decision making and disclosures (Ingram et al., 2024).

At the domestic level, national or regional regulation in some regions have focused on decreasing negative impacts and increasing transparency on business impacts on nature. Examples include biodiversity net gain requirements in the United Kingdom; and the European Union's regulations on deforestation-free products, on nature restoration, and on corporate sustainability due diligence that were put in place to drive business action on some aspects of nature (EC, 2022, 2023; Environment Act 2021, 2021; European Council, 2023).

At the international level, the Convention of Biological Diversity and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework plays a central role related to engaging businesses and the financial sector in efforts to promote conservation of biological diversity, the sustainable use of its components, and the fair and equitable sharing of its benefits (CBD, 2023b). Businesses can contribute to, or impede, achieving these goals and targets (CBD, 2022, 2023b).

The financial system, in collaboration with governments, is crucial in creating a regulatory environment that incentivizes businesses to reduce negative impacts and implement actions and investments that protect, restore, and preserve nature. Central banks, financial supervisors, public development banks, international finance institutions, and financial standard-setting bodies can encourage more effective and coordinated efforts of financial institutions to consider nature-related aspects in their products and services like loans, investments, and insurance policies. For example, the International Finance Corporation Performance Standards provide guidance that private sector clients are to meet throughout all stages of an investment made by the International Finance Corporation (IFC, 2012).

1.5.2. Economic and financial frameworks

The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework recognises the importance of economic and financing systems for achieving the 2030 goals and sustainably managing, conserving and restoring biodiversity globally. The framework calls for eliminating, phasing out or reforming subsidies harmful to biodiversity, scaling up positive incentives that promote the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, and increasing public and private finance for biodiversity. It also encourages innovative schemes and calls on institutions to optimise co-benefits and synergies associated with addressing the climate and biodiversity crises together. Finally, it highlights the role of collective action and improving transparency, effectiveness and efficiency of resources given and used (CBD, 2023a).

1.5.2.1. Integration of nature into financial and economic systems

Efforts to make nature “visible” on balance sheets and internalize the costs of nature loss and degradation are critical for encouraging business and government action on biodiversity (Dasgupta, 2021). One way to do this is through natural capital accounting that provides a structured and consistent systems for tracking physical and economic measurements of stocks and flows of natural capital, including information on the extent and condition of ecosystems. Natural capital accounting – specifically the System of Environmental-Economic Accounting that was adopted by the United Nations Statistical Commission in March 2021 – allows environmental data to consistently link with conventional economic measures in the System of National Accounts (United Nations Statistics Division, 2023). Businesses use the statistics generated from national accounts for a variety of purposes and decisions, however, natural capital has historically received limited attention within the system of national accounts resulting in an underrepresentation of the values that nature provides to society in national economic indicators and statistics (Nordhaus et al., 1999). Currently, approximately 90 countries are addressing this limitation by developing national natural capital accounts aligned with the system of environmental-economic accounting at a country-wide level to more fully integrate the value of nature into decision-making (United Nations Statistics Division, 2023). In addition, approaches such as gross ecosystem product are also developing as a way to capture and integrate the value of nature at economy-wide levels to inform and support policy making (Ouyang et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2023). However, natural capital accounting may not capture all of the important values of biodiversity, particularly those that are non-material or non-monetary. In addition, it is important to track both the biophysical as well as monetary values of nature at national and sub-national levels, noting that in some cases biophysical measurement and tracking may be sufficient for informing decisions and policies (Bagstad et al., 2021).

Although the UN system of environmental-economic accounting is aligned with national level accounts, businesses have begun using approaches that allow them to systematically track the value of nature for their business. Some businesses have begun corporate-level natural accounting (Forico, 2023), which allows them to systematically track the value of nature to their business on an annual basis. Other businesses have adopted approaches such as integrated profit and loss accounting to track the costs of their environmental impacts, including those related to nature (Kering, 2023; Natura & Co, 2023).

Currently, many fiscal policies make destroying nature less expensive than protecting it, with public finance flows via subsidies that contribute to environmentally harmful activities being much higher than the amount of public finance available for activities that support biodiversity (Dasgupta, 2020; UNEP, 2026). To align business returns with positive outcomes for nature and society, fiscal measures and policies can eliminate, phase out, or reform tax incentives and subsidies that promote environmental destruction, and increase incentives that promote conserving and sustainably using biodiversity.

In addition, another major barrier to positive action on nature is the limited public and private financing directed toward activities that deliver positive outcomes for nature. As outlined in **Section 1.1.2**, the biodiversity financing gap is estimated at a range from \$300 billion to 1 trillion per year, while achieving the Sustainable Development Goals related to water, food, health, and climate change will require at least \$4 trillion annually (IPBES, 2024e). Financial institutions can help businesses reduce their impact on nature by financing, lending and insuring activities that support positive outcomes for nature such as regenerative agriculture, sustainable forestry, and low-carbon technologies, and engaging in systemic change through policy, capacity building and collaboration initiatives (PRI, 2024b; UNEP, 2023a; UNEP FI, 2023b, 2025b; WEF & Oliver Wyman, 2024).

A promising example of the use of private financing to support biodiversity is the Cali Fund that was adopted by parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity at 16th Conference of the Parties. The Cali Fund is designed to enable businesses and institutions that commercially benefit from the use of Digital Sequence Information provided by nature to financially contribute to the fund, which will distribute funds to developing countries, countries with economies in transition, and IPLCs to support projects that support biodiversity and progress towards the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (CBD, 2025a).

Both traditional and innovative financial instruments are being implemented to incentivize governments, businesses and financial institutions to unlock more financing for biodiversity (UNDP, 2018; WEF, 2024; Zu Ermgassen et al., 2025). These opportunities can be led by public actors—such as multilateral development banks, central banks, foundations, national and/or subnational governments—and include a range of instruments like grants, subsidies, national payment for ecosystem services schemes, sovereign bonds, procurement and official development aid. Examples include the government-led Payments for Ecosystem Services programmes, implemented since the mid-1990s in Costa Rica and since 2003 in Mexico. These long-standing programmes have conserved millions of hectares of forests and benefited local communities in both countries (Izquierdo-Tort et al., 2025; UNDP, 2018). In addition, private actors, including commercial banks, insurers, investors and corporates, have deployed instruments such as sustainability-linked loans, nature-focused project finance, nature impact funds, insurance products, and venture capital to generate financial returns and support positive outcomes for biodiversity (UNEP, 2023a; WEF & Oliver Wyman, 2024; Zu Ermgassen et al., 2025). However, tracking and monitoring of how financing is used and directed towards influencing biodiversity outcomes will be increasingly important (Kedward, et al., 2023).

Blended finance approaches are critical for unlocking more capital for biodiversity by combining public and private capital (CPI, 2024; WEF & Oliver Wyman, 2024). Blended finance involves the strategic use of concessional, public, or philanthropic capital to mobilize additional private investment for projects that deliver positive social, environmental, or climate outcomes while still offering financial returns. For example, debt-for-nature swaps, such as those implemented in the Seychelles, Belize, Barbados, Gabon, the Bahamas, Ecuador, and the Galapagos Islands, have utilized blended finance approaches to refinance or restructure a country's sovereign debt and unlock funding for conservation and resilience efforts (Escovar-Fadul et al., 2025; The Nature Conservancy, 2024).

1.5.3. Social norms, values and culture

The drivers of biodiversity decline and the opportunities to address them are highly informed by the ways in which nature is valued in political and economic decisions (IPBES, 2022c). Historically, business and government policies have often prioritized a narrow set of values, particularly economic and monetary values, while much less consideration has focused on the values of nature associated with IPLCs' world-views of nature (IPBES, 2022c).

By including Indigenous perspectives, business decisions and strategies can adopt approaches that have greater alignment with local, cultural values (Berkes et al., 2000), which may lead to stronger relationships with local stakeholders where businesses source and operate. There is also growing recognition that businesses should integrate social and human rights considerations, such as impacts on IPLCs, poor and marginalised groups, rural communities, women and other vulnerable groups, when assessing their dependencies and impacts on nature. For example, both TNFD and SBTN guidance recognize this and provide guidance for businesses to engage with stakeholders in the landscape, including IPLCs (IFC, 2007; SBTN, 2024a; TNFD, 2023b). Although this guidance references international frameworks such as the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, industry-led processes may have limitations in areas requiring authoritative Indigenous leadership (UNEP FI, 2025a). These more integrated approaches however are still emerging and need more concerted attention and development (Martin-Ortega et al., 2022; Schilling-Vacaflor, 2021).

Businesses and financial institutions can also influence social norms and values through actions that publicly signal an organization's positions on biodiversity (Booth et al., 2024). Examples may include a business or financial institution publishing a nature strategy and goals, tracking and reporting progress towards goals, and publishing nature-related disclosures, all of which may encourage investment from and cooperation with like-minded businesses (Booth et al., 2024; Goyal, 2006; Zerbini, 2017). Organizations can also support shifts in social norms and values by developing key processes and decisions related to biodiversity that other organizations then adopt and use. For example, the International Finance Corporation established performance standards to provide its clients with guidance on how to identify risks and impacts as part of its efforts to encourage sustainable business practices, which include avoiding, minimizing, restoring, and offsetting biodiversity impacts (IFC, 2012). Other large organizations that influence significant amounts of international financing have also adopted the International Finance Corporation Performance Standards (EDFI, 2022; Norfund, 2021), demonstrating the influence that large financial institutions such as the International Finance Corporation can have on shaping market norms.

Civil society plays a crucial role in advancing social norms, values and culture needed to support transformative changes by educating consumers, advocating for sustainable practices, and enhancing transparency in business operations and, thus, empowering stakeholders to make more informed decisions (G. Ingram, 2020). Additionally, civil society has helped develop biodiversity monitoring strategies and verification systems that include IPLCs participation, knowledge, and perspectives (Danielsen et al., 2022). Many non-governmental organizations also actively shape biodiversity priorities globally by engaging in planning and implementing restoration and conservation initiatives, advocacy campaigns, collaborating with businesses, governments, and IPLCs to restore degraded ecosystems and enhance biodiversity, and defining targets and priorities for conservation and restoration locally, nationally and globally.

Additionally, civil society has an important role to play in holding businesses and governments accountable for their social and environmental impacts (Ingram, 2020). The report from the United Nations High-Level Expert Group on the Net-Zero Emissions Commitments of Non-State Entities provides recommendations to prevent net-zero from being undermined by false claims and greenwashing (United Nations, 2022). Specific recommendations of the role of civil society and non-governmental organizations include the need to increase transparency and accountability and aligning lobbying and advocacy efforts (United Nations, 2022; WBA, 2024). For example, civil society can play a key role in calling out poor progress on nature related initiatives such as failure to halt deforestation (CDP, 2023a, 2023b, 2025; Thomson, 2025; Thomson & Fairbairn, 2023). In addition, civil society in partnership with the business community, as discussed in many examples in **Section 1.4**, can lead initiatives that provide guidance and key insights on biodiversity to investors, and encourage companies and financial institutions to integrate biodiversity into their practices, engagement strategies and financing decisions (BankTrack, 2023; ShareAction, 2023).

1.5.4. Technology and data that enable business decisions

Many businesses lack access to high-quality, credible, comparable and decision relevant biodiversity-related data (Natural Capital Coalition, 2019; TNFD, 2024a) and, as importantly, often lack the internal capacity to process, translate, interpret and apply data for informing business and investor decisions. Efforts to address business needs for high quality biodiversity data and data analytics are growing rapidly and may accelerate improvements in the credibility, collection, consistency and connection of nature-related data sets.

A range of biodiversity-related datasets, tools and technologies are now available and rapidly evolving for different purposes, including assessing, monitoring and tracking changes in the extent or condition of ecological systems (Besson et al., 2022). A publicly accessible and widely used example includes ENCORE, which businesses and financial institutions use as a high-level screening tool to identify biodiversity-related dependencies and impacts at the portfolio, sector, and company levels (ENCORE, 2025). WWF's Risk Filter Suite, including a biodiversity and water risk filter, are also used for risk screening (WWF, n.d.). For commercial users, the Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool (IBAT) supports early-stage impact, risk, and opportunity screening, drawing on databases of protected areas, the IUCN Red List of threatened species, and key biodiversity areas. IBAT was established in 2005, provides high-quality, comparable and decision relevant data that now serves >10,000 users, generating ~10,000 reports annually (IBAT, 2021).

However, there remains a need to continue to increase access to and translation of global, regularly updated, location-specific and consistent biodiversity data relevant for businesses (McKenzie et al., 2025). International guidelines are needed related to biodiversity data but are currently lacking. Efforts to develop principles for producers and managers of scientific data including biodiversity data have addressed key issues such as Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability that may make it easier for businesses and others to access data on biodiversity (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

Accessing biodiversity-related data can be especially challenging for businesses with complex supply chains. Although corporate visibility into Tier 1 or direct suppliers has increased in recent years, fewer businesses have reliable data on Tier 2 supplier (suppliers of suppliers) and even fewer can trace their supply chains back to locations where raw materials are sourced (Alicke & Foster, 2024). Asset location data for nature-related risk analysis are often incomplete, inconsistent, and limited in scope or quality, with company disclosures selective and voluntary, public registers restricted to certain sectors or unreliable, third-party datasets non-standardized, incomplete or outdated, and commercial data costly and license-restricted (Christiaen et al., 2025). This lack of visibility into where businesses interface with biodiversity makes it difficult for large multi-national businesses with complex, geographically dispersed supply chains to understand and manage their impacts and dependencies on biodiversity. Various advances in data and technology can help businesses address these knowledge gaps, which are presented in more detail in **Chapter 4**.

Business engagement with biodiversity and the context in which it occurs is expected to continue to evolve. This evolution is likely to respond to developments related to, for example, nature transition plans and the rapidly increasing influence of artificial intelligence see **Box 1.4**.

Box 1.4. Examples of emerging implications of artificial intelligence and machine learning for businesses' interactions with biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.

Artificial intelligence and machine learning have the potential to influence and transform biodiversity monitoring, species modelling, and conservation management, with implications for businesses. Examples include: (i) automated species identification: convolutional neural networks can classify millions of camera-trap images, dramatically reducing manual analysis time (Norouzzadeh et al., 2018; Tabak et al., 2019), (ii) increased accessibility: open-source workflows are expanding access to artificial intelligence tools for non-

experts (Brook et al., 2025), and (iii) improved model efficiency: new approaches using smaller datasets enable more applied transfer and active learning (Bothmann et al., 2023; Duggan et al., 2021).

Field validation, such as at the Northeast Tiger and Leopard National Park has confirmed the reliability of these models in real field conditions (Tan et al., 2022). Beyond image classification, artificial intelligence supports ecological modelling and prediction, for example, through multispecies deep networks and using data collected by citizens to better predict plant community composition (Brun et al., 2024) and integrating machine learning-based models in ecosystem service mapping (Kass et al., 2024). Mobile robotics are also being tested for real-time data collection and species identification (Panigrahi et al., 2023).

However, knowledge gaps and challenges remain, including data imbalance, model interpretability, computational costs, and limited generalization (Cipriano et al., 2025; Xu et al., 2024). Moreover, the environmental and ethical concerns of large language models, are also under increasing scrutiny, stressing the importance of sustainable artificial intelligence design (Rillig et al., 2023).

1.5.5. Capacity & knowledge

An additional challenge for businesses and financial institutions in engaging with biodiversity is that many businesses frequently lack the internal capacity to process, interpret, translate and apply relevant data for informing business and investor decisions (Ingram et al. 2024). Interdisciplinary collaborations among corporate sustainability scholars and conservation biologists can be helpful in this context (Panwar et al., 2023). In addition, civil society can play an important role in capacity building for businesses through the development of knowledge sharing platforms, resources and tools that can support businesses and financial institutions, in understanding and managing their impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and the risks and/or opportunities they present to the organization. Such resources and trainings should be tailored to support capacity building on biodiversity at multiple levels within an organization including the board of directors, executive leadership teams, managers, and others (Finance for Nature, n.d.; TNFD, 2025b; WBCSD, 2025). In addition, more effort is needed to support businesses and IPLCs on ways to engage and collaborate with each other on nature-related issues.

1.5.6. Partnerships and collaborations for transformative change

Fostering an enabling environment and catalyzing transformative change to halt biodiversity loss globally will require partnerships across government, the financial system, businesses and financial institutions, and other actors, (including civil society and IPLCs). **Section 1.4** highlights a broad, growing, and dynamic landscape of initiatives, frameworks, and collaborations among key actors that are driving these developments.

Landscape scale collective action partnerships and investments among business and other stakeholders are emerging globally (TCGF, 2022). For example, the private sector, district governments, civil society, and local communities have worked together to reduce deforestation, degradation of forests and peatland, and fire risk in the Siak Pelalawan Landscape Programme (SPLP) in the Siak province of Indonesia (TCGF, 2022). Similarly, the African Forest Landscape Restoration Initiative is a continent-wide partnership launched in 2015 between African governments, NGOs, technical groups like IUCN and NEPAD, private financiers (e.g., World Bank), and local communities and aims to restore over 100 million hectares of degraded land by 2030—targeting food security, climate resilience, and biodiversity recovery. As of late 2021, countries had committed more than 127 per cent of the target area (AFR100, n.d.).

Strategic collaborations among businesses, financial institutions and civil society can also influence policy agendas. For example, at the 15th meeting of the Conferences of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity, over 400 businesses business and finance institutions from 53 countries

participated in the “Make it Mandatory” campaign led by Business for Nature, a non-governmental organization, that sought to encourage governments to adopt mandatory requirements for disclosure by business within Target 15 as part of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (Business for Nature, n.d.-b). As part of the "Moving Together on Nature" campaign, 154 financial institutions signed a statement calling for an ambitious Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework to be adopted at COP15 to provide a clear mandate for economic actors, including financial institutions, to take meaningful action to halt and reverse biodiversity loss. This campaign was coordinated by the United Nations-backed Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI), the United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative (UNEP FI), and the Finance for Biodiversity Foundation (Finance for Biodiversity Foundation, n.d.; PRI et al., 2022).

Collaborations are also important for unlocking financing and funding, from public and private sectors, to support biodiversity and reach the targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. For example, debt-for-nature swaps implemented in the Seychelles, Belize, Barbados, Gabon, the Bahamas, Ecuador, the Galapagos Islands, and El Salvador have involved unique collaborations across national governments, philanthropies, development finance institutions, insurance businesses, non-governmental organizations, and others to unlock additional funding for biodiversity and support the achievement of national and international commitments, such as National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) and Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) (Escovar-Fadul et al., 2025; The Nature Conservancy, 2024; World Bank, 2018).

Collectively, these projects are expected to mobilize billions in conservation funding and help governments enhance protection and management of terrestrial, freshwater, and marine ecosystems (Escovar-Fadul et al., 2025; The Nature Conservancy, 2024). Another example includes the Living Amazon Mechanism that promotes conservation and regeneration in the Amazon region while fostering sustainable livelihoods (Green Finance Institute Hive et al., 2025). By linking businesses with Amazonian producers, it offers financing at competitive interest rates and targeted support to strengthen supply chains, increase production and build community resilience (CPI, 2024; Green Finance Institute Hive et al., 2025). Similarly, the Global Fund for Coral Reefs (GFCR) is helping to mobilize 100s of millions of dollars for businesses and projects that support coral reef conservation globally through a blended finance approach that strategically combines grants, concessional finance, and commercial investments to increase capital available for marine conservation initiatives (Global Fund for Coral Reefs (GFCR), 2025). The grants and concessional finance help reduce the perceived risk of investing in coral reef-focused projects or businesses, making them more attractive to private investors. Such blended finance approaches, along with other examples in **Section 1.5.2.3** demonstrate the potential impacts that can result from strategic partnerships across public and private sectors.

Actions by all actors, working individually, and together in partnerships across multiple sectors and parts of society, will be needed to deliver the global systemic change required for businesses to contribute to the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity and the goals of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, 2025b).

1.6. Summary

Nature continues to decline at unprecedented rates, threatening the stability and future of social, ecological, and economic systems around the world. The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework was a landmark international agreement that seeks to reverse these trends and lays out clear targets that must be met to restore, conserve and sustainably manage nature and halt its decline. Achieving these goals will require a whole of society approach, including the involvement and leadership of businesses and financial institutions.

Businesses and financial institutions also will be financially impacted by the loss of biodiversity, and, at the same time, are drivers of biodiversity loss globally. In addition, there is a growing recognition that business opportunities can emerge from actions and investments that positively impact biodiversity.

Businesses and financial institutions impact and depend upon many aspects of biodiversity and its contributions to people, with variations across sectors, geography, and size and scope of operations, supply chains, and investments. However, many businesses and financial institutions do not yet have a complete understanding of their impacts and dependencies on biodiversity, and how they may lead to risks and/or opportunities for their organizations, as well as, their stakeholders, and IPLCs. Numerous frameworks, tools, methods and approaches have been developed to support businesses and financial institutions in filling some of these knowledge gaps and in understanding, reporting, and managing their impacts and dependencies on biodiversity (as reviewed in **Chapters 2, 3 and 4** of this assessment). Addressing these knowledge gaps is an important step for businesses to implement the changes needed to achieve the goals of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and maintain resilient, profitable business operations, value chains, and investments. While the number of businesses and financial institutions that are aware of and reporting on biodiversity related issues has grown significantly in recent years, few business strategies and actions related to positively impacting biodiversity have been documented.

Key actors across multiple aspects of society will need to work together to advance the enabling environment that will bolster business actions, financing activities, and decisions that positively impact biodiversity and avoid its loss. The enabling environment needed to catalyse the transformative changes required to meet the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework must include policies, legislation and regulations; economic and financial frameworks; social norms, values and culture; technology and data; and capacity and knowledge that foster and incentivize the restoration, conservation, and sustainable management of biodiversity globally.

1.7. References

- A4S. (2024). *The business case for nature* (A4S Nature Guidance Series, p. 32). Accounting for Sustainability (A4S). <https://www.accountingforsustainability.org/guides>
- ACPR. (2024). *French insurers facing the risks associated with biodiversity loss: Challenges and lessons learned for the insurance industry and supervisors*. L'Autorité de contrôle prudentiel et de résolution - ACPR - Banque de France. https://acpr.banque-france.fr/sites/default/files/medias/documents/20240620_analyses_syntheses_biodiv_fr_en.pdf
- ADB. (2023). *Environmental and Social Framework (W-Paper)*. Asian Development Bank. <https://www.adb.org/documents/environmental-and-social-framework>
- AFR100. (n.d.). *African Forest Landscape Restoration Initiative (AFR100)*. Retrieved <https://afr100.org/>
- Alicke, K., & Foster, T. (2024). *Supply chains: Still vulnerable* (Operations Practice, p. 10). McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/operations/our-insights/supply-chain-risk-survey#/>
- Alvarez, J., Postel-Vinay, N., Guckenberger, M., Lee, J., Lambin, R., O'Donnell, E., & Pasqua, C. (2025). *Nature-related financial risks database (June 2025)*. Resilient Planet Finance Lab, Environmental Change Institute, University of Oxford. <https://infinbio.org/nature-related-financial-risks-database>
- Andersen, I., Ishii, N., Brooks, T., Cummis, C., Fonseca, G., Hillers, A., Macfarlane, N., Nakicenovic, N., Moss, K., Rockström, J., Steer, A., Waughray, D., & Zimm, C. (2021). Defining 'science-based targets.' *National Science Review*, 8(7), nwaal86. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwaa186>
- Anderson, C. M., DeFries, R. S., Litterman, R., Matson, P. A., Nepstad, D. C., Pacala, S., Schlesinger, W. H., Shaw, M. R., Smith, P., Weber, C., & Field, C. B. (2019). Natural climate solutions are not enough. *Science*, 363(6430), 933–934. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaw2741>
- Arabadjieva, K. (2016). 'Better Regulation' in Environmental Impact Assessment: The Amended EIA Directive. *Journal of Environmental Law*, 28(1), 159–168. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jel/eqw001>
- Armstrong, D. I., Staal, A., Abrams, J. F., Winkelmann, R., Sakschewski, B., Loriani, S., Fetzer, I., Cornell, S. E., Rockström, J., & Lenton, T. M. (2022). Exceeding 1.5°C global warming could trigger multiple climate tipping points. *Science*, 377(6611), eabn7950. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abn7950>
- Asian Development Bank (ADB). (2022). *Insurance for Protecting Marine and Coastal Ecosystems* (p. 7). Asian Development Bank. <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/829001/insurance-protecting-marine-coastal-ecosystems.pdf>
- Bagstad, K. J., Ingram, J. C., Shapiro, C. D., La Notte, A., Maes, J., Vallecillo, S., Casey, C. F., Glynn, P. D., Heris, M. P., Johnson, J. A., Lauer, C., Matuszak, J., Oleson, K. L. L., Posner, S. M., Rhodes, C., & Voigt, B. (2021). Lessons learned from development of natural capital accounts in the United States and European Union. *Ecosystem Services*, 52, 101359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2021.101359>
- Bai, X., Bjørn, A., Kılıç, Ş., Sabag Muñoz, O., Whiteman, G., Hoff, H., Seaby Andersen, L., & Rockström, J. (2022). How to stop cities and companies causing planetary harm. *Nature*, 609(7927), 463–466. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-02894-3>

- Balehegn, M. (2016). Ecological and Social Wisdom in Camel Praise Poetry Sung by Afar Nomads of Ethiopia. *Journal of Ethnobiology*, 36(2), 457–472. <https://doi.org/10.2993/0278-0771-36.2.457>
- BankTrack. (2023). *Banks and Nature* [Online post]. https://www.banktrack.org/campaign/banks_and_nature
- Banque de France. (2021). *A “Silent Spring” for the Financial System? Exploring Biodiversity-Related Financial Risks in France* (Working Paper Series No. 826). <https://publications.banque-france.fr/en/silent-spring-financial-system-exploring-biodiversity-related-financial-risks-france>
- Barclay, S. H., & Steele, M. (2021). Rethinking protections for Indigenous sacred sites. *Harvard Law Review*, 134, 1294.
- BCG. (2021). *The Biodiversity Crisis Is a Business Crisis*. Boston Consulting Group. <https://www.bcg.com/publications/2021/biodiversity-loss-business-implications-responses>
- Beck-O’Brien, M., & Bringezu, S. (2021). Biodiversity Monitoring in Long-Distance Food Supply Chains: Tools, Gaps and Needs to Meet Business Requirements and Sustainability Goals. *Sustainability*, 13(15), Article 15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13158536>
- Berkes, F., Colding, J., & Folke, C. (2000). REDISCOVERY OF TRADITIONAL ECOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE AS ADAPTIVE MANAGEMENT. *Ecological Applications*, 10(5).
- Besson, M., Alison, J., Bjerger, K., Goroehowski, T. E., Høye, T. T., Jucker, T., Mann, H. M. R., & Clements, C. F. (2022). Towards the fully automated monitoring of ecological communities. *Ecology Letters*, 25(12), 2753–2775. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.14123>
- Bidaud, C., Schreckenber, K., & Jones, J. P. G. (2018). The local costs of biodiversity offsets: Comparing standards, policy and practice. *Land Use Policy*, 77, 43–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2018.05.003>
- Bidaud, C., Schreckenber, K., Rabeharison, M., Ranjatson, P., Gibbons, J., & Jones, Julia P. G. (2017). The Sweet and the Bitter: Intertwined Positive and Negative Social Impacts of a Biodiversity Offset. *Conservation and Society*, 15(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0972-4923.196315>
- Bjelle, E. L., Kuipers, K., Verones, F., & Wood, R. (2021). Trends in national biodiversity footprints of land use. *Ecological Economics*, 185, 107059. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECOLECON.2021.107059>
- BloombergNEF. (2023, September 12). *When the Bee Stings Counting the Cost of Nature-Related Risks*. https://assets.bbhub.io/professional/sites/24/BNEF_Nature-Risk.pdf
- BloombergNEF. (2024). *Opportunity Blossoms: The Business of Curbing Nature Loss* (p. 55). BloombergNEF. <https://assets.bbhub.io/professional/sites/24/Nature-Opportunities-2024.pdf>
- Boardman, A. E., & Vining, A. R. (1989). Ownership and Performance in Competitive Environments: A Comparison of the Performance of Private, Mixed, and State-Owned Enterprises. *The Journal of Law and Economics*, 32(1), 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1086/467167>
- Bocken, N. M. P., Short, S. W., Rana, P., & Evans, S. (2014). A literature and practice review to develop sustainable business model archetypes. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 65, 12–56. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.11.039>
- Boldrini, S., Ceglar, A., Lelli, C., Parisi, L., & Heemskerk, I. (2023). Living in a World of Disappearing Nature: Physical Risk and the Implications for Financial Stability. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4630721>
- Bond, A., Pope, J., Fundingsland, M., Morrison-Saunders, A., Retief, F., & Hauptfleisch, M. (2020). Explaining the political nature of environmental impact assessment (EIA): A neo-Gramscian

- perspective. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 244, 118694.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118694>
- Booth, H., Milner-Gulland, E. J., McCormick, N., & Starkey, M. (2024). Operationalizing transformative change for business in the context of Nature Positive. *One Earth*, S2590332224002951. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2024.06.003>
- Botchwey, G., Crawford, G., Loubere, N., & Lu, J. (2019). South-South Irregular Migration: The Impacts of China's Informal Gold Rush in Ghana. *International Migration*, 57(4), 310–328. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imig.12518>
- Bothmann, L., Wimmer, L., Charrakh, O., Weber, T., Edelhoff, H., Peters, W., Nguyen, H., Benjamin, C., & Menzel, A. (2023). Automated wildlife image classification: An active learning tool for ecological applications. *Ecological Informatics*, 77, 102231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2023.102231>
- Bromley, H. (2023). *Ten Case Studies Highlight the Financial Costs of Nature-related Risk*. <https://about.bnef.com/blog/ten-case-studies-highlight-the-financial-costs-of-nature-related-risk/>. <https://about.bnef.com/blog/ten-case-studies-highlight-the-financial-costs-of-nature-related-risk/>
- Brondizio, E., Diaz, S., Settele, J., Ngo, H. T., Gueze, M., Aumeeruddy-Thomas, Y., Bai, X., Geschke, A., Molnár, Z., Niamir, A., Pascual, U., Simcock, A., & Jaureguiberry, P. (with Santin Brancalion, P. H., Chan, K., Dubertret, F., Hendry, A., Liu, J., Martin, A., Martín-López, B., Midgley, G., Obura, D., Oliver, T., Scheffran, J., Seppelt, R., Strassburg, B., Spangenberg, J., Stenseke, M., Turnhout, E., Williams, M. J., Zayas, C., Mooney, H., ... Carneiro Da Cunha, M. M.). (2019). *Chapter 1 Assessing a planet in transformation: Rationale and approach of the IPBES Global Assessment on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3831852>
- Brook, B. W., Buettel, J. C., Van Lunteren, P., Rajmohan, P. P., & Aandahl, R. Z. (2025). MEWC: A user-friendly AI workflow for customised wildlife-image classification. *Peer Community Journal*, 5, e57. <https://doi.org/10.24072/pcjournal.565>
- Brun, P., Karger, D. N., Zurell, D., Descombes, P., De Witte, L. C., De Lutio, R., Wegner, J. D., & Zimmermann, N. E. (2024). Multispecies deep learning using citizen science data produces more informative plant community models. *Nature Communications*, 15(1), 4421. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-48559-9>
- Buckwell, A., & Morgan, E. A. (2022). *Chapter 3 Ecosystem services and natural capital: Application to sustainable finance*. <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/9783110733488-003/html>
- Buma, B., Gordon, D. R., Kleisner, K. M., Bartuska, A., Bidlack, A., DeFries, R., Ellis, P., Friedlingstein, P., Metzger, S., Morgan, G., Novick, K., Sanchirico, J. N., Collins, J. R., Eagle, A. J., Fujita, R., Holst, E., Lavallee, J. M., Lubowski, R. N., Melikov, C., ... Hamburg, S. P. (2024). Expert review of the science underlying nature-based climate solutions. *Nature Climate Change*, 14(4), 402–406. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-024-01960-0>
- Busch, T., Hamprecht, J., & Waddock, S. (2018). Value(s) for Whom? Creating Value(s) for Stakeholders. *Organization & Environment*, 31(3), 210–222. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1086026618793962>
- Business for Biodiversity & We Mean Business. (2021). *Building Integrated Policies for the Planet: How Governments can Drive Business Action on Nature and Climate*. <https://www.businessfornature.org/news/building-integrated-policies>
- Business for Nature. (n.d.-a). *About Business for Nature*. Retrieved <https://www.businessfornature.org/about>

- Business for Nature. (n.d.-b). *Make It Mandatory*. Retrieved <https://www.businessfornature.org/make-it-mandatory-campaign>
- Business for Nature. (n.d.-c). *Sector Actions Towards a Nature-Positive Future*. Retrieved July 12, 2024, from <https://www.businessfornature.org/sector-actions>
- Butt, N., Lambrick, F., Menton, M., & Renwick, A. (2019). The supply chain of violence. *Nature Sustainability*, 2(8), 742–747. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0349-4>
- Caldecott, B. (2017). Introduction to special issue: Stranded assets and the environment. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 7(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20430795.2016.1266748>
- Calice, P., Diaz Kalan, F., & Miguel, F. (2021). *Nature-Related Financial Risks in Brazil*. The World Bank. <https://doi.org/10.1596/1813-9450-9759>
- Capgemini Research Institute. (2023). *Preserving the Fabric of Life: Why Biodiversity Loss is as Urgent as Climate Change* (p. 76). Capgemini Research Institute. <https://prod.ucwe.capgemini.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/Final-Web-Version-Report-Biodiversity-1.pdf>
- Carvalho, S. H. C. D., Cojoianu, T., & Ascui, F. (2023). From impacts to dependencies: A first global assessment of corporate biodiversity risk exposure and responses. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(5), 2600–2614. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3142>
- CBD. (2011). *Convention on Biological Diversity: Text and annexes*. Convention on Biological Diversity. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/legal/cbd-en.pdf>
- CBD. (2022). *Decision Adopted by the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity. 15/4. Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework*. Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-15/cop-15-dec-04-en.pdf>
- CBD. (2023a). *15/4. Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework*. Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).
- CBD. (2023b). *Business Collaboration in Achieving the Goals of the Convention of Biological Diversity*. Welcome to the Business Engagement Programme. <https://www.cbd.int/business/default.shtml>
- CBD. (2023c). *Guidance on integrating human rights in National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plans (NBSAPs)* (p. 15). Convention on Biological Diversity. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/nbsap/Integrating-human%20rights-in-NBSAPs.pdf>
- CBD. (2025a). *GUIDE TO THE CALI FUND: SHARING THE BENEFITS OF GENETIC DATA FROM NATURE*. <https://www.cbd.int/article/Publication-Guide-to-Cali-Fund>
- CBD. (2025b, February 27). *COP 16 has fulfilled its promise to the world*. <https://www.cbd.int/article/cop16-resumed-session-closing-2025>
- CDP. (2023a). *High-Quality Mandatory Disclosure* (p. 59). CDP. https://cdn.cdp.net/cdp-production/cms/policy_briefings/documents/000/007/292/original/CDP_High_Quality_Mandatory_Disclosure.pdf?1693840960
- CDP. (2023b). *The Forest Transition: From Risk to Resilience*. https://cdn.cdp.net/cdp-production/cms/reports/documents/000/007/182/original/CDP_Global_Forest_Report_2023.pdf?1688396252
- CDP. (2025). *Biodiversity Targets*. CDP. <https://www.cdp.net/en/insights/biodiversity-targets>
- CERES. (2024). *Exploring Nature Impacts and Dependencies: A Field Guide to Eight Key Sectors*. Nature Action 100. <https://www.ceres.org/resources/reports/exploring-nature-impacts-and-dependencies-field-guide-eight-key-sectors>

- Ceres & Nature Action 100. (2024). *Exploring Nature Impacts and Dependencies: A Field Guide to Eight Key Sectors* (p. 36). Ceres on behalf of Nature Action 100.
<https://www.ceres.org/resources/reports/exploring-nature-impacts-and-dependencies-field-guide>
- Chaplin-Kramer, R., Neugarten, R. A., Sharp, R. P., Collins, P. M., Polasky, S., Hole, D., Schuster, R., Strimas-Mackey, M., Mulligan, M., Brandon, C., Diaz, S., Fluet-Chouinard, E., Gorenflo, L. J., Johnson, J. A., Kennedy, C. M., Keys, P. W., Longley-Wood, K., McIntyre, P. B., Noon, M., ... Watson, R. A. (2023). Mapping the planet's critical natural assets. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 7(1), 51–61. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-022-01934-5>
- Chettri, N., & Sharma, E. (2022). Contribution of Traditional Ecological Knowledge on Biodiversity Conservation—A Retrospective from the Hindu Kush Himalaya. In S. C. Rai & P. K. Mishra (Eds.), *Traditional Ecological Knowledge of Resource Management in Asia* (pp. 261–271). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-16840-6_15
- Christiaen, C., Lockwood, P., Jackman, A., & Caldecott, B. (2025). Location, location, location: Asset location data sources for nature-related financial risk analysis. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 74, 101527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2025.101527>
- Christiansen, H. (2011). *The Size and Composition of the SOE Sector in OECD Countries* (OECD Corporate Governance Working Papers No. 5; OECD Corporate Governance Working Papers, Vol. 5). <https://doi.org/10.1787/5kg54cwps0s3-en>
- Cipriano, C., Noce, S., Mereu, S., & Santini, M. (2025). Algorithms going wild – A review of machine learning techniques for terrestrial ecology. *Ecological Modelling*, 506, 111164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2025.111164>
- CISL. (2020a). *Biodiversity Loss and Land Degradation: An Overview of the Financial Materiality* (p. 13). University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership. <https://www.cisl.cam.ac.uk/system/files/documents/biodiversity-loss-and-land-degradation-overview.pdf>
- CISL. (2020b). *Measuring business impacts on nature: A framework to support better stewardship of biodiversity in global supply chains* [Text]. University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership (CISL). <https://www.cisl.cam.ac.uk/resources/natural-resource-security-publications/measuring-business-impacts-on-nature>
- CITES. (1973). *Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora*. <https://cites.org/sites/default/files/eng/disc/CITES-Convention-EN.pdf>
- CITES. (2019). *CITES and Livelihoods: Vicuña management in Bolivia*. Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES). https://cites.org/sites/default/files/eng/prog/Livelihoods/case_studies/CITES_livelihoods_Fact_Sheet_2019_Bolivia_Vicuna.pdf
- Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). (2022, December). *Decision COP 15/4: Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework*. <https://www.cbd.int/decisions/cop/15/4>
- Costanza, R. (2008). Ecosystem services: Multiple classification systems are needed. *Biological Conservation*, 141(2), 350–352. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2007.12.020>
- Cowger, W., Willis, K. A., Bullock, S., Conlon, K., Emmanuel, J., Erdle, L. M., Eriksen, M., Farrelly, T. A., Hardesty, B. D., Kerge, K., Li, N., Li, Y., Liebman, A., Tangri, N., Thiel, M., Villarrubia-Gómez, P., Walker, T. R., & Wang, M. (2024). Global producer responsibility for plastic pollution. *Science Advances*, 10(17), eadj8275. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adj8275>

- CPI. (2024). *Toolbox on Financing Nature-Based Solutions* (p. 72). Climate Policy Initiative. <https://www.climatepolicyinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Report-Toolbox-on-Financing-Nature-Based-Solutions.pdf>
- Crawford, G., Chisanga, C. N., & Fraser, A. (2015). *Creating and Sharing Value: The Development of Beneficiation in Zambia's Mining Sector* (p. 73). International Growth Centre (IGC). <https://www.theigc.org/sites/default/files/2016/08/Crawford-et-al-2015-Final-Report-1.pdf>
- Daily, G. C. (1997). *Nature's Service: Societal Dependence on Natural Ecosystems*. Island Press.
- Danielsen, F., Eicken, H., Funder, M., Johnson, N., Lee, O., Theilade, I., Argyriou, D., & Burgess, N. D. (2022). Community Monitoring of Natural Resource Systems and the Environment. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 47(1), 637–670. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-012220-022325>
- Dasgupta, P. (2020). *The Economics of Biodiversity: The Dasgupta Review – Interim Report* (No. PU2964). HM Treasury. <https://www.gov.uk/official-documents>
- Dasgupta, P. (with Großbritannien). (2021). *The economics of biodiversity: The Dasgupta review: abridged version* (Updated: 2 February 2021). HM Treasury.
- Dasgupta, P. (2025). *On natural capital: The value of the world around us*. Witness Books.
- Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH. (2023). *Catalysing Finance and Insurance for Nature-based Solutions* (p. 57). GIZ. https://www.greenfinanceplatform.org/sites/default/files/downloads/best-practices/GIZ_August%202023_Catalysing%20Finance%20and%20Insurance%20for%20Nature-based%20Solutions.pdf
- Díaz, S., Demissew, S., Carabias, J., Joly, C., Lonsdale, M., Ash, N., Larigauderie, A., Adhikari, J. R., Arico, S., Báldi, A., Bartuska, A., Baste, I. A., Bilgin, A., Brondizio, E., Chan, K. M., Figueroa, V. E., Duraïappah, A., Fischer, M., Hill, R., ... Zlatanova, D. (2015). The IPBES Conceptual Framework—Connecting nature and people. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability, Open Issue*, 14, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2014.11.002>
- Díaz, S., Pascual, U., Stenseke, M., Martín-López, B., Watson, R. T., Molnár, Z., Hill, R., Chan, K. M. A., Baste, I. A., Brauman, K. A., Polasky, S., Church, A., Lonsdale, M., Larigauderie, A., Leadley, P. W., Van Oudenhoven, A. P. E., Van Der Plaats, F., Schröter, M., Lavorel, S., ... Shirayama, Y. (2018). Assessing nature's contributions to people. *Science*, 359(6373), 270–272. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aap8826>
- DNB & PBL. (2020). *Indebted to nature – Exploring biodiversity risks for the Dutch financial sector*. De Nederlandsche Bank (DNB) and PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency. <https://www.dnb.nl/media/4c3fqawd/indebted-to-nature.pdf>
- Dobinson, T., Gower, G., & Fahey-Palma, T. (2023). Anthropogenic impacts of mining on indigenous peoples in Western Australia: Divergent values. *Ethnicities*, 14687968231219582. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14687968231219582>
- Donaldson, T., & Walsh, J. P. (2015). Toward a theory of business. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 35, 181–207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.riob.2015.10.002>
- Dou, J., Su, E., & Wang, S. (2019). When Does Family Ownership Promote Proactive Environmental Strategy? The Role of the Firm's Long-Term Orientation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 158(1), 81–95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-017-3642-z>
- Duggan, M. T., Groleau, M. F., Shealy, E. P., Self, L. S., Utter, T. E., Waller, M. M., Hall, B. C., Stone, C. G., Anderson, L. L., & Mousseau, T. A. (2021). An approach to rapid processing of camera trap images with minimal human input. *Ecology and Evolution*, 11(17), 12051–12063. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.7970>
- EC. (2022). *Corporate sustainability due diligence*. https://commission.europa.eu/business-economy-euro/doing-business-eu/corporate-sustainability-due-diligence_en

- EC. (2023). *Regulation on Deforestation-free products*. European Commission.
https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/forests/deforestation/regulation-deforestation-free-products_en
- ECB (with Ceglar, A., Boldrini, S., Lelli, C., Parisi, L., & Heemskerk, I.). (2023). *The Impact of the Euro Area Economy and Banks on Biodiversity* (No. 335; Occasional Paper Series, p. 36). European Central Bank (ECB). <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2866/3563>
- EDFI. (2022). *Summary on Investments and Human Rights* (p. 2). Association of European Development Finance Institutions. <https://www.edfi.eu/>
- EFRAG. (2024a). *EFRAG IG 1: Materiality Assessment Implementation Guidance*. European Financial Reporting Advisory Group (EFRAG).
https://www.efrag.org/Assets/Download?assetUrl=/sites/webpublishing/SiteAssets/IG+1+Materiality+Assessment_final.pdf
- EFRAG. (2024b). *ESRS–ISSB Standards Interoperability Guidance* (p. 33). European Financial Reporting Advisory Group.
<https://www.efrag.org/sites/default/files/sites/webpublishing/SiteAssets/ESRS-ISSB%20Standards%20Interoperability%20Guidance.pdf>
- EFRAG. (2025). *EFRAG 2025 State of Play" market study portal*.
https://insights.efrag.org/?utm_source=substack&utm_medium=email
- EIOPA. (2023). *EIOPA Staff paper on nature-related risks and impacts for insurance*. European Insurance and Occupational Pensions Authority.
https://www.eiopa.europa.eu/document/download/9525e286-3253-44b7-81d1-2051e0b05a9c_en?filename=EIOPA%20Staff%20paper%20-%20Nature-related%20risks%20and%20impacts%20for%20insurance.pdf
- El-Fadl, K., & El-Fadel, M. (2004). Comparative assessment of EIA systems in MENA countries: Challenges and prospects. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 24(6), 553–593.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2004.01.004>
- ENCORE. (2025). *Economic activities*. <https://encorenature.org/en/data-and-methodology/sectors>
- Environment Act 2021 (2021). <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2021/30/schedule/14>
- Escovar-Fadul, X., Griswold, K., Gatchev, S., Monteiro, C., Smith, J., Revellino, P., & Garvey, M. (2025). *Practice Standards for Debt Conversion Projects for Nature, Resilience, and People* (Version 1.0). The Nature Conservancy. <https://www.nature.org/en-us/what-we-do/our-priorities/protect-water-and-land/land-and-water-stories/nature-bonds/>
- European Commission. (2025a, January 27). *Nature restoration law: Commission welcomes final adoption*. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_25_614
- European Commission. (2025b, February 26). *Omnibus I package: Commission simplifies rules for sustainability and EU investments delivering over €6 billion in administrative relief*. https://finance.ec.europa.eu/publications/omnibus-i-package-commission-simplifies-rules-sustainability-and-eu-investments-delivering-over-eu6_en
- European Commission. (2025c, June 11). *Commission adopts a quick fix for companies already conducting corporate sustainability reporting*. Press Release.
https://finance.ec.europa.eu/publications/commission-adopts-quick-fix-companies-already-conducting-corporate-sustainability-reporting_en
- European Council. (2023). *Nature restoration: Council and Parliament reach agreement on new rules to restore and preserve degraded habitats in the EU*.
<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2023/11/09/nature-restoration-council-and-parliament-reach-agreement-on-new-rules-to-restore-and-preserve-degraded-habitats-in-the-eu/>

- European Research Executive Agency. (2024, December 9). *EU-funded projects leading the way to transformative change for biodiversity*. https://rea.ec.europa.eu/news/eu-funded-projects-leading-way-transformative-change-biodiversity-2024-12-09_en
- European Union. (2022, December 14). *Directive (EU) 2022/2464 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 amending Regulation (EU) No 537/2014, Directive 2004/109/EC, Directive 2006/43/EC and Directive 2013/34/EU, as regards corporate sustainability reporting (Text with EEA relevance) (Issue 2022/2464)*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022L2464>
- EY. (2024). *Using transparency to drive action to protect and restore nature EY Nature Risk Barometer 2024* (p. 36). Ernst & Young Global Limited. <https://www.ey.com/content/dam/ey-unified-site/ey-com/en-us/insights/climate-change-sustainability-services/documents/ey-nature-risk-barometer-2024.pdf>
- FAO. (2019). *Bolivia's sweet new industry*. <https://www.fao.org/newsroom/story/Bolivia-s-sweet-new-industry/es>
- Feger, C., & Mermet, L. (2022). New Business Models for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Management Services: Action Research With a Large Environmental Sector Company. *Organization & Environment*, 35(2), 252–281. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1086026620947145>
- Fernández-Llamazares, Á., Garteizgogeoasca, M., Basu, N., Brondizio, E. S., Cabeza, M., Martínez-Alier, J., McElwee, P., & Reyes-García, V. (2020). A State-of-the-Art Review of Indigenous Peoples and Environmental Pollution. *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management*, 16(3), 324–341. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.4239>
- Finance for Biodiversity Foundation. (n.d.). *About the Pledge*. Retrieved <https://www.financeforbiodiversity.org/about-the-pledge/>
- Finance for Nature. (n.d.). *Finance for Nature – Resources*. Retrieved <https://financefornature.unep.org/resources>
- Flores, B. M., Montoya, E., Sakschewski, B., Nascimento, N., Staal, A., Betts, R. A., Levis, C., Lapola, D. M., Esquivel-Muelbert, A., Jakovac, C., Nobre, C. A., Oliveira, R. S., Borma, L. S., Nian, D., Boers, N., Hecht, S. B., Ter Steege, H., Arriera, J., Lucas, I. L., ... Hirota, M. (2024). Critical transitions in the Amazon forest system. *Nature*, 626(7999), 555–564. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06970-0>
- Forest Peoples Programme, International Indigenous Forum on Biodiversity, Indigenous Women's Biodiversity Network, Centres of Distinction on Indigenous and Local Knowledge, & Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity. (2020). *Local Biodiversity Outlooks 2: The contributions of indigenous peoples and local communities to the implementation of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 and to renewing nature and cultures. A complement to the fifth edition of Global Biodiversity Outlook*. Forest Peoples Programme. www.localbiodiversityoutlooks.net
- Forico. (2023). *Natural Capital Report 2022*. <https://forico.com.au/natural-capital>
- FSB. (2024). *Achieving Consistent and Comparable Climate-related Disclosures 2024 Progress report* (p. 43). Financial Stability Board. <https://www.fsb.org/uploads/P121124.pdf>
- FSDA. (2024). *Progress Report: Finance Sector Deforestation Action (FSDA)* (p. 36). Finance Sector Deforestation Action (FSDA) and UN Climate Change High-Level Champions. <https://www.climatechampions.net/media/cnjfueq/fsda-progress-report-june-2024.pdf>
- Gartenberg, C. M., Prat, A., & Serafeim, G. (2016). Corporate Purpose and Financial Performance. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2840005>
- GBIHR. (2023). *Integrating human rights into company climate action: Insights from business practitioners*. Global Business Initiative on Business and Human Rights.

https://gbih.org/images/docs/GBI_Resource_-_Integrating_human_rights_into_climate_action_2024.pdf

- GEF. (2019). *Environmental and Social Safeguard Standards*. The Global Environment Facility (GEF). <https://www.thegef.org/documents/environmental-and-social-safeguard-standards>
- Gereffi, G. (2019). Economic upgrading in global value chains. In S. Ponte, G. Gereffi, & G. Raj-Reichert (Eds.), *Handbook on Global Value Chains*. Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781788113779.00022>
- Gereffi, G., Humphrey, J., & Sturgeon, T. (2005). The governance of global value chains. *Review of International Political Economy*, 12(1), 78–104. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09692290500049805>
- Gërxhani, K. (2004). The Informal Sector in Developed and Less Developed Countries: A Literature Survey. *Public Choice*, 120(3/4), 267–300. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:PUCH.0000044287.88147.5e>
- Girard, F., Hall, I., & Frison, C. (2022). *Biocultural Rights, Indigenous Peoples And Local Communities: Protecting Culture and the Environment* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003172642>
- Global Fund for Coral Reefs (GFCR). (2025). *About the Global Fund for Coral Reefs*. About. <https://globalfundcoralreefs.org/about/>
- Golez, A. M. P. (2015). Perpetuity of Family-Owned Business in the Philippines: Managing the Ecological Threat. *Asian Journal of Biodiversity*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.7828/ajob.v6i1.700>
- Goyal, A. (2006). Corporate Social Responsibility as a Signalling Device for Foreign Direct Investment. *International Journal of the Economics of Business*, 13(1), 145–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13571510500520077>
- Green Finance Institute. (2024). *Assessing the Materiality of Nature-Related Financial Risks for the UK*. <https://hive.greenfinanceinstitute.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/GFI-GREENING-FINANCE-FOR-NATURE-FINAL-FULL-REPORT-RDS4.pdf>
- Green Finance Institute Hive, UNDP Biodiversity Finance Initiative (BIOFIN), & UNEP Finance Initiative (UNEP FI). (2025). *Revenues for Supplier Cooperatives and Associations in the Brazilian Amazon through Sustainable Supply Chains, The Living Amazon Mechanism* (Revenues for Nature Guidebook Series, p. 49). Revenues for Nature (R4N). <https://hive.greenfinanceinstitute.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/R4N-GUIDEBOOKS-BRAZIL-LAM.pdf>
- Green, P. A., Vörösmarty, C. J., Koehler, D. A., Brown, C., Rex, W., Rodriguez Osuna, V., & Tessler, Z. (2024). Mapping a sustainable water future: Private sector opportunities for global water security and resilience. *Global Environmental Change*, 88, 102906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2024.102906>
- GRI. (2022). *The Materiality Madness: Why definitions matter* (No. 3; The GRI Perspective, p. 4). Global Reporting Initiative. <https://www.globalreporting.org/media/r2oojx53/gri-perspective-the-materiality-madness.pdf>
- GRI. (2024a). *GRI - Topic Standard Project for Biodiversity*. Global Reporting Initiative. <https://www.globalreporting.org/standards/standards-development/topic-standard-project-for-biodiversity/>
- GRI. (2024b, June 30). *GRI and TNFD make reporting on biodiversity easier*. <https://www.globalreporting.org/news/news-center/gri-and-tnfd-make-reporting-on-biodiversity-easier/>
- Griscom, B. W., Adams, J., Ellis, P. W., Houghton, R. A., Lomax, G., Miteva, D. A., Schlesinger, W. H., Shoch, D., Siikamäki, J. V., Smith, P., Woodbury, P., Zganjar, C., Blackman, A., Campari, J., Conant, R. T., Delgado, C., Elias, P., Gopalakrishna, T., Hamsik, M. R., ...

- Fargione, J. (2017). Natural climate solutions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(44), 11645–11650. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1710465114>
- Hadji-Lazaro, P., Salin, M., Svartzman, R., Espagne, E., Gauthey, J., Berger, J., Calas, J., Godin, A., & Vallier, A. (2024). Biodiversity loss and financial stability as a new frontier for central banks: An exploration for France. *Ecological Economics*, 223, 108246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2024.108246>
- Hassan, A., Roberts, L., & Rodger, K. (2022). Corporate accountability for biodiversity and species extinction: Evidence from organisations reporting on their impacts on nature. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 31(1), 326–352. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2890>
- Heinze, C., Blenckner, T., Martins, H., Rusiecka, D., Döscher, R., Gehlen, M., Gruber, N., Holland, E., Hov, Ø., Joos, F., Matthews, J. B. R., Rødven, R., & Wilson, S. (2021). The quiet crossing of ocean tipping points. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(9), e2008478118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2008478118>
- Hill, R., Adem, Ç., Alangui, W. V., Molnár, Z., Aumeeruddy-Thomas, Y., Bridgewater, P., Tengö, M., Thaman, R., Adou Yao, C. Y., Berkes, F., Carino, J., Carneiro Da Cunha, M., Diaw, M. C., Díaz, S., Figueroa, V. E., Fisher, J., Hardison, P., Ichikawa, K., Kariuki, P., ... Xue, D. (2020). Working with Indigenous, local and scientific knowledge in assessments of nature and nature's linkages with people. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 43, 8–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2019.12.006>
- Hill, R., Díaz, S., Pascual, U., Stenseke, M., Molnár, Z., & Van Velden, J. (2021). Nature's contributions to people: Weaving plural perspectives. *One Earth*, 4(7), 910–915. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2021.06.009>
- Houdet, J., & Teren, G. (2022). *Quality Biodiversity Footprint Assessments in Practice: Why Organisational Biodiversity Accounting Matters. A Position Paper of the Biodiversity Disclosure Project (BDP)*. National Biodiversity and Business Network, Endangered Wildlife Trust, South Africa.
- Hugé, J., de Bisthoven, L. J., Mushieta, M., Rochette, A.-J., Candido, S., Keunen, H., Dahdouh-Guebas, F., Koedam, N., & Vanhove, M. P. M. (2020). EIA-driven biodiversity mainstreaming in development cooperation: Confronting expectations and practice in the DR Congo. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 104, 107–120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2019.11.003>
- IBAT. (2021). *IBAT Annual Report 2021* (p. 18). IBAT Alliance (BirdLife International, Conservation International, IUCN, UNEP-WCMC). <https://app.ibat-alliance.org/pdf/ibat-annual-report-2021.pdf>
- IFC. (2007). *Stakeholder Engagement: A Good Practice Handbook for Companies Doing Business in Emerging Markets*. International Finance Corporation. https://www.ifc.org/wps/wcm/connect/topics_ext_content/ifc_external_corporate_site/sustainability-at-ifc/publications/publications_handbook_stakeholderengagement_wci_1319577185063
- IFC. (2012). *IFC Performance Standards on Environmental and Social Sustainability* (p. 72). International Finance Corporation. https://www.ifc.org/wps/wcm/connect/topics_ext_content/ifc_external_corporate_site/sustainability-at-ifc/publications/publications_handbook_pps
- IFC. (2023). *Biodiversity Finance Reference Guide—Building on the Green Bond Principles and Green Loan Principles*. International Finance Corporation (IFC).
- IFRS. (2023). *IFRS S1 General Requirements for Disclosure of Sustainability-related Financial Information*. <https://www.ifrs.org/issued-standards/ifrs-sustainability-standards-navigator/ifrs-s1-general-requirements/>

- IIGCC, PRI, & Eurosif. (2025, February 4). *Investor joint statement on Omnibus Legislation*.
<https://www.unpri.org/eu-policy/investor-joint-statement-on-european-commissions-omnibus-legislation/13025.article>
- ILO. (1972). *Employment, income and equality: A strategy for increasing productivity in Kenya* (p. 593). International Labor Office (ILO).
https://labordoc.ilo.org/discovery/fulldisplay/alma991450513402676/41ILO_INST:41ILO_V2
- ILO and UNEP FI. (2023). *Just Transition Finance: Pathways for Banking and Insurance*.
https://www.unepfi.org/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Just-transition-finance_Pathway-for-Banking-and-Insurance.pdf
- Ingram, G. (2020, April 6). *Civil Society: An Essential Ingredient of Development*. Brookings Institution – Global Economy & Development Commentary.
<https://www.brookings.edu/articles/civil-society-an-essential-ingredient-of-development/>
- Ingram, J. C., Bagstad, K. J., Vardon, M., Rhodes, C. R., Posner, S., Casey, C. F., Glynn, P. D., & Shapiro, C. D. (2022). Opportunities for businesses to use and support development of SEEA-aligned natural capital accounts. *Ecosystem Services*, 55, 101434.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2022.101434>
- Ingram, J. C., McKenzie, E. J., Bagstad, K. J., Finisdore, J., Van Den Berg, R., Fenichel, E., Vardon, M., Posner, S., Santamaria, M., Mandle, L., Barker, R., & Spurgeon, J. (2024). Leveraging natural capital accounting to support businesses with nature-related risk assessments and disclosures. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 379(1903), 20220328. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2022.0328>
- Instituto Socioambiental. (2024). *Indígenas da Terra Raposa Serra do Sol vão receber pagamentos por serviços ambientais*. <https://terrasindigenas.org.br/pt-br/noticia/216199>
- IPBES. (2016a). *The assessment report of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services on pollinators, pollination and food production*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3402856>
- IPBES. (2016b). *The methodological assessment report on scenarios and models of biodiversity and ecosystem services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3235428>
- IPBES (with Montanarella, L., Scholes, R., & Brainich, A.). (2018a). *The IPBES assessment report on land degradation and restoration*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3237392>
- IPBES (with Archer, E., Luthando E. Dziba, Kulemani Jo Mulongoy, Malebajoa Anicia Maoela, & Walters, M.). (2018b). *The IPBES regional assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services for Africa*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3236177>
- IPBES (with Karki, M., Sellamuttu, S. S., Okayasu, S., & Suzuki, W.). (2018c). *The IPBES regional assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services for Asia and the Pacific* (Version Report). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3237373>
- IPBES (with Rounsevell, M., Fischer, M., Rando, A. T. M., & Mader, A.). (2018d). *The IPBES regional assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services for Europe and Central Asia* (Version Report). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3237428>
- IPBES (with Rice, J., Seixas, C. S., Zaccagnini, M. E., Bedoya-Gaitán, M., & Valderrama, N.). (2018e). *The IPBES regional assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services for the Americas*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3236252>
- IPBES. (2019a). *Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services* (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3831673>
- IPBES (with Díaz, S., Settele, J., Brondízio, E. S., Ngo, H. T., Guèze, M., Agard, J., Arneth, A., Balvanera, P., Brauman, K. A., S. H. M. Butchart, Chan, K. M. A., L. A. Garibaldi, K. Ichii

- J. Liu, S. M. Subramanian, Midgley, G. F., Miloslavich, P., Molnár, Z., Obura, D., Pfaff, A., ... Zayas, C. N.). (2019b). *Summary for policymakers of the global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services* (Version summary for policy makers). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3553579>
- IPBES (with Balvanera, P., Pascual, U., Christie, M., & González-Jiménez, D.). (2022a). *Methodological assessment of the diverse values and valuation of nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6522522>
- IPBES. (2022b). *Methodological assessment of the diverse values and valuation of nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6522522>
- IPBES. (2022c). *Summary for Policymakers of the Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7410287>
- IPBES (with Fromentin, J.-M., Emery, M. R., Donaldson, J., Danner, M.-C., Halosserie, A., Kieling, D., Balachander, G., Barron, E. S., Chaudhary, R. P., Gasalla, M., Halmy, M., Hicks, C., Parlee, B., Park, M. S., Rice, J., Ticktin, T., & Tittensor, D.). (2022d). *Summary for policymakers of the thematic assessment of the sustainable use of wild species of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES)* (Version 1). Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6425599>
- IPBES. (2023a). *Edith Bastidas, Johnson Cerda, Q'apaq Conde, Binota Moy Dhamai, Guadalupe Yesenia Hernández Márquez, Cecil Le Fleur, Gathuru Mburu, Sherry Pictou, Novia Sagita, Lucía Xiloj and Durgha Yamphu. Report of the first indigenous and local knowledge dialogue workshop on the IPBES assessment on business and biodiversity: Framing the assessments. 23-24 September 2023.*
- IPBES. (2023b). *Scoping report for a methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.* <https://www.ipbes.net/document-library-catalogue/scoping-report-methodological-assessment-impact-and-dependence-business>
- IPBES. (2024a). *IPBES Invasive Alien Species Assessment: Full report* (Version 4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7430682>
- IPBES. (2024b). *IPBES Transformative Change Assessment: Full report* (Version 4.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11382215>
- IPBES (with O'Brien, K., Garibaldi, L., Agrawal, A., Bennett, E., Biggs, O., Calderón Contreras, R., Carr, E. R., Frantzeskaki, N., Gosnell, H., Gurung, J., Lambertucci, S. A., Leventon, J., Chuan, L., Reyes García, V., Shannon, L., Villasante, S., Wickson, F., Zinngrebe, Y., Périanin, L., ... Zaccagnini, M. E.). (2024c). *IPBES Transformative Change Assessment: Summary for Policymakers* (Version v10.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11382230>
- IPBES (with McElwee, P. D., Harrison, P. A., van Huysen, T. L., Alonso Roldán, V., Barrios, E., Dasgupta, P., DeClerck, F., Harmáčková, Z., Hayman, D. T. S., Herrero, M., Kumar, R., Ley, D., Mangalagiu, D., McFarlane, R. A., Paukert, C., Pengue, W. A., Prist, P. R., Ricketts, T. H., Rounsevell, M. D. A., ... Obura, D.). (2024d). *Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13850290>

- IPBES. (2024e). *Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. IPBES Secretariat. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850054>
- IPBES, Cerda, J., Satao, G., Jackson, C. A., le Fleur, Y., Kabinda, Z., Kraalshoek, F., Laltaika, E., Loupa, P., Makai, J., Petersen, S., Phattahanaphraiwan, S., Karmushu, R. S., & Useb, J. (2024). *Report of the second Indigenous and local knowledge dialogue workshop on the IPBES assessment on business and biodiversity: Reviewing the first drafts of the assessment*. (p. 67). https://files.ipbes.net/ipbes-web-prod-public-files/2024-12/IPBES_Business_2ndILKDialogue_Report_Final_ForWeb.pdf
- IPBES, Edith Bastidas, Edith Bastidas, Binota Moy Dhamai, Guadalupe Yesenia Guadalupe Yesenia, Cecil Le Fleur, Novia Sagita, Lucía Xiloj, & Durga Yamphu. (2023). *Report of the first Indigenous and local knowledge dialogue workshop on the IPBES assessment on business and biodiversity: Framing the assessment*. https://files.ipbes.net/ipbes-web-prod-public-files/2024-01/IPBES_Business_1stILKDialogue_Report_FinalForWeb.pdf
- IPCC. (2023). *Chapter 1: Point of Departure and Key Concepts. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Sixth Assessment Report: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability*. <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/chapter/chapter-1/>
- Irvine-Broque, A., & Dempsey, J. (2023). Risky business: Protecting nature, protecting wealth? *Conservation Letters*, 16(4), e12969. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12969>
- IUCN. (2015). *Rwanda's Green Well: Opportunities to engage private sector investors in Rwanda's forest landscape restoration* (p. 100). <https://portals.iucn.org/library/sites/library/files/documents/2015-017.pdf>
- IUCN. (2023, August 12). *Measuring Nature-Positive – Setting and implementing verified, robust targets for species and ecosystems*. <https://iucn.org/our-work/biodiversity/nature-positive>
- Izquierdo-Tort, S., Alatorre, A., Shapiro-Garza, E., Corbera, E., Deschamps-Lomelí, J., Ávila-Foucat, V. S., Carabias, J., Dupras, J., Kolinjivadi, V., Nuñez, J. M., Perevochtchikova, M., Sims, K., & Van Hecken, G. (2025). Payments for ecosystem services in Mexico: Two decades of progress and challenges between research and practice. *Ecosystem Services*, 73, 101720. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2025.101720>
- Jones, J. P. G., Bull, J. W., Roe, D., Baker, J., Griffiths, V. F., Starkey, M., Sonter, L. J., & Milner-Gulland, E. J. (2019). Net Gain: Seeking Better Outcomes for Local People when Mitigating Biodiversity Loss from Development. *One Earth*, 1(2), 195–201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2019.09.007>
- Kaplinsky, R., & Morris, M. (2000). *A HANDBOOK FOR VALUE CHAIN RESEARCH*.
- Kariyapperuma, N., & Collins, E. (2021). Family logics and environmental sustainability: A study of the New Zealand wine industry. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(8), 3626–3650. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2823>
- Karolyi, G. A., & Tobin-de la Puente, J. (2023). Biodiversity finance: A call for research into financing nature. *Financial Management*, 52(2), 231–251. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fima.12417>
- Kass, J. M., Fukaya, K., Thuiller, W., & Mori, A. S. (2024). Biodiversity modeling advances will improve predictions of nature's contributions to people. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 39(4), 338–348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2023.10.011>
- Katic, P. G., Cerretelli, S., Haggard, J., Santika, T., & Walsh, C. (2023). Mainstreaming biodiversity in business decisions: Taking stock of tools and gaps. *Biological Conservation*, 277, 109831. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109831>

- Kedward, K., Zu Ermgassen, S., Ryan-Collins, J., & Wunder, S. (2023). Heavy reliance on private finance alone will not deliver conservation goals. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 7(9), 1339–1342. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02098-6>
- Kedward, K., zu Ermgassen, S., Ryan-Collins, J., & Wunder, S. (2023). Heavy reliance on private finance alone will not deliver conservation goals. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 7(9), Article 9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02098-6>
- Kering. (2023). *Biodiversity strategy. Bending the curve on biodiversity loss*. https://www.kering.com/api/download-file/?path=Kering_Sustainability_Strategie_Biodiversite_2023_a57da2f106_V2_1a8d1320ed.pdf
- Khalvati, M., Michine (Yvonne Fulton), I., Mukwa (Zane Bell), W., & Metatawabin, M. J. (2011). Traditional ecological knowledge: Impact on commercial health. *Journal of Commercial Biotechnology*, 17(2), 131–133. <https://doi.org/10.1057/jcb.2010.35>
- Kramer, M., Kind-Rieper, T., Munayer, R., Giljum, S., Masselink, R., van Ackern, P., Maus, V., Luckeneder, S., Kuschnig, N., Costa, F., & Rüttinger, L. (2023). *Extracted Forests. Unearthing the role of mining-related deforestation as a driver of global deforestation*. <https://www.wwf.de/fileadmin/fm-wwf/Publikationen-PDF/Wald/WWF-Studie-Extracted-Forests.pdf>
- Lammerant, J. (2021). *ASSESSMENT OF BIODIVERSITY MEASUREMENT APPROACHES FOR BUSINESSES AND FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS* (No. 3). European Business and Biodiversity Platform. https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/EU%20B%40B%20Platform%20Uupdate%20Report%203_FINAL_1March2021.pdf
- Latapí, M. A., Jóhannsdóttir, L., & Davídsdóttir, B. (2019). A literature review of the history and evolution of corporate social responsibility. *International Journal of Corporate Social Responsibility*, 4(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40991-018-0039-y>
- Lawson, C. (1994). THE THEORY OF STATE-OWNED ENTERPRISES IN MARKET ECONOMIES. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 8(3), 283–309. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6419.1994.tb00104.x>
- Leonova, N., & Rentschler, J. (2022). *Air Pollution and Poverty: PM2.5 Exposure in 211 Countries and Territories* (Policy Research Working Paper No. 10005; p. 28). World Bank. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/37322>
- Locke, H., Rockström, J., Bakker, P., Bapna, M., Gough, M., Lambertini, M., Morris, J., Polman, P., Samper, C., Sanjayan, M., Zabey, E., & Zurita, P. (2021). *A Nature-Positive World: The Global Goal for Nature*. 21.
- LOI n° 2019-1147 du 8 novembre 2019 relative à l'énergie et au climat (1), Pub. L. No. LOI n° 2019-1147, Article 29 (2019). https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/jorf/article_jo/JORFARTI000039355992
- Lyver, P. O., Richardson, S. J., Gormley, A. M., Timoti, P., Jones, C. J., & Tahi, B. L. (2018). Complementarity of indigenous and western scientific approaches for monitoring forest state. *Ecological Applications*, 28(7), 1909–1923. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1787>
- Managi, S., & Kumar, P. (2018). *Inclusive Wealth Report 2018: Measuring Progress Towards Sustainability* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351002080>
- Mandai, S. S., & Souza, M. M. P. de. (2021). Guidelines for the analysis of the inclusion of biodiversity in Environmental Impact Statements. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 87, 106523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2020.106523>
- Mariani, G., Moullec, F., Atwood, T. B., Clarkson, B., Conant, R. T., Cullen-Unsworth, L., Griscom, B., Gutt, J., Howard, J., Krause-Jensen, D., Leavitt, S. M., Lee, S. Y., Livesley, S. J.,

- Macreadie, P. I., St-John, M., Zganjar, C., Cheung, W. W., Duarte, C. M., Shin, Y., ... Mouillot, D. (2024). Co-benefits of and trade-offs between natural climate solutions and Sustainable Development Goals. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 22(10), e2807. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.2807>
- Maron, M., Quétier, F., Sarmiento, M., ten Kate, K., Evans, M. C., Bull, J. W., Jones, J. P. G., zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Milner-Gulland, E. J., Brownlie, S., Treweek, J., & von Hase, A. (2023). 'Nature positive' must incorporate, not undermine, the mitigation hierarchy. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02199-2>
- Marques, A., Martins, I. S., Kastner, T., Plutzer, C., Theurl, M. C., Eisenmenger, N., Huijbregts, M. A. J., Wood, R., Stadler, K., Bruckner, M., Canelas, J., Hilbers, J. P., Tukker, A., Erb, K., & Pereira, H. M. (2019). Increasing impacts of land use on biodiversity and carbon sequestration driven by population and economic growth. *Nature Ecology and Evolution*, 3(4), 628–637. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-019-0824-3>
- Marsden, L., Ryan-Collins, J., & F Abrams, J. (2024). *Ecosystem tipping points: Understanding risks to the economy and financial system*. UCL Institute for Innovation and Public Purpose. https://www.ucl.ac.uk/bartlett/public-purpose/sites/bartlett_public Purpose/files/ecosystem_tipping_points_policy_report_iipp.pdf
- Martin-Ortega, O., Dehbi, F., Nelson, V., & Pillay, R. (2022). Towards a Business, Human Rights and the Environment Framework. *Sustainability*, 14(11), 6596. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14116596>
- Maus, V., Giljum, S., da Silva, D. M., Gutschlhofer, J., da Rosa, R. P., Luckeneder, S., Gass, S. L. B., Lieber, M., & McCallum, I. (2022). An update on global mining land use. *Scientific Data*, 9(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01547-4>
- McKenzie, E. J., Jones, M., Seega, N., Siikamäki, J., & Vijay, V. (2025). Science and technical priorities for private sector action to address biodiversity loss. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 380(1917), 20230208. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2023.0208>
- McKinsey & Company. (2022, September 13). *Where the world's largest companies stand on nature*. McKinsey Sustainability. <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/sustainability/our-insights/where-the-worlds-largest-companies-stand-on-nature#/>
- McKinsey & Company. (2023). *Companies are broadening their commitments to nature beyond carbon*. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/agriculture/how-we-help-clients/natural-capital-and-nature/our-insights/companies-are-broadening-their-commitments-to-nature-beyond-carbon#/>
- Mengist, W., Soromessa, T., & Feyisa, G. L. (2020). A global view of regulatory ecosystem services: Existed knowledge, trends, and research gaps. *Ecological Processes*, 9(1), 40. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13717-020-00241-w>
- Millennium Ecosystem Assessment. (2003). *Ecosystems and human well-being: A framework for assessment* (J. Alcamo & E. M. Bennett, Eds.). Island Press.
- Milner-Gulland, E. J. (2022). Don't dilute the term Nature Positive. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 6(9), 1243–1244. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-022-01845-5>
- Mohr, J., & Thissen, C. (2022). Measuring and Disclosing Corporate Valuations of Impacts and Dependencies on Nature. *California Management Review*, 65(1), 91–118. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00081256221131653>
- Möller, T., Högner, A. E., Schleussner, C.-F., Bien, S., Kitzmann, N. H., Lamboll, R. D., Rogelj, J., Donges, J. F., Rockström, J., & Wunderling, N. (2024). Achieving net zero greenhouse gas

- emissions critical to limit climate tipping risks. *Nature Communications*, 15(1), 6192.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-49863-0>
- Moretti, M., Belliggiano, A., Grando, S., Felici, F., Scotti, I., Ievoli, C., Blackstock, K., Delgado-Serrano, M. M., & Brunori, G. (2023). Characterizing value chains' contribution to resilient and sustainable development in European mountain areas. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 100, 103022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.103022>
- Morgan, R. K. (2012). Environmental impact assessment: The state of the art. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 30(1), 5–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2012.661557>
- Natura & Co. (2023). *Integrated Report*.
https://2023ar.naturaeco.report/documents/85/Natura_Co_Integrated_Report_2023_17.4.pdf
- Natural Capital Coalition. (2016). *Natural Capital Protocol* (p. 136).
www.naturalcapitalcoalition.org/protocol
- Natural Capital Coalition. (2019). *Data use in natural capital assessments. Assessing challenges and identifying solutions. Full report*. <https://capitalscoalition.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/Full-Report.pdf>
- Nature Positive Initiative. (n.d.). *About the Initiative*. Retrieved
<https://www.naturepositive.org/about/the-initiative/>
- NCFA, & WCMC. (2018). *Exploring Natural Capital Opportunities, Risks and Exposure: A practical guide for financial institutions*. Natural Capital Finance Alliance and UN Environment World Conservation Monitoring Centre: 27.
<https://wedocs.unep.org/20.500.11822/38389>
- NGFS. (2023a). *Nature-related Financial Risks: A Conceptual Framework to guide Action by Central Banks and Supervisors*. Network for Greening the Financial System (NGFS).
https://www.ngfs.net/sites/default/files/medias/documents/ngfs_conceptual-framework-on-nature-related-risks.pdf
- NGFS. (2023b). *Recommendations toward the development of scenarios for assessing nature-related economic and financial risks*. Network for Greening the Financial System (NGFS).
https://www.ngfs.net/sites/default/files/medias/documents/ngfs_nature_scenarios_recommendations.pdf
- NGFS. (2024a). *Nature-related Financial Risks: A Conceptual Framework to guide Action by Central Banks and Supervisors* (p. 49) [Technical document]. Network for Greening the Financial System (NGFS). <https://www.ngfs.net/en/publications-and-statistics/publications/nature-related-litigation-emerging-trends-and-lessons-learned-climate-related-litigations://www.ngfs.net/en/publications-and-statistics/publications/nature-related-financial-risks-conceptual-framework-guide-action-central-banks-and-supervisors>
- NGFS. (2024b). *Nature-related litigation: Emerging trends and lessons learned from climate-related litigation*. Network for Greening the Financial System (NGFS).
<https://www.ngfs.net/sites/default/files/medias/documents/report-nature-related-litigation-emerging-trends-lessons-climate.pdf>
- NGFS & INSPIRE. (2021). *Biodiversity and financial stability: Exploring the case for action. NGFS Occasional Paper*. (p. 17). Network for Greening the Financial System (NGFS)-The International Network for Sustainable Financial Policy Insights, Research, and Exchange (INSPIRE).
https://www.ngfs.net/sites/default/files/medias/documents/biodiversity_and_financial_stability_exploring_the_case_for_action.pdf
- Nicholls, S., & Crompton, J. (2018). A Comprehensive Review of the Evidence of the Impact of Surface Water Quality on Property Values. *Sustainability*, 10(2), 500.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su10020500>

- Nikuradze, E., & Tvalodze, S. (2023). *Biodiversity-related Financial Risks – Why it Matters and How Can We Measure Them? Case Study of Georgia* (Working Paper Series WP 02/2023; p. 50). National Bank of Georgia. <https://www.nbg.gov.ge>
- Nordhaus, W. D., Kokkelenberg, E. C., & National Research Council (U.S.) (Eds.). (1999). *Nature's numbers: Expanding the national economic accounts to include the environment*. National Academy Press.
- Norfund. (2021). *Environmental and Social Risk Management*. <https://www.norfund.no/annualreport-2021/responsible-investor/e-and-s/>
- Norouzzadeh, M. S., Nguyen, A., Kosmala, M., Swanson, A., Palmer, M. S., Packer, C., & Clune, J. (2018). Automatically identifying, counting, and describing wild animals in camera-trap images with deep learning. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *115*(25). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1719367115>
- Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment. (2024). *Official Norwegian Reports NOU 2024: 2. In interaction with nature – Nature risk for industries, sectors and society at large in Norway*. <https://www.regjeringen.no/contentassets/a653320aa3f949038bb0e7ad92de1234/en-gb/pdfs/nou202420240002000engpdfs.pdf>
- OECD. (2023). *A supervisory framework for assessing nature-related financial risks: Identifying and navigating biodiversity risks* (OECD Business and Finance Policy Papers No. 33). <https://doi.org/10.1787/a8e4991f-en>
- Ostrom, E. (2010). Beyond Markets and States: Polycentric Governance of Complex Economic Systems. *American Economic Review*, *100*(3), 641–672. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.100.3.641>
- Ostrom, E. (2015). *Governing the Commons: The Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action* (1st ed.). Cambridge University Press. <https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/9781316423936/type/book>
- Ouyang, Z., Song, C., Zheng, H., Polasky, S., Xiao, Y., Bateman, I. J., Liu, J., Ruckelshaus, M., Shi, F., Xiao, Y., Xu, W., Zou, Z., & Daily, G. C. (2020). Using gross ecosystem product (GEP) to value nature in decision making. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *117*(25), 14593–14601. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1911439117>
- Panigrahi, S., Maski, P., & Thoniyath, A. (2023). Real-time biodiversity analysis using deep-learning algorithms on mobile robotic platforms. *PeerJ Computer Science*, *9*, e1502. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1502>
- Panwar, R., Ober, H., & Pinkse, J. (2023). The uncomfortable relationship between business and biodiversity: Advancing research on business strategies for biodiversity protection. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, *32*(5), 2554–2566. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3139>
- Pascual, U., Balvanera, P., Anderson, C. B., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Christie, M., González-Jiménez, D., Martin, A., Raymond, C. M., Termansen, M., Vatn, A., Athayde, S., Baptiste, B., Barton, D. N., Jacobs, S., Kelemen, E., Kumar, R., Lazos, E., Mwampamba, T. H., Nakangu, B., ... Zent, E. (2023). Diverse values of nature for sustainability. *Nature*, *620*(7975), 813–823. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06406-9>
- Pascual, U., Balvanera, P., Díaz, S., Pataki, G., Roth, E., Stenseke, M., Watson, R. T., Başak Dessane, E., Islar, M., Kelemen, E., Maris, V., Quaas, M., Subramanian, S. M., Wittmer, H., Adlan, A., Ahn, S., Al-Hafedh, Y. S., Amankwah, E., Asah, S. T., ... Yagi, N. (2017). Valuing nature's contributions to people: The IPBES approach. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, *26–27*, 7–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2016.12.006>
- PBAF Global. (n.d.). *Partnership for Biodiversity Accounting Financials (PBAF)*. Retrieved <https://pbafglobal.com/>

- Phalan, B., Hayes, G., Brooks, S., Marsh, D., Howard, P., Costelloe, B., Vira, B., Kowalska, A., & Whitaker, S. (2018). Avoiding impacts on biodiversity through strengthening the first stage of the mitigation hierarchy. *Oryx*, 52(2), 316–324.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605316001034>
- Pictou, S., Conway, J., & Day, A. (2021). *Wolastoqiyik and Mi'kmaq Grandmothers—Land/Water Defenders Sharing and Learning Circle: Generating Knowledge for Action*.
https://www.kairoscanada.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Grandmothers_Land_Defense_Report_Pictou_2021.pdf
- Pollination. (2024). *Nature-Positive Strategy: Practical Guidance for Corporates* (p. 49). Pollination Group. <https://pollinationgroup.com>
- Pörtner, H.-O., Scholes, R. J., Agard, J., Archer, E., Bai, X., Barnes, D., Burrows, M., Chan, L., Cheung, W. L. (William), Diamond, S., Donatti, C., Duarte, C., Eisenhauer, N., Foden, W., Gasalla, M. A., Handa, C., Hickler, T., Hoegh-Guldberg, O., Ichii, K., ... Ngo, H. (2021). *IPBES-IPCC co-sponsored workshop report on biodiversity and climate change*. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5101133>
- Pörtner, H.-O., Scholes, R. J., Arneeth, A., Barnes, D. K. A., Burrows, M. T., Diamond, S. E., Duarte, C. M., Kiessling, W., Leadley, P., Managi, S., McElwee, P., Midgley, G., Ngo, H. T., Obura, D., Pascual, U., Sankaran, M., Shin, Y. J., & Val, A. L. (2023). Overcoming the coupled climate and biodiversity crises and their societal impacts. *Science*, 380(6642), eabl4881.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abl4881>
- PRI. (2024a). *Investor initiatives*. <https://www.unpri.org/investing-for-nature-resource-hub/investor-initiatives/12003.article>
- PRI. (2024b). *Nature Policy Roadmap: Policy Recommendations for Scaling Up Investor Action for Nature* (p. 30) [DISCUSSION PAPER]. Principles for Responsible Investment Association.
<https://www.unpri.org/>
- PRI, UNEP FfE, & Finance for Biodiversity Foundation. (2022, December 19). 'Moving Together on Nature': Statement from the Private Financial Sector to the Convention on Biological Diversity COP15. <https://www.financeforbiodiversity.org/about-the-pledge/>
- Putniņš, T. J. (2015). Economics of state-owned enterprises. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 38(11), 40.
- PwC. (2023, April 19). *Managing nature risks: From understanding to action*.
<https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/strategy-and-business/content/sbpwc-2023-04-19-Managing-nature-risks-v2.pdf>
- Ranger, N., Alvarez J., Freeman, A., Harwood, T., Obersteiner, M., Paulus, E., & Sabuco, J. (2023). *The Green Scorpion: The Macro-Criticality of Nature for Finance – Foundations for scenario-based analysis of complex and cascading physical nature-related risks*. Oxford: Environmental Change Institute, University of Oxford.
https://www.eci.ox.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2023-12/INCAF-MacroCriticality_of_Nature-December2023.pdf
- Reguero, B. G., Beck, M. W., Schmid, D., Stadtmüller, D., Raeppele, J., Schüssele, S., & Pflieger, K. (2020). Financing coastal resilience by combining nature-based risk reduction with insurance. *Ecological Economics*, 169, 106487.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.106487>
- Rillig, M. C., Ågerstrand, M., Bi, M., Gould, K. A., & Sauerland, U. (2023). Risks and Benefits of Large Language Models for the Environment. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 57(9), 3464–3466. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.3c01106>

- Rooibos Council. (2022). *Khoi and San receive first cycle of benefit-sharing funds from Rooibos industry*. General News, News and Research. <https://sarooibos.co.za/khoi-and-san-receive-first-cycle-of-benefit-sharing-funds-from-rooibos-industry/>
- Sánchez, A. C., Kamau, H. N., Grazioli, F., & Jones, S. K. (2022). Financial profitability of diversified farming systems: A global meta-analysis. *Ecological Economics*, *201*, 107595. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107595>
- Sangha, K. K., Evans, J., Edwards, A., Russell-Smith, J., Fisher, R., Yates, C., & Costanza, R. (2021). Assessing the value of ecosystem services delivered by prescribed fire management in Australian tropical savannas. *Ecosystem Services*, *51*, 101343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2021.101343>
- SBTN. (2024a). *Stakeholder engagement and science-based targets for nature* (p. 51). <https://sciencebasedtargetsnetwork.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/Stakeholder-engagement-guidance-v1-0.pdf>
- SBTN. (2024b, October 1). *Guiding companies for a nature positive future: SBTN's interplay with global initiatives*. Science Based Targets Network. <https://sciencebasedtargetsnetwork.org/news/blog/mobilizing-companies-for-a-nature-positive-future/>
- Scheidel, A., Fernández-Llamazares, Á., Bara, A. H., Del Bene, D., David-Chavez, D. M., Fanari, E., Garba, I., Hanaček, K., Liu, J., Martínez-Alier, J., Navas, G., Reyes-García, V., Roy, B., Temper, L., Thiri, M. A., Tran, D., Walter, M., & Whyte, K. P. (2023a). Global impacts of extractive and industrial development projects on Indigenous Peoples' lifeways, lands, and rights. *Science Advances*, *9*(23), eade9557. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.ade9557>
- Scheidel, A., Fernández-Llamazares, Á., Bara, A. H., Del Bene, D., David-Chavez, D. M., Fanari, E., Garba, I., Hanaček, K., Liu, J., Martínez-Alier, J., Navas, G., Reyes-García, V., Roy, B., Temper, L., Thiri, M. A., Tran, D., Walter, M., & Whyte, K. P. (2023b). Global impacts of extractive and industrial development projects on Indigenous Peoples' lifeways, lands, and rights. *Science Advances*, *9*(23), eade9557. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.ade9557>
- Schelske, O., Bohn, J. R., & Fitzgerald, C. (2021). Insuring Natural Ecosystems as an Innovative Conservation Funding Mechanism: A Case Study on Coral Reefs. In S. Eslamian & F. Eslamian (Eds.), *Handbook of Disaster Risk Reduction for Resilience* (pp. 435–452). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61278-8_19
- Scherzinger, F., Schädler, M., Reitz, T., Yin, R., Auge, H., Merbach, I., Roscher, C., Harpole, W. S., Blagodatskaya, E., Siebert, J., Ciobanu, M., Marder, F., Eisenhauer, N., & Quaas, M. (2024). Sustainable land management enhances ecological and economic multifunctionality under ambient and future climate. *Nature Communications*, *15*(1), 4930. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-48830-z>
- Scheyvens, R., Banks, G., Vunibola, S., Steven, H., & Meo-Sewabu, L. (2020). Business serves society: Successful locally-driven development on customary land in the South Pacific. *Geoforum*, *112*, 52–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2020.03.012>
- Schilling-Vacaflor, A. (2021). Integrating Human Rights and the Environment in Supply Chain Regulations. *Sustainability*, *13*(17), 9666. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13179666>
- Science Based Targets Network. (2024). *Corporate Manual for Setting Science-Based Targets for Nature*. <https://sciencebasedtargetsnetwork.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/Corporate-manual-for-setting-SBT-for-Nature.pdf>
- Science Based Targets Network (SBTN). (n.d.). *Target Tracker*. Target Tracker. Retrieved <https://sciencebasedtargetsnetwork.org/company/target-tracker/>
- Seddon, N. (2022). Harnessing the potential of nature-based solutions for mitigating and adapting to climate change. *Science*, *376*(6600), 1410–1416. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abn9668>

- ShareAction. (2023). *ShareAction's 2023 Point of No Returns reports. Executive Summary*.
<https://shareaction.org/reports/point-of-no-returns-2023-part-i-ranking-and-general-findings/executive-summary>
- Shiva, V. (2016). *Biopiracy: The plunder of nature and knowledge*. North Atlantic Books.
- Simeoni, C., Furlan, E., Pham, H. V., Critto, A., de Juan, S., Trégarot, E., Cornet, C. C., Meesters, E., Fonseca, C., Botelho, A. Z., Krause, T., N'Guetta, A., Cordova, F. E., Failler, P., & Marcomini, A. (2023). Evaluating the combined effect of climate and anthropogenic stressors on marine coastal ecosystems: Insights from a systematic review of cumulative impact assessment approaches. *Science of The Total Environment*, 861, 160687.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.160687>
- Slawinski, N., Winsor, B., Mazutis, D., Schouten, J. W., & Smith, W. K. (2021). Managing the Paradoxes of Place to Foster Regeneration. *Organization & Environment*, 34(4), 595–618.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1086026619837131>
- Sonter, L. J., Ali, S. H., & Watson, J. E. M. (2018). Mining and biodiversity: Key issues and research needs in conservation science. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 285(1892), 20181926. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2018.1926>
- Sonter, L. J., Herrera, D., Barrett, D. J., Galford, G. L., Moran, C. J., & Soares-Filho, B. S. (2017). Mining drives extensive deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon. *Nature Communications*, 8(1), 1013. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-00557-w>
- Stiglitz, J. E. (1977). The Theory of Local Public Goods. In M. S. Feldstein & R. P. Inman (Eds.), *The Economics of Public Services* (pp. 274–333). Palgrave Macmillan UK.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-02917-4_12
- Stiglitz, J. E. (1998). *Towards a new paradigm for development: Strategies, policies, and processes*.
https://www.iatp.org/sites/default/files/Towards_a_New_Paradigm_for_Development_Strateg.htm
- SustainAbility, UNEP & UNGC. (2008). *Unchaining Value*.
https://d306pr3pise04h.cloudfront.net/docs/news_events%2F8.1%2Funchaining_value.pdf
- Swiss Re Institute. (2020). *Biodiversity and ecosystem services: A business case for re/insurance* (p. 60). Swiss Reinsurance Company Ltd. <https://www.swissre.com/dam/jcr:a7fe3dca-c4d6-403b-961c-9fab1b2f0455/swiss-re-institute-expertise-publication-biodiversity-and-ecosystem-services.pdf>
- Tabak, M. A., Norouzzadeh, M. S., Wolfson, D. W., Sweeney, S. J., Vercauteren, K. C., Snow, N. P., Halseth, J. M., Di Salvo, P. A., Lewis, J. S., White, M. D., Teton, B., Beasley, J. C., Schlichting, P. E., Boughton, R. K., Wight, B., Newkirk, E. S., Ivan, J. S., Odell, E. A., Brook, R. K., ... Miller, R. S. (2019). Machine learning to classify animal species in camera trap images: Applications in ecology. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 10(4), 585–590.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13120>
- Tan, M., Chao, W., Cheng, J.-K., Zhou, M., Ma, Y., Jiang, X., Ge, J., Yu, L., & Feng, L. (2022). Animal Detection and Classification from Camera Trap Images Using Different Mainstream Object Detection Architectures. *Animals*, 12(15), 1976. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani12151976>
- Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD). (2020). *Guidance on Scenario Analysis for Non-Financial Companies*. Financial Stability Board. <https://www.fsb-tcfd.org/publications/>
- TCFD. (2017). *Recommendations of the Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures* (Final report; p. 74). Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures.
<https://assets.bbhub.io/company/sites/60/2021/10/FINAL-2017-TCFD-Report.pdf>
- TCGF. (2022). *Collective Action and Investment in Landscape Initiatives: The Business Case for Forest Positive Transformation*. The Consumer Goods Forum (CGF) Forest Positive

- Coalition of Action. <https://www.theconsumergoodsforum.com/environmental-sustainability/forest-positive/key-projects/coalition-wide-actions/>
- TEEB. (2012a). *The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity in Business and Enterprise*. Earthscan. <http://www.teebweb.org/media/2012/01/TEEB-For-Business.pdf>
- TEEB. (2012b). *The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity in Business and Enterprise* (Bishop J. (ed.)). Earthscan. <https://teebweb.org/publications/teeb-for/business-and-enterprise/>
- The Climate Champions Team, Capital for Climate, Innovative Finance for the Amazon, Cerrado and Chaco (IFACC), & Brunswick Group. (2024). *Scaling Nature Finance Now: The Opportunity for Investors in Brazil and Beyond* (p. 21). https://www.climatechampions.net/media/5fpf2fgc/scaling-nature-finance-now_-the-opportunity-for-investors-in-brazil-and-beyond_final.pdf
- The Nature Conservancy. (2024). *Nature Bonds Toolkit* (p. 68). <https://www.nature.org/en-us/what-we-do/our-priorities/protect-water-and-land/land-and-water-stories/nature-bonds/toolkit/>
- Thomson, E. (2025). *Companies profit, forests fall: Everyone pays the price* (p. 31). Global Canopy. https://forest500.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/Forest500_Report_2025_.pdf
- Thomson, E., & Fairbairn, A. (2023). *2023: A watershed year for action on deforestation* [Annual Report 2023]. Global Canopy. https://forest500.org/sites/default/files/forest_500-2023_annual_report.pdf
- TNFD. (2022). *Additional Draft Guidance for Corporates on Science-Based Targets for Nature: LEAP (P2)* (Version Beta v0.3). TNFD. <https://framework.tnfd.global/the-leap-nature-risk-assessment-process/prepare/target-setting/>
- TNFD. (2023a). *Discussion Paper on Conducting advanced scenario analysis*. Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD). https://tnfd.global/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/TNFD_Discussion_paper_on_conducting_advanced_scenario_analysis_2023.pdf?v=1701692155
- TNFD. (2023b). *Guidance on engagement with Indigenous Peoples, Local Communities and affected stakeholders* (p. 56). https://tnfd.global/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Guidance_on_engagement_with_Indigenous_Peoples_Local_Communities_and_affected_stakeholders_v1.pdf?v=1695138220
- TNFD. (2023c). *Guidance on the identification and assessment of nature related issues: The LEAP approach* (p. 282). Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD). https://tnfd.global/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Guidance_on_the_identification_and_assessment_of_nature-related-issues_The_TNFD_LEAP_approach_v1.pdf?v=1695138163
- TNFD. (2023d). *Recommendations of the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures*. (p. 154). Taskforce on Nature-Related Financial Disclosures. <https://tnfd.global/publication/recommendations-of-the-taskforce-on-nature-related-financial-disclosures/>
- TNFD. (2024a). *A Roadmap for Upgrading Market Access to Decision-Useful Nature-Related Data* (p. 58). Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures. <https://tnfd.global/publication/a-roadmap-for-upgrading-market-access-to-decision-useful-nature-related-data/>
- TNFD. (2024b). *Sector guidance Additional guidance for financial institutions*. https://tnfd.global/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/TNFD-Additional-guidance-for-financial-Institutions_v2.0.pdf?v=1720185908
- TNFD. (2024c). *TNFD adoption now over 400 organisations and new sector guidance released*. <https://tnfd.global/tnfd-adoption-now-over-400-organisations-and-new-sector-guidance-released/>

- TNFD. (2025a). *Additional Guidance by sector*. Publications. https://tnfd.global/tnfd-publications/?_sft_framework-categories=additional-guidance-by-sector#search-filter
- TNFD. (2025b). *Asking Better Questions on Nature, For Board Directors*. Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures. <https://tnfd.global/tnfd-publications/>
- TNFD. (2025c). *Assessment Tools Catalogue*. Tools Catalogue Nature-Related Data Tools to Help Assess Nature-Related Issues and Aligned with the TNFD's LEAP Approach. <https://tnfd.global/assessment-guidance/tools-catalogue/>
- TNFD. (2025d). *Evidence Review on the Financial Effects of Nature-Related Risks* (p. 80). University of Oxford Environmental Change Institute, Resilient Planet Finance Lab, Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD), Global Canopy. <https://tnfd.global/publication/guidance-on-scenario-analysis/#publication-content>
- TNFD. (2025e). *TNFD 2025 status report*. Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures. <https://tnfd.global/publication/tnfd-2025-status-report/>
- TNFD. (2025f, January 23). *TNFD issues new sector guidance* [Press release]. <https://tnfd.global/new-set-of-sector-guidance-published/>
- TNFD, & EFRAG. (2024). *Correspondence Mapping: ESRS and TNFD* (p. 95). TNFD. <https://tnfd.global/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Correspondence-mapping-ESRS-and-TNFD.pdf>
- TPT. (2024). *The Future for Nature in Transition Planning* (p. 24). Transition Plan Taskforce (TPT). <https://itpn.global/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/The-Future-for-Nature-1.pdf>
- Trucost. (2013). *Natural capital at risk: The top 100 externalities of business* (p. 43). <https://capitalscoalition.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/Trucost-Nat-Cap-at-Risk-Final-Report-web.pdf>
- UN. (1992). *Rio declaration on environment and development*. United Nations.
- UN (Ed.). (2008). *International Standard industrial classification of all economic activities (ISIC)* (Rev. 4). United Nations.
- UN. (2021). *Glasgow Leaders' Declaration on Forests and Land Use—UN Climate Change Conference (COP26) at the SEC – Glasgow 2021*. <https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/ukgwa/20230418175226/https://ukcop26.org/glasgow-leaders-declaration-on-forests-and-land-use/>
- UNDP. (2018). *The BIOFIN Workbook 2018: Finance for Nature* (p. 204). Biodiversity Finance Initiative (BIOFIN), United Nations Development Programme. <https://www.biofin.org/>
- UNDRR. (2019, November 26). *Understanding Risk. United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction*. <http://www.undrr.org/building-risk-knowledge/understanding-risk>
- UNEP (Ed.). (2010). *Mainstreaming the economics of nature: A synthesis of the approach, conclusions and recommendations of teeb*. UNEP.
- UNEP. (2021). *Making peace with nature: A scientific blueprint to tackle the climate, biodiversity and pollution emergencies* (p. 168). United Nations Environment Programme. <https://www.unep.org/resources/making-peace-nature>
- UNEP. (2022). *Prioritising Nature-related Disclosures. Considerations for high-risk sectors* (p. 45). UN Environment Programme. <https://www.unepfi.org/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Prioritising-nature-related-disclosures.pdf>
- UNEP. (2023a). *Driving Finance for Sustainable Food Systems: A Roadmap to Implementation for Financial Institutions and Policy Makers* (p. 78). UNEP. <https://www.unep.org/resources/report/driving-finance-sustainable-food-systems>

- UNEP. (2023b). *State of Finance for Nature 2023: The Big Nature Turnaround - Repurposing \$7 Trillion to Combat Nature Loss*. United Nations Environment Programme. <https://doi.org/10.59117/20.500.11822/44278>
- UNEP. (2026). *State of Finance for Nature 2026: Nature in the Red—Powering the Trillion Dollar Nature Transition Economy*. <https://wedocs.unep.org/handle/20.500.11822/49119>
- UNEP Copenhagen Climate Centre (UNEP-CCC). (2025). *Webinar: Reimagining Urban Growth: Scaling Nature-based Solutions for Climate Resilient Cities*. <https://unepccc.org/events/webinar-reimagining-urban-growth-scaling-nature-based-solutions-for-climate-resilient-cities/>
- UNEP FI. (2023a). *Nature-Positive Insurance: Evolving Thinking and Practices*. UN Environment Programme Finance Initiative (UNEP FI). <https://www.unepfi.org/industries/insurance/nature-positive-insurance-evolving-thinking-and-practices/>
- UNEP FI. (2023b). *PRB Nature Target Setting Guidance. Principles for Responsible Banking: Guidance for banks* (Principles for Responsible Banking). https://www.unepfi.org/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/PRB-Nature-Target-Setting-Guidance_2023.pdf
- UNEP FI. (2024). *PRB Sector Action Guidance for Nature: Getting Started in Agricultural, Forestry and Mining Sectors* (Principles for Responsible Banking, p. 62). UNEP.
- UNEP FI. (2025a). *Nature-related finance and Indigenous Peoples: Advancing equity to halt and reverse nature loss*. United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative (UNEP FI). <https://www.unepfi.org>
- UNEP FI. (2025b). *Rooted in Risk: Framing Nature-Related Assessments for Insurers* (p. 115). WWF and AIGCC. <https://www.unepfi.org/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/Rooted-in-Risk-1.pdf>
- UNEP FI, & PRI. (2025). *Guidelines and Recommendations for Halting Deforestation* (p. 29). Net-Zero Asset Owner Alliance. <https://www.unepfi.org/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/56-Recommendation-for-halting-deforestation.pdf>
- UNEP-WCMC & UNEP FI. (2024). *Accountability for Nature: Comparison of Nature-Related Assessment and Disclosure Frameworks and Standards* (p. 88). <https://www.unepfi.org/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Accountability-for-Nature.pdf>
- UNEP-WCMC & UNEP FI. (2025). *Accountability for Nature: Comparison of Nature-Related Assessment and Disclosure Frameworks and Standards* (p. 104) [2025 update]. https://www.unepfi.org/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Accountability-for-Nature_V1_2.pdf
- UNGC. (2000). *The Ten Principles of the UN Global Compact*. The Power of Principles. <https://unglobalcompact.org/what-is-gc/mission/principles>
- United Nations. (2022). *Integrity Matters: Net Zero Commitments by Businesses, Financial Institutions, Cities and Regions* (p. 42). United Nations. <https://www.climate-change.org/en/library/integrity-matters-net-zero-commitments-by-businesses-financial-institutions-cities-and-regions/>
- United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative (UNEP FI). (2021). *Recommended Exclusions for Sustainable Blue Economy Financing* (p. 30). UNEP Finance Initiative. https://www.unepfi.org/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Recommended-Exclusions-for-Sustainable-Blue-Economy-Financing_UNEP-FI.pdf
- United Nations Global Risk Report*. (2024). United Nations. <https://www.un.org/en/summit-of-the-future/pact-for-the-future>

- United Nations Statistics Division. (2023). *Global Assessment of Environmental-Economic Accounting and Supporting Statistics 2023*. System of Environmental Economic Accounting. <https://seea.un.org/content/global-assessment-environmental-economic-accounting>
- Unruh, G. C. (2000). Understanding carbon lock-in. *Energy Policy*, 28(12), 817–830. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-4215\(00\)00070-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-4215(00)00070-7)
- van Toor, J., Pilic, D., Schellekens, G., van Oorschot, M., & Kok, M. (2020). *Indebted to Nature: Exploring biodiversity risks for the Dutch financial sector* (PBL report number 4215; p. 44). DNB, the Dutch Central Bank and PBL, Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency.
- Vlasov, M. (2021). In Transition Toward the Ecocentric Entrepreneurship Nexus: How Nature Helps Entrepreneurs Make Ventures More Regenerative Over Time. *Organization & Environment*, 34(4), 559–580. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1086026619831448>
- Vörösmarty, C. J., Rodriguez Osuna, V., Koehler, D. A., Klop, P., Spengler, J. D., Buonocore, J. J., Cak, A. D., Tessler, Z. D., Corsi, F., Green, P. A., & Sánchez, R. (2018). Scientifically assess impacts of sustainable investments. *Science*, 359(6375), 523–525. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aao3895>
- WBA. (2024). *Nature Benchmark 2022-2024*. Nature Benchmark. <https://www.worldbenchmarkingalliance.org/publication/nature/>
- WBCSD. (2017). *Incentives for Natural Infrastructure: Review of Existing Policies, Incentives and Barriers Related to Permitting, Finance and Insurance of Natural Infrastructure* (p. 34). World Business Council for Sustainable Development. <https://www.wbcd.org/Programs/Food-and-Nature/Resources/Incentives-for-Natural-Infrastructure>
- WBCSD. (2021). *Vision 2050: Time to Transform How business can lead the transformations the world needs* (p. 118). World Business Council for Sustainable Development. https://timetotransform.biz/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/WBCSD_Vision_2050_Time-To-Transform.pdf
- WBCSD. (2022). *OP2B (One Planet Business for Biodiversity) 's Framework for Restorative Actions*. World Business Council on Sustainable Development Technical Document. World Business Council on Sustainable Development (WBCSD). https://www.wbcd.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Technical-Document_OP2Bs-Framework-for-Restoration-Actions.pdf
- WBCSD. (2023). *Roadmaps to Nature Positive: Foundations for all businesses* (Roadmaps to Nature Positive). World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD). <https://www.wbcd.org/resources/roadmaps-to-nature-positive-foundations-for-all-businesses/>
- WBCSD. (2024). *Roadmaps to Nature Positive*. World Business Council on Sustainable Development (WBCSD). <https://www.wbcd.org/Imperatives/Nature-Action/Nature-Positive/Roadmaps-to-Nature-Positive>
- WBCSD. (2025, May 22). *Building business capacity on nature*. <https://www.wbcd.org/news/building-business-capacity-on-nature/>
- Weber, O., & Saunders-Hogberg, G. (2018). Water management and corporate social performance in the food and beverage industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 195, 963–977. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.05.269>
- WEF. (n.d.). *Nature Positive Transitions, Actionable pathways to halt and reverse nature loss by 2030*. Retrieved <https://initiatives.weforum.org/nature-positive-transitions/home>
- WEF. (2020). *The Future Of Nature And Business*. https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_The_Future_Of_Nature_And_Business_2020.pdf

- WEF. (2023). *Nature-Positive Industry Sector Transitions*.
<https://www.weforum.org/publications/industry-transitions-to-nature-positive-report-series/>
- WEF. (2024). *Global Risks Report 2024*. World Economic Forum.
<https://www.weforum.org/publications/global-risks-report-2024/>
- WEF. (2025a). *Nature-Positive Corporate Assessment Guide for Financial Institutions* (p. 56).
World Economic Forum.
https://reports.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Nature_Positive_Corporate_Assessment_Guide_for_Financial_Institutions_2025.pdf
- WEF. (2025b). *The Global Risks Report 2025*.
https://reports.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Global_Risks_Report_2025.pdf
- WEF & Oliver Wyman. (2024). *Financing the Nature-Positive Transition: Understanding the Role of Banks, Investors and Insurers. CEO Briefing*. World Economic Forum.
https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Financing_the_nature_positive_transition_2024.pdf
- WEF, & PWC. (2020). *Nature Risk Rising: Why the Crisis Engulfing Nature Matters for Business and the Economy* (p. 36). World Economic Forum and Pricewaterhouse Coopers.
- Weiskopf, S. R., Isbell, F., Arce-Plata, M. I., Di Marco, M., Harfoot, M., Johnson, J., Lerman, S. B., Miller, B. W., Morelli, T. L., Mori, A. S., Weng, E., & Ferrier, S. (2024a). Biodiversity loss reduces global terrestrial carbon storage. *Nature Communications*, *15*(1), 4354.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-47872-7>
- Weiskopf, S. R., Isbell, F., Arce-Plata, M. I., Di Marco, M., Harfoot, M., Johnson, J., Lerman, S. B., Miller, B. W., Morelli, T. L., Mori, A. S., Weng, E., & Ferrier, S. (2024b). Biodiversity loss reduces global terrestrial carbon storage. *Nature Communications*, *15*(1), 4354.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-47872-7>
- Wiedmann, T. O., Schandl, H., Lenzen, M., Moran, D., Suh, S., West, J., & Kanemoto, K. (2013). The material footprint of nations. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *112*(20), 6271–6276. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1220362110>
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., Da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, *3*(1), 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- Willcock, S., Cooper, G. S., Addy, J., & Dearing, J. A. (2023). Earlier collapse of Anthropocene ecosystems driven by multiple faster and noisier drivers. *Nature Sustainability*, *6*(11), 1331–1342. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-023-01157-x>
- Wilson, E. O. (1999). *Biodiversity*. National Academies Press.
- World Bank. (2017). *The World Bank Environmental and Social Framework*. World Bank.
<https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/383011492423734099/pdf/The-World-Bank-Environmental-and-Social-Framework.pdf>
- World Bank. (2018, October 19). *Seychelles Launches World's First Sovereign Blue Bond* [Press release]. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2018/10/29/seychelles-launches-worlds-first-sovereign-blue-bond>
- World Bank. (2022). *NATURE AND DEVELOPMENT Integrating Climate and Nature Action* (p. 132). World Bank.
<https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/0054ddab7bfac0338f255a2ea5d9c32e-0320012022/original/2-Nature-Climate.pdf>
- World Bank, & Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM). (2022). *An Exploration of Nature-related Financial Risks in Malaysia*. World Bank. <https://www.bnm.gov.my/documents/20124/3770663/wb-bnm-2022-report.pdf>

- World Bank Group. (2021). *Nature-Related Financial Risks in Brazil* (Policy Research Working Paper No. 9759).
<https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/105041629893776228/pdf/Nature-Related-Financial-Risks-in-Brazil.pdf>
- World Bank Group. (2023). *Investing in Nature for Green, Resilient, and Inclusive Growth*.
<https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/2845dd98f24558d9b80e4a155d60c78f-0320012022/original/1-Nature-GRID.pdf>
- World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD). (2017). *Landscape Connectivity: A Call to Action* (p. 40). World Business Council for Sustainable Development.
<https://www.wbcsd.org/Programs/Food-and-Nature/Resources/Landscape-Connectivity-A-call-to-action>
- Wüstemann, H., Bonn, A., Albert, C., Bertram, C., Biber-Freudenberger, L., Dehnhardt, A., Döring, R., Elsasser, P., Hartje, V., Mehl, D., Kantelhardt, J., Rehdanz, K., Schaller, L., Scholz, M., Thrän, D., Witing, F., & Hansjürgens, B. (2017). Synergies and trade-offs between nature conservation and climate policy: Insights from the “Natural Capital Germany – TEEB DE” study. *Ecosystem Services*, 24, 187–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.02.008>
- WWF. (n.d.). *BIODIVERSITY RISK FILTER*. Retrieved July 16, 2024, from
<https://riskfilter.org/biodiversity/home>
- WWF, UNEP-WCMC, SGP/ICCA-GSI, LM, TNC, CI, WCS, EP, ILC-S, CM, & IUCN. (2021). *The State of Indigenous Peoples' and Local Communities' Lands and Territories: A technical review of the state of Indigenous Peoples' and Local Communities' lands, their contributions to global biodiversity conservation and ecosystem services, the pressures they face, and recommendations for actions*.
- Wynberg, R. (2023). Biopiracy: Crying wolf or a lever for equity and conservation? *Research Policy*, 52(2), 104674. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2022.104674>
- Xu, Z., Wang, T., Skidmore, A. K., & Lamprey, R. (2024). A review of deep learning techniques for detecting animals in aerial and satellite images. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 128, 103732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2024.103732>
- Zerbini, F. (2017). CSR Initiatives as Market Signals: A Review and Research Agenda. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 146(1), 1–23.
- Zheng, H., Wu, T., Ouyang, Z., Polasky, S., Ruckelshaus, M., Wang, L., Xiao, Y., Gao, X., Li, C., & Daily, G. C. (2023). Gross ecosystem product (GEP): Quantifying nature for environmental and economic policy innovation. *Ambio*, 52(12), 1952–1967.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-023-01948-8>
- Zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Hawkins, I., Lundhede, T., Liu, Q., Thorsen, B. J., & Bull, J. W. (2025). The current state, opportunities and challenges for upscaling private investment in biodiversity in Europe. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 9(3), 515–524.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-024-02632-0>
- zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Howard, M., Bennun, L., Addison, P. F. E., Bull, J. W., Loveridge, R., Pollard, E., & Starkey, M. (2022). Are corporate biodiversity commitments consistent with delivering ‘nature-positive’ outcomes? A review of ‘nature-positive’ definitions, company progress and challenges. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 379, 134798.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134798>

—